

**Social Media in SMEs: The Impact of Experience of Gender
difference on Muslim Entrepreneurs in the Food Industry in the
UK**

**A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration**

**Mudassar Sohail
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(Resubmission)**

DECLARATION

This thesis is the result of my own research and has not been accepted nor concurrently submitted in candidature for any other degree.

Mudassar Sohail

September 2021

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated with respect, humility and love to my parents,
Mr Inayat Ullah Malik & Miss Hameedan Bibi
and beloved siblings.

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I express my profound thanks to Almighty ALLAH, who enabled me to complete this study.

The researcher invokes peace for the noblest of all and model of mankind Sayyed-Ul-Mursaleen and Khatam-Un-Nabiyyen Muhammad (peace be upon him), the last prophet of Allah.

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Abstract

Social media has become a prominent force in society and business globally in less than twenty years. Historically, it is a marketing medium and entrepreneurs are impressed by the innovative advancement of communications developments, specifically food-related SMEs by the social media platforms. Social media has now become the necessity of every single business and like the internet. The research explored the Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences and considered the impacts of gender on social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. The opportunity-based theory of entrepreneurship was conceptualised, and the framework for this research developed. The focus was placed on how Muslim entrepreneurs employ social media to form the marketing opportunity, decide the marketing opportunity, and exploit it. This study selected a mixed-method approach and followed an exploratory sequential research design to conduct the research. The research, therefore, collected both qualitative as well as quantitative data. A mixed-method approach was applied to collect the data consistent with the research objectives. Phase one, in-depth semi-structured interviews were undertaken with Muslim entrepreneurs and data analysed to explore their experiences towards social media marketing in the small and medium-sized food business in the UK. Interview findings then informed to construct the survey questionnaire. Phase two, an online questionnaire will be sent to Muslim entrepreneurs to elicit their response to several social media utilisation questions across the UK. In phase one, 20 in-depth semi-structured interviews conducted with Muslim entrepreneurs, and in phase two, 120 responses collected from Muslim entrepreneurs in an online survey. To analyse the collected data, this study used NVivo software to analyse qualitative data using thematic analysis technique while SPSS Version No. 26 was used to analyse the quantitative data. Findings reveal several different experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs' employment of social media marketing as an opportunity. This research provided significant insights for the academic researcher, entrepreneurs, food businesses, SMEs, and marketers. Muslim entrepreneurs learn social media as a marketing tool and techniques that enable them to communicate and engage with customers. This study explored the benefits and responses (e.g., elements of social media marketing, entrepreneurial opportunity, and gender experiences). It reveals that gender influences Muslim entrepreneurs to select social media platforms differently. Social media marketing helped food SMEs learn communication ways, form marketing strategies, interact with customers and increase brand awareness. Thus, this research contributes to the knowledge of consumer behaviour in the use of social media. From a practical viewpoint, this research suggested entrepreneurial marketing strategies effectively to design social media marketing and used, strengthening communication and relationship with customers.

Key words: social media, social media marketing, gender, entrepreneurship, Muslim Entrepreneurs.

GLOSSARY OF ABBREVIATIONS/TERMS

SM	Social Media
SMM	Social Media Marketing
SMC	Social Media Communication
SMI	Social Media Interaction
BA	Brand Awareness
EE	Entrepreneurial Experiences
BT	Business Types
CFB	Customer Feedback
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
RQ	Research Question

LIST OF PAPERS PUBLISHED IN ASSOCIATION WITH THIS THESIS

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Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Overview of Chapter

The first chapter of this study introduces the research and the study structure. The chapter is divided into eight different sections. The first section of the study presents the chapter overview. The second section explores the background of the research. This part of the study briefly illustrates current knowledge on social media marketing, entrepreneurship, gender and the Halal food industry in the UK. The third section of the study explains the rationale of the research. The fourth section of the study explains the complete structure of this study. This section is followed by academic benefits and practical benefits from the study. The seventh section sets the research aim(s), question(s) and objective(s). This section briefly illustrates the main research question and the research sub-questions and introduces the objective of the study. Lastly, the study presents an overview of the applied research methodology.

1.2 Background of Study

Entrepreneurs are known as one of the most significant driving forces of economies (Dutta, Roy and Sobel, 2009). This entrepreneurial view is change inevitable by entrepreneurs and respond to changes that have developed outside themselves and perceive change as a new opportunity (Drucker 1986). This is possibly why entrepreneurship and innovations are stated together in the literature (Windrum & Koch, 2008) because entrepreneurs, as it is in the definition of Drucker (1986), must be people who have adopted a business model that must constantly be looking for opportunity. Opportunity identification is an essential element of entrepreneurship; Shane and Venkataraman (2000) defined entrepreneurship as “*the discovery and exploitation of profitable opportunities*” (p. 217). While successful entrepreneurship is “*the discovery, creation, and exploitation of opportunities to create future goods and services that sustain the natural and/or communal environment and provide development gain for others*” (Patzelt and Shepherd, 2011, p. 632).

The 21st century's most significant development is the discovery of internet technologies. The internet technologies development, similar to many other subjects, has changed the styles of running businesses. The widespread use of social media can be revealed as the best example of this development. In the last few years, social media employment immensely developed and at present, an approximation of 2.7 billion people worldwide are mainly employing social media in their daily lives (Kemp, 2017).

The significant rise in social media uses changed marketing behaviours, resulting in a substantial surge in advertising on social media (Kumar et al., 2016). However, social media considered the latest discovery that brings people's communication to a very different dimension. Social media (SM) is "*a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content*" (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010, p,61). Social media changed the communication patterns in which people communicate with each other. To exploit social media opportunities, entrepreneurs have benefited businesses from this management, such as marketing (Alalwan et al., 2017; Misirlis & Vlachopoulou, 2018).

The exploration of social media phenomena has been an interest of academics and practitioners, especially in the recent modern era. Entrepreneur employs social media for various marketing purposes and reasons which is key to their business actions (Olanrewaju et al., 2020). Moreover, entrepreneurs use social media primarily to market their product/services. Employment of these social media platforms improved their businesses (Tajvidi and Karami, 2017), which is key to an entrepreneur's business success. However, there are few studies on social media that are not making a direct link to entrepreneurship. Alternatively, this study tends to be comprehensive and specific to a particular domain like social media marketing

(Misirlis & Vlachopoulou, 2018; Alalwan et al., 2017) and country-specific (Abed, Dewivedi, and William, 2015) such as the UK.

Although social media defined as a means of communication, social media platforms have also been seen as an entrepreneurial opportunity and have become a trading hub without boundaries. Therefore, for entrepreneurs who can recognise this opportunity, social media has converted it into a set of tools to reach existing customers. Also, the social media evolution allowed entrepreneurs to use social media as one of their marketing tools. Small and medium-sized (SMEs) businesses are relatively fascinating in social media marketing and have significant worth exploring, specifically when social media platforms are considered affordable as a marketing tool for SMEs in the food business. However, there is still needed to know what trends are being followed in the same manner by SMEs. Few studies shed light on the social media features and challenges as a marketing tool for SMEs in the food business. It would benefit SMEs in recognising what types of social media marketing help their businesses and which specific practices applied to accomplishing achievement.

At present, this research opportunity enhanced a rich literature keen on marketing practices in food-related SMEs. Taking marketing purposes into account, using social media as a marketing tool has increased the SMEs' sales in the food-related business. However, as social media is a known newly emerged phenomenon, thoughtful its features as a marketing tool would remain a challenge for entrepreneurs.

Having said that, social media is a newly emerged phenomenon, particularly in today's time, the undervaluing of its power, and believed that social media marketing is the main problem that justifies researching, mainly it is potential of a marketing tool for SMEs. SMEs are the backbone of the UK economy; at present, 6 million SMEs are running and representing 99% of all UK businesses (Wunsch, 2020). According to the research, SME's play a massive role in countries like the United Kingdom, accumulating more than one-third of industrial

employment (Smit and Watkins, 2012). Similarly, it was observed that in 1979, the SME's market consisted of 2.5 million SME's in the UK as compared to 5.2 million in 2014 (Burns, 2016). The statistics showed that 7000 SME's out of which 99% of the UK businesses generated 60.1% employment and 6.6% of the turnover of £231 billion (Burns, 2016). Although all these statistics are quite appealing, there are, just like any other business, drawbacks for opting for SME's.

However, as stated above, SMEs are still not using social media marketing widely, even though it offers SMEs many opportunities in marketing with a little cost. Similarly, as a cost-effective marketing tool, social media enables entrepreneurs to position their businesses and compete with large businesses in marketing (Kaplan, 2012). According to Anwar and Daniel (2016), social media helps businesses engage and identify ethnic markets, which are hard to reach through mainstream media like radio, TV and newspapers. Thus, this study attempts to explore the experience of male and female entrepreneurship using social media marketing. British Muslims are chosen particularly as a unit of analysis in the study since they are running SMEs in the UK, and one can observe the experience of gender on Muslim entrepreneurship.

This exploratory sequential mixed-methods research design (Creswell, 2013) examines the experiences of British Muslim entrepreneurs employing social media marketing in food SMEs in the UK. The current study recognised that British Muslim entrepreneurs are in the food industry especially (e.g. fast food, takeaway, restaurant, and online bloggers). According to Anwar and Daniel (2016), one research was undertaken on the online retail ethnic business, which has indicated that ethnic businesses are employing online media entering into another industry. They have indicated and demanded more research exploration on ethnic entrepreneurship, such as British Muslim entrepreneurs on the emerging ethnic industry such as British Halal food.

Thus, this study explicitly looking at Halal food SMEs run by British Muslims would make it significant research to explore their entrepreneurial experiences in utilising social media marketing. Furthermore, unlike conventional marketing, social media presented an equal opportunity to the entrepreneurs to run business, engage, and identify customers more effectively (Smith, Smith and Shaw, 2017). Hence, the researcher needs to investigate the social media platforms dynamic features of the food industry to measure how social media platforms play roles and their effect on Muslim entrepreneurs.

Presently, this research tried to provide a brief research background by shedding lights on entrepreneurship, food-related SMEs and social media marketing.

1.3 Rationale of the Study

Muslim entrepreneurship being ethnic entrepreneurship, the fastest growing business in the UK (Haq, 2015). Social media has changed the consumer's behaviour and transferred from traditional marketing channels to get information about the product or brand (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Accordingly, social media marketing has displayed its main influences on the behaviour of consumers (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). For that reason, Batra and Keller (2016) argued that significant interest for entrepreneurs to assimilate the marketing communication concepts by social media. From this aspect, the use of social media enabled the entrepreneurs to communicate, reach out, and relate to customers and target groups to enhance the business confidence that provides products or services (Safko, 2010).

In addition, significantly used social media platforms, i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and Twitter, have enabled the entrepreneurs to stand in competition with big organisations for marketing and customer engagement (Qualman, 2010). For this main reason, entrepreneurs consider that social media is a powerful marketing tool to communicate and engage with customers. Lister (2018) reported that more than 50 million entrepreneurs created Facebook

business pages, a similar trend seen on another leading social media platforms, Instagram, on 50% of users following social media business profiles (Pickard-Whitehead, 2018). From a business prospect, social media offered truly enormous opportunities for entrepreneurs to practice social media as a marketing tool; it enables them to increase brand awareness, the services and products they provide.

Furthermore, Smith, Smith and Shaw (2017) acknowledged the several differences between offline marketing and social media marketing, the new shift of social media provides cost-effective and innovative ways to engage with consumers, unlike offline marketing. Nonetheless, the current literature on ethnic marketing used entrepreneurial offline marketing activities in the context of brick and mortar businesses such as takeaway, restaurant, clothing, grocery superstore, information technology and accountancy firms (Catney and Sabate, 2015; Basu, 2011 & Altinay and Altinay, 2008). Similarly, other several studies undertaken on the social media marketing impacts on to the consumer's behaviour, not many studies have undertaken on the social media platforms, i.e. Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat and Twitter (Chu and Cheng, 2020) in the context of gender experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs. This demands the investigation of social media marketing experiences by ethnic entrepreneurs such as Muslim entrepreneurs and how they employ this marketing on their SMEs, especially in the food businesses. Additionally, several marketing managers feel unsure about social media marketing outcomes and suitable techniques for employing social media in their marketing activities (Kumar et al., 2016).

The primary aim behind the Muslim entrepreneurs' selection is considered a principal unit of analysis in the current study. The Muslim population in the UK is a composition of many ethnic entrepreneurs such as British Pakistanis, British Indians and British Bangladeshis. British Muslim entrepreneurs' selection is part of the worldwide Muslim consumer segment that refers

to the overall growing halal markets across the globe concerning expendable revenue (Temporal, 2011), entry of internet, and mobile phone use (Wiest & Eltantawy, 2015). Muslim Council of Britain (2013) stated that the ethnic population, such as Muslims in Europe and particularly in the UK, shows progress increment in the socio-economic development and buying power. The United Kingdom is the leading Muslim populated states in Europe, counting approximately 3 million people. It is reported that the accumulated spending power of Muslim people is £20.5 billion in the UK, and their annual contribution of £31 billion to the UK economy (Muslim Council of Britain, 2013). Shelina Jan Mohamed, Vice-President of Ogilvy Noor, stated that *"British Muslims is a segment crying out to be served"* and described them *"as a young, brand conscious, well-connected and increasingly affluent consumer segment"* (Muslim Council of Britain, 2013, cited in Wright, 2013, p.8).

Moreover, the minority society of Muslim was considered one of the most prominent ethnic groups in the UK and recognised themselves as both Muslims and British (Ali, 2015). The next generation, such as second and third, also recognise their identity as British Asian Muslims and provide less preference to their home country identity (Jacobson, 2006, and Hamid 2011). Jacobson (2006) further stated that British Muslims are social media and mobile technology people and their lifestyles spent following British consumer culture while practising the values of Islam.

1.4 Thesis Layout/Structure

The study encompassed six chapters that are demonstrated and summarised below (see Figure 1) following other important components of the thesis: abstract, acknowledgement, table of content, list of figures and tables, references and appendices.

Chapter 1: Introduction

The introduction chapter of the study provides details about the study background, the rationale of the study research, significance of the study, research aims and objectives, overview of research methodology and the layout of the thesis. In the end, an overall summary of the chapter is provided.

Chapters 2: Literature Review

The literature chapter of the study provides the entrepreneurship literature of the study, followed by a comprehensive literature review of other important areas of research. This important area of literature includes the emergence of entrepreneurship, digital entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial traits and Muslim entrepreneurship. The study then presents a literature review on gender, gender entrepreneurship, gender and social media, gender differences, theories of gender, social media, social media marketing, and entrepreneurship theories. In the end, the research presents the conceptual research framework.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The methodology chapter of the study describes research philosophies, research approach, research design, research strategy, data collection methods, sampling procedure, ethical issues, data analysis methods, bias and research limitations, reliability and validity of the research, and at the end, a summary of the whole methodology chapter.

Chapter 4: Qualitative Findings

Chapter 4 of the study provides qualitative findings from the in-depth interviews. It also provides the thematic analyses of data collected from the interviews according to the study's emerging themes through NVivo software. At the end key summary of the interviews' findings is provided.

Chapter 5: Quantitative Findings

Chapter 5 of the study provides quantitative findings from an online questionnaire. It provides descriptive analyses of data collected from Muslim entrepreneurs through an online questionnaire. The descriptive analysis presents the descriptive statistics of research constructs, incorporating empirical questions, standard deviation, mean value, and minimum and maximum for each measurement item. Also, two-way ANOVA analyses will be conducted to find the impact of gender and relationship between both independent (SMU, SMC, SMI, BA and CFB) variables and dependent (gender, ethnicity and business types) variables, and bivariate correlation analysis will also be performed to test the hypotheses through SPSS software version 26. according to the emerged themes from this study. At the end key summary of the questionnaire's findings is provided.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

Chapter six of the research concludes the study and presents the results against the study's objectives presented in chapter one. This is followed by results from the predictable variables, testing of hypotheses, similarities and differences among Muslim entrepreneurs. The study then presents the main lesson learned (research contribution) from the research and its limitations. Moreover, research provides the direction for future research and the managerial implication from the study. Finally, the chapter presents a summary of the chapter.

Figure 1: Structure of The Thesis

1.5 Academic Benefits from the study

To date, and best of academic knowledge, this is one of the few studies which explores the entrepreneurial phenomena with the lens of social perspective focussing on gender. As such, gender informs entrepreneurial understanding as a cultural value-based phenomenon. At present, a large amount of research exploring gender and entrepreneurship in the business context, the relationship considered less attention by food-related SMEs and social media marketing utilisation. However, this study is an in-depth investigation of entrepreneurs on social media marketing and gender-specific phenomenon.

Meyer (2018) suggested that females experience dissimilar barriers and challenges than their male counterparts; consequently, mainly gender-oriented research of entrepreneurship could help develop and improve female entrepreneurship. Richter et al., (2013) social media marketing employment and its importance must be considered significant more than simple technology adoption. It is argued that utilisation of social media marketing has several impacts on entrepreneurial decisions, such as entrepreneurs employing social media marketing benefiting their businesses through different marketing activities, which aim to increase brand awareness and communication. Thus, this research contributes to the current literature by undertaking an in-depth analysis and highlighting the entrepreneurial experiences of social media marketing in food SMEs.

1.6 Practical Benefits from the study

This research provides several important practical benefits that may enhance businesses' entrepreneurial knowledge and marketing management within food-related SMEs in the UK. Firstly, the impact of gender on entrepreneurial actions and activities might contribute to improving marketing strategies. Especially segmentation strategies and market identifications of food-related SMEs may be improved by considering niche market requirements. Paulauskaite et al. (2017) argued that the demand for customised and authentic products increased by customers; advanced marketing strategies might enhance business performance. Secondly, as indicated in this study, entrepreneurship creates opportunities within the food industry in which entrepreneurs can use their benefits, particularly for marketing their products. Thirdly, the Entrepreneurial view on social media marketing has vital recommendations for business owners/managers on what social media platforms significantly impact food SMEs. To employ powerful social media platforms to initiate the marketing activity for the food business, the manager should consider the social media platform's accessible features.

Additionally, the current study points out the employment of social media as a marketing tool that has enabled the entrepreneurs to rich their marketing expertise and increase the opportunities in communication, interaction, brand awareness, receive positive and negative feedback on the product and respond to the feedback. The British Muslim consumer's growth is a large part of the market, not limited to British Muslims. Moreover, marketing expertise under which gender influences entrepreneurial actions could inform why some businesses in the food industry fail. Therefore, this study provides social media marketing students and potential entrepreneurs to become fully experienced in utilising social media marketing techniques and coping with the challenges.

1.7 Research Aim(s) and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to examine whether gender has any impact on Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards the use of social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. To explore the research aim(s), the objectives of this study are given as follows:

1. To explore the role of social media platforms usage by Muslim entrepreneurs in food businesses.
2. To investigate social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK.
3. To find out the gender experience of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs using social media marketing for their food businesses.

Based on the above research objectives, this research seeks out the answers to the research questions given as follows respectively:

RQ1: What are the roles of social media platforms used by Muslim entrepreneurs in the food industry?

RQ2: What are the social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK?

RQ3: What are the different gender experiences of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employing social media marketing for their food businesses?

1.8 Approach of the Study (Methodology)

This study explores whether gender impacts Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards the social media marketing uses for their food SMEs in the UK.

Targeting Muslim entrepreneurs running food businesses in the Kingdom was deemed ideal as these entrepreneurs would be key stakeholders in this study, and therefore, their opinions would be valuable. Muslim entrepreneurs contribute significantly to the halal food industry, so their views are precisely relevant and make Muslim entrepreneurs a valuable sample. The Muslim entrepreneurs' experiences of using social media marketing would also help the research practitioners design a marketing strategy for SMEs in the UK food business. In a similar manner but large in numbers Muslim entrepreneurs were targeted through an online survey to enhance the analysis and generalise the interview findings because as such entrepreneurs whose opinions and views were deemed significant in the research subject and matter, their experiences on social media marketing employment contribute to food-related SMEs in the UK.

In this study, the research approach and following research design were influenced by the subject, the research aims and objectives. This research mainly follows a mixed-methods approach, subsequently two different research phases. In phase one, in-depth semi-structured interviews will be undertaken with Muslim entrepreneurs, and data analysed help explore their experiences towards using social media marketing in the small and medium-sized food business in the UK. Interview findings then will inform to construct the survey questionnaire. In phase two, a questionnaire was sent to Muslim entrepreneurs running food SMEs to elicit their response to several questions across the UK and validate and generalise their findings. The online questionnaire includes close ended self-completed questions that will follow the standardise list, enabling the researcher to ascertain the point answers (Maylor & Blackmon, 2005) of Muslim entrepreneurs. This online questionnaire is vital in acquiring quantitative data, which will be employed descriptively following the mixed research method. The research, therefore, collected both qualitative as well as quantitative data. The mixed-methods approach seen as highly pertinent for undertaking this study, a point further elaborated upon in the methodology chapter of this thesis.

Having said that, the research moved to the next chapter, a chapter of the literature review.

Chapter 2 - Literature Review

In this chapter, a conceptual research framework of the study presented, and the literature mainly explained by including the academic concepts and reasonable pieces of evidence collected from many different literary resources. Furthermore, this chapter will review the literature on entrepreneurship, digital entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial traits. This is followed by the literature review on gender, social media marketing, Halal food and the UK context. Lastly, entrepreneurship theories will be discussed, and the proposed research framework presented.

2.1 The Emergence of Entrepreneurship

Despite massive research conducted on this genre, the context and content of this phenomenon of *entrepreneurship* remain conflicting, stratified and electric, and making is somewhat ambiguously robust to elaborate in detail its historical theories. However, that does not isolate it from being explained. The existence of this concept stems from the conjunctions of various resources (Urban, 2013). The term entrepreneurship introduced in 1759 by Richard Cantillon and defined as “*the entrepreneur is a specialist taking risk*” (Casson et al., 2009, p. 3). Schumpeter (1934) described that an entrepreneur is seen as an innovator vital for economic growth. He stated that the entrepreneur creates new businesses and contributes to significant structural changes in the economy.

Shedding light at some historical work, the entrepreneurial theory was developed by non-linear changes such as competition, globalisation, demand curves and the discovery of new mechanisms etc. They were presenting new conceptualisation and meanings for this concept. With time, by the mid-twentieth century, the concept of entrepreneurial behaviour was defined by many economic-based approaches. Numerous psychologists and sociologists initiated this behavioural factor towards entrepreneurship; Max Weber (1930) was one of the initial key

exhibitors interested in this concept (Urban, 2013). He developed a value system in which businessmen and businesswomen performed as innovators, self-reliant individuals with responsibilities as business leaders gave a source of power that would influence entrepreneurial behaviour (Urban, 2013). when talking about entrepreneurial behaviour, the light sheds on the work of McClelland (1961), who argues that an entrepreneur is individual exercising control over this work process and production that is not just limited to his consumption (McClelland, 1961).

However, in recent time, this topic received significant attention and expansion (Harrison, Paul, Burnard, 2016). Entrepreneurship and entrepreneur both terms used interchangeably. Numerous scholars defined the term differently. The definition of entrepreneurship even has become complicated in modern theories of economics. According to Shane and Venkataraman (2000) entrepreneurship only exists when there are entrepreneurial opportunities. Entrepreneurial opportunities mean such circumstances that are suitable to introduce new products, services and sold them on profit. Shane and Venkataraman (2000) further argued that there are two fundamental assumptions to successfully exploit the entrepreneurial opportunity (a) the individual must be able to recognise the existence of such opportunity and confident that it has value (b) the potential entrepreneur must be willing to exploit the entrepreneurial opportunity.

This literature will narrow the concept of entrepreneurship to small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) in the UK. This widely consumed term was coined by the European Commission as 'small and medium-sized enterprise' in 1996. These are organisations that employ less than 250 employees (Burns, 2016). However, the terminology of SME has been widely used but lacks a standard definition. This is because of the geographic location of SME and the legislations of the specific countries influencing various SME definitions. According to the research, SME's play a massive role in countries like the United Kingdom and the United

States, accumulating more than one-third of industrial employment (Smit and Watkins, 2012). Similarly, it was observed that in 1979, the SME's market consisted of 2.5 million SME's in the UK as compared to 5.2 million in 2014 (Burns, 2016). Not only that, but the statistics also showed that 7000 SME's out of which 99% of the businesses operating within the UK generated 60.1% employment and 46.7% turnover (Burns, 2016). The statistics also show that sole proprietors and self-employed business are the new trends in the country. 75.6% of all the UK businesses comprise only self-employed partners that are generating 17.3% of UK employment and 6.6% of the turnover of £231 billion approximately (Burns, 2016). Although all these statistics are quite appealing, there are other business drawbacks for opting for SME's. In 2008, Cressy presented framework that smaller businesses and firms have higher failure than large businesses (as cited in Burns, 2016).

Likewise, the productivity for smaller firms tends to be far less than the large ones, even when monitored within the same industry. In Europe, it was observed that the businesses and firms comprising of 200 employees or less have a lower level, like 55% of the productivity as compared to the large firms employing more than 1000 employees (Eurostat, 2009). The research indicated these differences are mainly due to lack of capital backing and because these SME's provide lower pay to employees with poor working conditions and more significant accident rates.

Conversely, it will not be suitable to consider all SME's as unproductive and poor employers because these businesses have major diversity of practice (Burns, 2016). In the European context, the SME's contributed about 67.1% of employment and 57.6% towards GDP (Eurostat, 2009). The EU economies heavily rely on SME's, especially in their service sector such as hotels, Catering, retailing, wholesaling and construction (Burns, 2016). Between 2007 to 2012, SME's in Asia contributed 66% of employment and 38% towards GDP. Hence, it is sufficient to say that the importance of SME's in every economy is thriving.

Although entrepreneurship is complicated, however, it is a significant contributor to economic development. Entrepreneurship enables the formation of new business. Consequently, it becomes a source of wealth in the economy, increases employment opportunities in the country, increases productivity and enhances innovation (Audretsch and Peña-Legazkue, 2012). However, the impact entrepreneurship has on economic development are contingent on new businesses. Not any business can contribute to economic development. The newly formed business must be innovative and must have the potential to grow (Shane, 2009).

There are three key reasons, which enrich the belief that entrepreneurship encourages economic growth. Firstly, Acs & Armington (2002) argued that it supports competition, resulting in better efficiency and productivity and employment growth. Secondly, according to Acs et al. (2008), entrepreneurship enables “*knowledge spill overs*” which becomes a key source of entrepreneurial opportunities, which leads to innovative start-up businesses. Thirdly, entrepreneurship creates vast numbers of enterprises and boosts the variety of businesses in a location. Thus, this type of diversity influences economic growth (Audretsch, Keilbach and Lehmann, 2006).

2.1.1 Digital Entrepreneurship

Digital entrepreneurship is a newly evolved technique that can be pursued as “*new venture opportunities presented by new media and internet technologies*” grab global attention (Davidson and Vaast, 2010, p. 8). Digital entrepreneurship is similar to traditional entrepreneurship. However, the key dissimilarity occurs because in digital entrepreneurship, “*some or all of the entrepreneurial venture takes place digitally instead of in more traditional formats*” (Hair et al., 2012, p. 3). A digital entrepreneur is an entity that produces and carries essential organisational tasks and activities, for example, marketing, management, using information and communication technologies (Hair et al., 2012) and emerging digital technologies such as online channels, smartphone and artificial intelligence. The most recent

development of digital infrastructures such as social media networking channels (Fischer & Reuber, 2011) provided the direction in very united ways of practising entrepreneurship (Aldrich, 2014). Digital entrepreneurship developed traditional business relationships and given a new sense of running a business in electronic businesses (Schwens and Kabst, 2009). The significant growth of digital entrepreneurship, precisely information and communication technology, proved helpful in expanding internationally (Clacher and Hagendroff, 2012).

2.1.2 Muslim Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurs that are parts of Islamic entrepreneurship (Gumusay, 2015) have known as Muslim entrepreneurs. In a global business environment, culture and religion have an essential role, pushing Islamic entrepreneurship as a key research topic (Ramadani et al., 2015). Religion is also a key factor among many other factors which influence the intention of individuals. Religion plays an essential role in influencing the values, behaviour, and attitude of individuals and their lifestyle (Oukil, 2013) and the activity of entrepreneurs to decide for entrepreneurship or choose a job.

The religion 'Islam' emphasises the significance of being a businessperson as someone that improves society. However, there is a need to research religion and its influence (Basu & Altinay, 2012), notably on Muslim entrepreneurship. This view was further supported by Gumusay (2015) that Islamic entrepreneurship studies with a marketing orientation lens are needed.

According to Islam, life consists of all human life parts: social, economic, political, and moral, where all factors are linked. According to Islamic principles, Muslim entrepreneurs are bound to set up their businesses, also known as Shari'ah law (Ramadani et al., 2015). Additionally, for Muslim, prohibition and the permitted of whole things are mentioned in the Shari'ah law. Muslims must perform three duties: responsibility for the Almighty ALLAH, responsibility between human beings, and responding to the world.

Syahida et al. (2013) stated that running a business and following Islamic principles are measured as worship. It believes that all Muslim undertaking entrepreneurial activities may be classified as Muslim entrepreneurs, which is not true. Few Muslims abide and follow the Islamic principle of laws, few Muslims only follow the partial act, and few other Muslims do not abide or follow the Islamic laws fully (Oukil, 2013). As per the UK study, many Muslims do not follow the Islamic laws in their business and do sale prohibited things such as alcohol and pork (Basu & Altinay, 2012).

It does not involve those activities that are known to harm society (Ramadani et al., 2016). In contrast, Muslim entrepreneurship presents a new way to imitate entrepreneurship significantly (Gumusay, 2015). Muslim entrepreneurship practices might be applied, Islamic principles considered as encouragement, and a positive attitude can be a replacement (Gumusay, 2015). Muslim entrepreneurship may and should allow us to reflect more broadly on the role of religion in entrepreneurship and how both a specific scriptural source and a supernatural being provides direction and suggestions.

Islam invites all Muslims to work hard and do business activities based on Shari'ah law, which is considered good deeds. Islamic entrepreneurship can incorrectly be assumed entrepreneurship for Muslims or Muslim mainstream states (Gumusay, 2015). In general, Muslim entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship are favoured by institutional aspects that there is not essential to be mainly Muslim populated state, products and services to be focused on merely Muslims (Gumusay, 2015). The firm or entrepreneur must be a Muslim to run the Muslim entrepreneurship as it includes the religious lens.

At the same time, an entrepreneurial practise may align with Islamic principles, as Muslim entrepreneurs believe in and practice for God, which accepts religion solely. However, it cannot be assumed that Muslim entrepreneurship has no perceptiveness for non-Mulsim (Gumusay, 2015).

It is argued that in recent time Islamic entrepreneurship (Muslim Entrepreneurship) is emerged popular to other similar terms such as Islamic economic and Islamic finance (Gumusay, 2015). Furthermore, Muslim entrepreneurship is noticeably tremendous and applicable to marketing. Therefore, it emerges to be a marketing-oriented technique instead of theologically or academically rigorous (Gumusay, 2015); this enhances Muslim entrepreneurship (Ramadani et al., 2016).

2.1.3 Entrepreneurial Traits

All entrepreneurs have certain traits in common. An entrepreneur depends on the intrinsic nature of features instead of a rational process (Cunningham & Lischeron, 1991). Entrepreneurs can figure out the entrepreneurial risks against the financial income they receive from employment (Campbell, 1992). Entrepreneurs have specific natural traits that help them to become successful (Bolton & Thompson, 2000). Entrepreneurs hold more energy as compared to the ordinary person.

Ang and Chang (2004) entrepreneurs are meticulous and capable of overcoming hindrances. He further stated that entrepreneurs are always pursuing opportunities and solutions. Entrepreneurs are good in internal discipline and confidence. Learned (1992) stated that entrepreneurs are observant and can quickly recognise innovative business plans, innovative markets, innovative products and decide whether the new business venture is viable. Generally, entrepreneurs are the head step people in the business and managed to inspire others. Entrepreneurs choose to arrange persons to perform what they need and provide direction to those who work under them (Neider, 1987).

Individual strength to focus on the new entrepreneurial opportunity and capable spirit is exceptionally vital for the entrepreneur. In order to control the risk of beginning a new venture, an individual need to be assured that it will achieve business success. The individual cannot take the chance of risk if it doubts with its confidence. They might not be capable of handling

the barriers and difficulties of beginning a new company. An individual who has robust self-control and focus will be capable of shouldering the responsibilities more effortlessly. People who hold such focus excel and encourage essential effort to launch the new business successfully. Cohen (1980) argued that entrepreneurs are born and not made. Psychologist Alan Jacobowitz expressed one such opinion. In a research interview conducted using over 500 entrepreneurs, Jacobowitz observed some popular character features an entrepreneur holds. Cohen (1980) stated those character features: independent, loners, restless, seeking new challenges, and most extremely self-confident.

Several factors influence the entrepreneurs, such as different perceptions, values, individual characteristics, environment and background (Krueger & Brazil, 1994). Entrepreneurs are risk takers, and risk always relies on the understanding of external circumstances and conditions. Moreover, entrepreneurs approach differently to their risk perception (Brindley, 2005).

Study shows that entrepreneurs are more expert at ascertaining potential of risk and maintaining the uncertainties linked with risk. Timmons (1994) inform that entrepreneurs' primary characteristics are to take risks. Entrepreneurs frequently get benefit from unexploited entrepreneurial opportunities, and therefore, they essentially control risk efficiently. Cox & Jennings (1995) entrepreneurs must be resilient and have a strong understanding. Sexton (1990) argued that an entrepreneur is an idealist who formulate a roadmap of its business, which supports and leads business success.

In order to grow, entrepreneurs would efficiently deliver business ideas to their workers and shareholders. The entrepreneur must have clear intentions of where they want to go. An entrepreneur's encouragement may have for a business primarily be trailed up with constant consideration and aim. Bird (1988) illustrated that entrepreneurs are goal-oriented and focus on achieving their goals. Entrepreneurs hold specific kind of traits that enable them as an

entrepreneur. They have colossal strength: visionaries, risk-takers, exploit opportunities, hard worker and confidence.

2.2 Gender Perspective

Gender recognised as a cultural and social conception that differentiates a male from a female and, therefore, illustrates how women and men collaborate (Vanessa, 2017). It is meaningful that "*Gender is a social construction of sex where characteristics are ascribed to men and women, which underpin notions of femininity and masculinity*" (Marlow & Patton, 2005, p. 717). Gender is a societal state that may be clinch irrespective of biological sex (Marlow & Patton, 2005) and depends on what is made rather than (Ahl & Marlow, 2012).

As per the basic construction of a community with their relation to the surroundings, gender is universally claimed with an individual's sex; instead, it fails to incorporate the importance of behavioural rather than biological and physical appearance (Vanessa, 2017). The finding of these prospects is frequently faced with the innovative demands of the culture and can differ accordingly (Gupta, 2000). The researcher argues that since *gender* has been given considerable visibility and investigation in social reality since recent times, it was 'non-existent' (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004).

The prodigy gender made its first official introduction in the scientific disclosure (Rubin, 1975), expressing 'gender-sex systems' highlighting the processes, pattern behaviours and relationships by which every society alters biological sexuality as per human activity (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Furthermore, the terms gender was then incorporated into various social studies globally, such as *the academic studies of American Feminism* (Nicholson, 1994). The grammatical connotation of the terms gender is the social classification of considering human beings as two and only two types of individuals; men and women (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004).

The two concepts of 'male and female' together as a gender are the norm by which individuals perceive and represent themselves in society (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Likewise, gender meaning, historically and culturally situated, they are different according to their gender relationships. Contextualised, established, and representation of the gender relations associate a circumscribed object to man and woman in any culture. The prototypes of maleness and femaleness always represent the differences and observed the order of language (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004).

2.2.1 Gender and Entrepreneurship

Extending on the debate of gender and entrepreneurship, according to Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio (2004) women opt to run the business as per the two significant factors; compulsion and attraction. Compulsions terms from the intrinsic need of a female are earning money or increase their household income to survive rather than opting to work. Alternatively, attraction belongs to the other continuum of compulsion; women desire to undertake entrepreneurship as an optimistic act chosen by women who perceive it.

As per the studies of Krueger and Brazeal (1994), encouraging environments, political and social support, leadership, and a team essence can enhance the entrepreneurship activity amongst both men and women in the society. The literature on entrepreneurship argues on men possessing strong and forceful characteristics, vital for business success instead of the other gender (Vanessa, 2017). However, studies also reflect that active social and family relations, parental aspirations and inclination to help amongst women can significantly contribute to maintaining emotional relations by female entrepreneurs (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994).

The literature on gender and entrepreneurship looks into the mythological aspect of masculinity attached with entrepreneur or enterprise (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). The literature argues that the essential characteristics of entrepreneurship derived from the mythological figure of a mercurial personality; open-minded, strong-headed and sharp and pragmatic (Bruni,

Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Therefore, these features argued to reside relatively in the domains of a male individual and, significantly debated, to be uncertain when associated with females (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004).

This is because gender assigns activity and proactivity to the males and attaches adaption and flexibility with the females. Literature states that historically, entrepreneurship lies in the symbolic domain of the male (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004; Collinson and Hearn, 1994, 1996) and, as Connell (1995) notes, hegemonic masculinity is also embodied in the figure of the entrepreneur (as cited in Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). The entrepreneurial activity of opening new markets and new products and activates, was majorly adopted by males. On the other hand, although research argues that many entrepreneurial definitions and theories are stuck and based on the early/historical judgment of enterprises associated with males. The economic world has been driven by the emerging innovative and globalised outburst that compels a researcher to focus on entrepreneurship's distinctive features, which is an innovation (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Innovation is regarded as quality being intrinsic to an individual, leading to an entrepreneur's description of any gender an individual who possesses innovative features of intellect and direction (Schumpeter, 1939, p. 82).

The attention towards entrepreneurship in business research is currently growing (Zimmerer and Scarborough, 2001), and with this, there has been a massive increase in the research areas focusing on women in gender and entrepreneurship (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Unlike in the 70s, women considered key pioneers in entrepreneurship, and the number of women in this industry has highly accelerated in recent time (Weiler and Bernasek, 2001). According to research, female-owned businesses are among the fastest booming entrepreneurial populations globally (Brush, de Bruin and Welter, 2009).

Similarly, these businesses contribute significantly to employment, innovation, and wealth creation in most economies (Brush et al., 2006). Despite this rising importance of female-owned businesses and entrepreneurs, the research on this phenomenon is one of the few studies, and female entrepreneurship is under-researched (Brush et al., 2006). This leads to a gap in gender-specific academic research compared to the significant proportion of business ownership. When arguing about gender, it is imperative to look at the gender differences in the genres of entrepreneurship and economic development.

A significant gender gap has been monitored (as addressed above) in the entrepreneurial activity rate globally. Global Entrepreneurship Monitor's research on 18 different economies from 2002 to 2010 proposes that women's entrepreneurial activity is lower than their male counterparts at various development steps (Kelley, Singer and Herrington, 2011). Nevertheless, it can be argued that women's likelihood of entrepreneurial activity is lower in advanced countries than in less advanced countries (Sarfaraz, Faghieh and Majd, 2014). Research further observed that women in advanced areas experience more equal opportunities than women in less advanced areas.

As the economies progressing to a significant level of growth and the entrepreneurial activity rate decreases, despite of gender. Thus, both males and females have different employment options in more developed economies, and people seem to be more enthusiastic about taking secured jobs instead of running their firms. Overall, it was examined that the entrepreneurial gap between men and women lowers or decreases with the increase in the levels of economic developments (Kelley, Singer and Herrington, 2011).

The further the economies shift from factor-driven stages to efficiency-driven stages and majorly include innovation-driven stages, the gap being argued tends to decrease (As per reports, from 5.2% to 3.4%) (Sarfaraz, Faghieh and Majd, 2014). It is found that equality of gender may lead to more female entrepreneurship. Consequently, one can assume the countries

in which females have an equal number of opportunities compared to males, the female's entrepreneurial activity is more distinguished than the economies where females experience a higher gender inequality rate. It can be argued that generally, inequality of gender itself does not majorly propose the proportion of female entrepreneurs.

It can be argued that gender plays an imperative role in influencing the entrepreneurial aim, directly or indirectly (Vanessa, 2017) hence, which is why many young entrepreneurs are refusing to be a part of the stereotypical identities, where gender has an influence on entrepreneurship projects. Therefore, there is a gap existing in entrepreneurship by gender, influencing the entrepreneur's experience, especially in digital marketing (Noguera, Alvarez, & Urbano, 2013).

2.2.2 Male and Female Entrepreneurs Differentiation

The world is full of many successful male and female entrepreneurs. Research suggests that several traits can be recognised in both males and females and different distinctions also subsist in both. However, the fundamental qualities are risk controlling, decision-making techniques, business goals, business financing, management styles, networking capabilities and motivations. The current study found that differences between male and female exist when it comes to entrepreneurship. Gender entrepreneurship, such as male and female entrepreneurs psychologically and demographically, can be similar. It is not an easy decision for a female to become an entrepreneur compared to a male counterpart. The female gender is extra delicate to males in non-financial issues (Brush, 1992). It is well known that both male and female gender know business knowledge before running a business. They take mentorship and follow their role models, which directly support them in deciding to become entrepreneurs.

The following Table 1 presents the male and female entrepreneurial different actions. Males decide quickly, and females want extra time. Moreover, male entrepreneurs emphasise cost-effective strategies and more profit-driven, while female entrepreneurs pursue to make a social contribution and want to ensure their equality. The following table also presents male and

female-run different types of businesses. When both counterparts see a financial risk, males are readier to accept the risk than a female counterpart. Male and female also have differences in how they manage their businesses. Male takes more risks than female. Good relations with employee’s management are significant to female entrepreneurs. The following table also showed differing characteristics of male and female entrepreneurs.

Table 1: General Characteristics of Male and Female Entrepreneurs.

Male Entrepreneurship	Female Entrepreneurship
Easy decision making.	Feel difficulty in decision making.
Business emphasised on cost and economy.	Business emphasised on quality and social contribution.
Financial risk takers.	Conservative mindset taking Financial Risk or decisions.
Task oriented Managers.	Emphasis on good employee relationships.
Manufacturing and construction businesses.	Service and small retail businesses.

2.2.3 Business Goals of Male and Female Entrepreneurs

There is a different expectation, motives for establishing a business, aim, prospects, and nature of business changes among genders, which differentiate goals to achieve. Therefore, these attribution and observation require when considering the genders perspective of business activities; for instance, studies observed several differences between male's and female's new business operations; these include the following (i) male entrepreneurs have more business experience and high expectation than female entrepreneurs, (ii) female entrepreneurs are more likely take low business risk than male entrepreneurs (iii) male entrepreneurs more likely to spend more time searching for business opportunities than female entrepreneurs (Vanessa, 2017).

However, it is imperative to examine what other studies observed in genders perspectives of businesses in the entrepreneurship literature. Salleh and Osman (2007) adopted sequential mixed method research and identified "*that women have various goals for venturing into business and uniqueness of their background is reflected in their business goals*" (p33). Some female entrepreneurs are motivated to start-up business due to a personal need to increase family income and some are motivated in business to gain financial freedom.

This indicates that the business goals of female entrepreneurs are different, and it depends on their needs, background and circumstances. Langa-Fox and Roth (1995) identified three key types of female entrepreneurs. These include achiever entrepreneurs, pragmatic entrepreneurs, and managerial entrepreneurs; thus, these determine the female business goals. For instance, the achiever entrepreneurs' goals are to obtain higher income, and the managerial entrepreneurs' goals are to have self-attributed power to influence income and the pragmatic incline to achieve both high income and power to influence the income. It further argued that a female entrepreneur business goal is to be flexible in order to enable them to balance family and work (Salleh and Osman 2007).

The male entrepreneurs' goals, on the other hand, have been described in the literature as the most dominant entrepreneurs over female entrepreneurs. For this reason, Veena and Nagaraja (2013) claimed that male entrepreneurs are generally interpreted as being more successful than their female counterpart in opening and managing enterprises. As a result, many male entrepreneurs are more goal-oriented, profit-oriented, and have this belief and expectation of business success financially, as they are groomed from their childhood to ponder and act big in business. Similarly, a comparative study of successful male and female investigated that male entrepreneurs show better financial management in their daily business operations.

Moreover, male-owned entrepreneurs appeared to be more successful than female-owned businesses (Fairlie and Robb, 2009) because male entrepreneurs tend to have more start-up capital and human capital gained via previous working experience in business (Brixiová, Kangoye, and Said, 2020).

Although, to some extent, literature argued that male and female business goals could be similar. It depends on the business orientation, knowledge and behaviours of them; a typical example of this trend is the findings of (Turuk, Horvatinović, & Sudarić, 2020), which identified entrepreneurs' previous experience in the form of role models and entrepreneurial families before opening enterprises; most significantly for a female entrepreneur to start-up. It could be assumed that both male and female entrepreneurs' business goals rely on their behaviours, knowledge, and aspiration; thus, determine how they manage and approach their business and customers. Therefore, it is essential to some of the gender theories to evaluate male and female entrepreneurs' method or actions within their business context and business operations to achieve success.

2.2.4 Gender Theories

The gender theories are considered vital because they will enable this study to understand the masculine or feminine activities selected in business environments such as food SMEs and Muslim entrepreneurs. It is also imperative to acknowledge that entrepreneurs could acquire business skills for studying and utilising gender theories in their search of the logical, societal and political questions that motivate their business operation (Kubiček and Machek, 2019).

In the literature, gender theories are classified into several types, including critical race theory, affect theory, feminist theory, performativity, literary theory, feminist new materialism, and standpoint theory etc. (Danes, Stafford, and Loy, 2017; Collins. et al., 2014; Kubiček, and Machek, 2019).

These theories encompass privately owned businesses that contribute to a required theoretical deconstruction of the current views of entrepreneurs' operations, sustainability, and success (Collins. et al., 2014). For this reason, this study will focus on two key gender theories, which include critical race theory and standpoint theory. Therefore, the ongoing research explores the gender experience of Muslim entrepreneurs in utilising social media marketing platform for food businesses. These two theories would broaden the understanding of Muslim entrepreneurs' existence and perceptions in food businesses (Kubiček and Machek, 2019).

2.2.4.1 Critical Race Theory

Critical race theory is an approach that acts to seek the understanding and combat race inequity in a business environment. The entrepreneurship perspective views race as socially constructed features that play an essential role in which many populations failed to be recognised (Danes, Stafford, and Loy, 2017; Collins. et al., 2014). Generally, this theory is used to study activities and transform the association between race, racism and power; consideration of these concepts does not only take into civil and ethnic discourse but also consider them in a broader viewpoint that involve businesses, self-interest and feelings (Delgado, and Stefancic, 2017).

With entrepreneur's business-critical race theory could be used to understand their gender experience in social media marketing. For instance, Gold (2016) used the critical race theory on black American entrepreneurship and identified that critical race view offers the utmost definite reason for entrepreneurial achievements. Following this trend, it is important to note that critical race theory concentrates on identifying how entrepreneurs being male or female, can share their experiences (Kubiček and Machek, 2019). With this in mind, critical race theory does not recognise genders identity only but also their knowledge of the business's race identification.

Furthermore, critical race theory functions to ask several business questions to enable entrepreneurs to identify a solution to marketing problems and improve performance (Trevino, Harris, & Wallace, 2008). Which include the following: what is the importance of race in a contemporary business environment, where, in method and to what means does race appear in dominant business culture and structure the way entrepreneurs communicate with one another. In response to these questions, entrepreneurs can identify how their business operation improves and achieves significant performance.

Therefore, critical race theory for gender entrepreneurship is more than recognising race, racism and racialised character in fictional business (Gold, 2016); it instead outlines the position of studying and trying to understand the socio-cultural forces that structure ways of which male and female entrepreneurs observe, experience, and respond to discrimination in business. In support of this notion, Yosso (2005) agreed that critical race theory “*focuses on and learns from the array of cultural knowledge, skills, abilities and contacts possessed by socially marginalised groups that often go unrecognised and unacknowledged*” (p69).

The main aim of using this gender theory in this study is to comprehend male and female entrepreneurs' different social media marketing experiences within societies based on their race and relations. Also, to ascertain how knowledge stems from social media marketing employment of different entrepreneurs because gender perspective of male and female differs in terms of their business knowledge and experiences. Therefore, a critical race theory review provides the need to enhance race relations to attain more fair and harmonious communities for business.

2.2.4.2 Standpoint Theory

The standpoint theory is concerned with the insight of entrepreneurs that are marginalised and have different epistemic resources to understand the social structure in business, and these structures identify their understanding of the nature and life of the business (Wylie and Sismondo, 2015). This theory demonstrates specific insight women possess and meaning that is distinct from men in society. Concerning gender entrepreneur's standpoint theory could be explored to recognise female entrepreneurs' knowledge in contrast to male entrepreneurs in a business environment. In line with this, findings from Patterson, Mavin & Turner (2012) revealed that gender knowledge generates four ideas of female entrepreneurs' knowledge of gender in business leadership; these include awareness of knowledge, accepting and embracing change and responding to differences that gives a challenge to genders in entrepreneurs business.

In the same fashion, standpoint theory is the key leading theory that standardises entrepreneurs understanding of business through experiences (Adaman & Devine, 2002); its practice and culture function to shape up entrepreneur's view in a certain level of business. A typical example of the standpoint theory is the changing of genders perception in socio-economic states of the nation, the type of business entrepreneur is doing (Bruyat & Julien, 2001). As a result of this, the basic gender differences tailor to the difference to perspectives.

Therefore, the primary assumption of the standpoint theory in entrepreneurship business is to understand the marginalised entrepreneurs' view. Although understanding this view could be objective or subjective and changes from one gender to another, shared viewpoints can be viewed in specific collections where gender exchange everyday environments (Foley, 2006).

Accordingly, these gender theories are imperative in studying entrepreneurship, most especially when they consider their genders. Such as understanding the masculine or feminine actions in the food SMEs and Muslim entrepreneurs acquire their business knowledge. Thus, the Standpoint theory review has proven that social and political awareness shapes entrepreneurs' business perceptions. Standpoint theory instructs the researcher to explore how male and female entrepreneurs experience differently while using social media marketing for their food SMEs in the UK. Therefore, the overviews of these theories enable this study to elicit vital information suitable to address the research problem.

2.3 Digital Marketing and its Importance

Digitalisation has changed the traditional methods in which businesses and customers communicate with each other and used essentially in daily routine (Taiminen & Karjaluoto, 2015). Many consumers spend their times using social media and online services (Nielsen, 2017). Customers used different online platforms for browsing, notably, digital media helps businesses change consumer behaviour (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010) about products and firms (Muntinga, Moorman and Smit, 2011). Digital marketing has developed over the period from a specific word unfolding the marketing of products and services using online platforms on macro-level describing the procedure of using digital technologies to gain customers, build customer preferences, retain customers, help brands, and boost turnover (Kannan & Li, 2017). Kanan and Li (2017) described digital marketing as the technology-enabled development of recent time where businesses communicate with consumers and shareholders to collectively create, collaborate, distribute, and maintain every ones' value. According to Chaffey and Smith (2013), online media helps in market development by taking advantage of low-cost advertising. Along with this, online marketing can also be used to add value to the products and services for achieving customer satisfaction. For example, businesses can provide the information for their products and services and other facilities via their website.

Furthermore, digital marketing helps organisations achieve a competitive edge over others operating in the same industry and acquire significant market share for its products and services, market penetration (Chaffey and Smith, 2013). Incorporating digital marketing strategies also helps companies diversify their products and services that contribute to their expansion and growth (Prato, Sanz and Simon, 2014). Being a digitalised business, it has many forms that are positively linked to business performance, unique and small business growth. Digital marketing and social media present multiple entrepreneurial opportunities for firms to influence new customers and approach their consumers more efficiently (Taiminen & Karjaluoto, 2015).

Moreover, internet uses benefit the firms by minimising the costs and enabling communication both internally and externally (Chong and Pervan, 2007). The recent advancement in digitalisation, such as social media, has claimed the positive connection between utilisation and effects. According to new research of 12 SMEs firms undertaken in the UK, the use of social media found to advance effectiveness and increase external communication (Barnes, Lescault & Andonian, 2012). Digital media and technologies are quickly making changes in the environment in which businesses run. These digital technologies are playing a pivotal role in minimising the lack of symmetries between the firm and consumers are essential ways (Kannan & Li, 2017).

In addition, digital technologies and environmental aspect interaction begin with the theory of how consumer behaviour is varying because of several different technologies and devices access both in the online and mobile perspectives. Global most robust economy perspective, in 2020, it is predicted that consumer expenditure will grow to the most substantial rate since 2011 (Angus and Westbrook, 2020). However, consumer behaviour and attitude will play a leading role to cause the disruption in 2018 and shape the new changes with internet access and mobile technology (Angus and Westbrook, 2020).

Additionally, technological advancement is creating opportunities for consumers to find out more about themselves and their origin. Consumer behaviour change informs the business to rethink their marketing plans, especially in the domain of digital. The literature review considered a significant part of the study that enables the researcher to utilise the information previously addressed by prominent researchers on similar or related research issues. Past literature disagrees that conventional marketing theories are currently not applicable to small and medium-sized businesses (Reijonen, 2010). Firms' marketing techniques are simple, spontaneous and reactive (Gilmore, Callagher and Henry, 2007). Therefore, it is a significant gap between social media marketing activity in small and medium-sized businesses and good practice facilitated by marketing theory. SMEs are considered a sales generator, and their marketing strategies are developing more awareness of the products and businesses (Reijonen, 2010).

2.3.1 Social Media

Running a business through social media is essential for every entrepreneur, for a start-up, gaining customers and improving profitability. Social media can help entrepreneurs build publicity for all types of business and enhance the opportunities for customers to know about their businesses. Thus, in the business context, social media is online communication that enables an organisation to communicate with clients to share useful ideas and information in real-time (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). Social media has enabled people to grow their business and make better living through online businesses (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). The organisation can utilise it to connect with their various customer better, generate online business, sell and advertising goods and service.

2.3.2 Social Media Networking Sites

Social media networking sites and their users have risen exponentially (Doty and Dworkin, 2014), especially among entrepreneurs. Facebook is high ranked social media sites (Ryan, 2017). Many people use social media networking sites; these people, such as entrepreneurs, request their contacts or customers to join them (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). One of the highest users networking sites is Facebook and accounted for 1.59 billion users in 2015 (Ryan, 2017). Various social sites, namely Instagram and Pinterest, which are overtaken by Facebook, have accounted for substantial growth in 2015 and currently, an amount of 31% online users use Pinterest, whereas Instagram users are 28%. There is the key to social media networking sites' popularity because these sites offer users (Ryan, 2017), such as entrepreneurs' ability to find and connect with the targeted audience. These sites are increasingly helping businesses and organisations by using paid advertising to connect with their customers.

Social media networks help design frameworks from relationships that facilitate key resources to an entrepreneur (Nielsen, 2017) and have gained the importance of the area of interest for entrepreneurial study (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). With the help of social networks, the entrepreneurs may authorise their environment (Johannisson, 1988) to access key resources, i.e. knowledge, support, and resource channels access (Greve & Salaff, 2003). Thus, the four leading social media platforms of which entrepreneurs can communicate, interact, create brand awareness and receive the product feedback of their business operation are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat.

2.3.3 Social Media Marketing as a Tool

Ryan (2017) argued that "*social media is the umbrella term for web-based software and services that allow the users to come together online and exchange, discuss, communicate and participate in any form of social interaction*" (p. 120). This interaction may include text, images, audio, video and other media files (Ryan, 2017). Furthermore, social media may also produce new content, recommending and sharing the same content, rating services, products and brands, communicating current topics, showing interests and hobbies, sharing expertise (Ryan, 2017). Many websites have started the social media element to interact with their customers, and few of the most famous sites appear in current times, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter, due to its popularity.

Effective marketing of social media is getting out of the house mallet tactic to product campaign (Ryan, 2017), and Social media is also gaining a prompt and vital significance in B2C marketing (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Moreover, social media enables entrepreneurs to facilitate key resources and improve profitability (Ryan, 2017). However, in trade, it is employed barely (Taiminen and Karjaluoto, 2015). Social media enabled the entrepreneurs to know what their customers are fascinated with, what they want, and then deliver useful advice, information, and content (Ryan, 2017). Social media significantly influenced and helped the SMEs businesses and their online presence.

It is noted that social media adoption and formed strategies for businesses have a limited amount of research in recent studies. This research includes presenting literature, as it examines the Social Media marketing strategies essentially from Muslim entrepreneurship perspective facilitating the information employing Social Media channels (Järvinen and Taiminen, 2016) uncover that social media uses in B2C marketing is a time saver for consumer, relating it to their purchasing behaviour.

Social media as a marketing tool helps entrepreneurs take advantage of modern communication tools and adjust to the new effective business style (Thoumrunroje, 2014). Furthermore, social media marketing enables businesspeople and customers to identify brands' information and interact with customers before purchasing them (Pantano and Di Pietro (2013). Social media marketing tools enable them to provide information about business needs, customer review and competitive movement (Constantinides, 2014).

According to Chaffey and Smith (2013), the analytical tool helps entrepreneurs to increase business performance. Also, social media insights and analytical tool helped businesses to know customers' preferences and consumer behaviours. Entrepreneurs must use Facebook insight and Instagram analytics (Akbar & Özgül, 2018; Oham, Kokkranikal, & Coca-Stefaniak, 2019). on the other hand, users share content online to communicate and discuss (Afiyanita, 2021) social media trend. A *social media marketing strategy* is a technology that promotes effective communication between entrepreneurs and customer to maintain business values (Kanan and Li, 2017).

2.3.4 Social Media Communications

Nowadays, "*many young entrepreneurs specifically are exploiting the gathering of people and potential virility of the huge swath of mediums to spread the news for better outcomes, and longer-enduring activities*" (Aku, 2018, p. 2). Presently, social media have dominated worldwide business activities. In the UK, particularly entrepreneurs have explored specific social media networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and Twitter; thus, social media communication has dramatically helped UK entrepreneurs improve their business performance and sales (Olanrewaju et al., 2018). For instance, Aku (2018) revealed that social media communication contributes significantly to an entrepreneur's performance and concludes that Facebook and Instagram influence importantly in recognising creativity among entrepreneurs.

In the literature, social media communications influence the way entrepreneurs communicate with customers and create better opportunities for doing to enable business growth rapidly in organisations (Khajeheian, 2013). Genç and Oksuz (2015) argued that Facebook is still the key source of entrepreneur marketing communication and advantageous instruments to businesses to identify influential social media communication usage of female entrepreneurs. Similarly, Sarkar and Ghosal (2018) analysed 100 samples of entrepreneurs and identified Facebook as the utmost and most negligible variance of the features that enable entrepreneurs to improve their performance.

Furthermore, a study on Facebook usage by Wong (2012), irrespective of gender, finding identified a significant direct impact of entrepreneurs' usage of Facebook and the domain innovativeness of business. This indicates that social media communication significantly influences an entrepreneur's performance and customer satisfaction (Singh and Sinha, 2017), business growth and financial performance (Sinha & Verma, 2020). Thus, social media communication is an essential tool for entrepreneurs and a minimum investment for businesses. Also, social media communication generates an affordable channel for businesses through Facebook and suitable tools for entrepreneurs with limited resources (Nakara, Benmoussa, & Jaouen, 2012), and product promotion enhances both business growth and financial performance (Deželjin, Bienenfeld, & Turkalj, 2017; Sinha & Verma, 2020).

Exploratory research of entrepreneurs on social media communication using small business operations by Granger and Reiter (2015) identified that entrepreneurs are mostly used Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Periscope and Snapchat to advertise and communicate with their customer's but conclude that Snapchat and Facebook remain solid and consider useful for online businesses in the UK. This notion is supported by Martin (2015), whose findings indicated that marketing products in Snapchat and Instagram are now the smartest investment in entrepreneurship business.

Similarly, AlArfaj and Solaiman (2019) interview female entrepreneurs and identified that social media communications through Instagram, Twitter and Snapchat are explored by business owners to build a reputation to satisfy their customers and gain customers trust. A survey of 212 business owners confirmed that social media communication enables entrepreneurs to access vital resources and what can help them achieve business performance (Oham, Kokkranikal & Coca-Stefaniak, 2019). In the same fashion, Gentina, Chen & Yang (2020) identified that Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat business activities are significant for entrepreneurs with lower levels of resources and improve sale performance.

This implies that social media communications can abet to develop "individuals' sense of connectedness with real or online communities and social media can be an effective communication (or marketing) tool for corporations, entrepreneurs, nonprofit organisations, including advocacy groups and political parties and government" (Lakshmi, Mahboob and Choudhry, 2017, p. 66). Literature confirmed that entrepreneurs often post their business activities on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Snapchat (Oham, Kokkranikal & Coca-Stefaniak, 2019; Olanrewaju et al., 2018). This shows that social media communication can be seen as one of the best channel organisations interacts with their customers.

Social media pages and profiles such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter could help both entrepreneurs and their managers to interact and respond to customer reviews (Azar et al., 2016; Hammick and Ju, 2016). For instance, a review of literature from 2002-2018 to investigate the impact of social media communication on the entrepreneurship operation by Olanrewaju et al. (2020) revealed that entrepreneurial social media communication has gone beyond businesses interaction but also used for business networking, a search of information and mass funding for businesses.

It can be concluded that the users of social media communication activities for business result in a significant influence with enhanced entrepreneur's business performance and innovation improvement being a meaningful outcome.

2.3.5 Social Media for Brand Awareness

Organisations utilise social media for numerous reasons and aims, such as communicating and advertising their products, which is important to their business operations (Olanrewaju et al., 2020). This operational activity is most important to entrepreneurs and early development stages that often require aid information to start-up and manage the new business. Entrepreneurs social media activities may include marketing of products and services; thus, the ability to do this and communicate with customers is another important factor for brand awareness. Social media is an utmost marketing element that could connect with many shoppers (Alhaddad, 2015) and increase their product awareness (Melati and Febiatty, 2016).

Brand awareness is the activity of entrepreneurs that demonstrate how customers recognise their products by their name; hence, forming brand awareness is the main action in promoting both old and new brand. Indeed, awareness of an entrepreneur's brand may involve qualities that differentiate the brand from its competitors through social media, which is essential for businesses (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The study of the impact of brand awareness by Zhao et al. (2017) revealed that brand awareness can directly forecast and promotes brand loyalty. Similarly, to identify the role of social media brand awareness (Melati & Febianty, 2016) identified that hotels companies could increase brand awareness through social media.

To identify the relationship between social media communication marketing and its brand awareness (Tritama & Tarigan, 2016) argued that social media communication has a meaningful influence on brand awareness (Timilsina, 2017) and improves its revenue. Similarly, a regression analysis demonstrates that 34% of social media brand awareness is done through Facebook sites (Akbar, & Özgül, 2018). In investigating Facebook social media

marketing on brand awareness, ElAydi (2018) identified six core dimensions of social media marketing activities: online communities, interaction, sharing content, accessibility, and credibility. Statistically, an analysis of 364 SMEs by Qalati & Kwabena (2019) identified a significant correlation between social media and brand performance.

A research carried out to investigate the impact of social media on 800 restaurants brand awareness (Fernández-Miguélez, et al., 2020) argued that social media promotes SMEs brand awareness to their customers; social media brand awareness has a positive impact on restaurants business (Timilsina, 2017). As a result, regardless of the type of business entrepreneurs, social media brand awareness is important to growth and customers satisfaction. Thus, advertising awareness improves entrepreneurs' brands and promotes products image (Alhaddad, 2015).

Altogether, it can be concluded that social media brand awareness may help entrepreneurs to improve their brand's awareness and performance. Irrespective of the literature above, Sari, Suziana and Games (2020) confirmed that social media advertising for Muslim entrepreneurs significantly affects brand awareness and purchase intention. In the same fashion, the study of a sample of 270 restaurants by Kizgin et al. (2020) shows that social media advertisement and online brand awareness promotes customer purchasing performances.

2.3.6 Social Media for Customer Feedback

One of the keyways to make customers feel involved and important to organisations is to ask for their feedback and strategising the business; accordingly, by knowing customers opinions about the company's brand or service, entrepreneurs can make a decision that will help their business develop faster. Social media is the fastest and easiest platform to obtain customers feedback for business development; thus, customers feedback is the data, insight and input of customers opinion about the company's products and services (Tajvidi et al., 2018).

For this reason, Fundin and Bergman (2003) argued that organisations should address customer feedback obtained from social media as a means for the development of the goods and services and recommends entrepreneurs develop an organised process of taking customers feedback.

This is because social media and customers feedback has become a crucial mean through which information about the company's products and services can be shared. Thus, a semi-structured interview carried out by Keizers (2015) revealed that the information and opinions easily influence customers they obtain about organisational goods and service. This is further supported by Schwichtenberg (2015) finding, which confirmed that social media and customer feedback significantly impact both company's products and customer retention.

This empirical evidence provides useful insights into how social media for customer feedback directly influences a company's products option and customers retention. Given that entrepreneurs are required to use social media to obtain important customer feedback to improve their business operations and products. For instance, an analysis of 293 customers of international fast-food restaurants by Hanaysha (2017) shows that social media marketing and customer feedback significantly affect business performance. To understand the role of social media in a retail business, Ramanathan, Subramanian, and Parrott (2017) argued that customer feedback on social media requires entrepreneurs to design a strategy that will improve business performance and value.

However, it is vital to consider social media customer helpful feedback for improving entrepreneurs' brand and business performance. Several studies suggested that entrepreneurs could explore customer feedback survey, email and contact form, on-site activity and instant feedback from website to obtain customer feedback (Grimes, 2018; Erkan and Evans, 2018; Kamboj et al., 2018). In light of this, Grimes (2018) asserted that entrepreneurs should incorporate customer feedback into the business and create operations more broadly.

Furthermore, Erkan and Evan (2018) conducted survey feedback of customer and identified that anonymous customer feedback is more significant on customer online buying intention than the reference on social media. Similarly, a survey method was adopted by Kamboj et al. (2018) to examine antecedents of products creation and identified that social networking sites contribution motivate a direct impact on customer participation, which in turn improves product trust and loyalty. This agreed with the recent result from Anaya-Sánchez et al. (2020), which stated that brand trust affects repurchase intention and online word of mouth; these scholars concluded that brand trust negatively and positively affects an online brand community.

Furthermore, email is another format in which entrepreneurs could find it easier to gather customers feedback because companies can use it as a support channel; to communicate with their customers about brand and services (Appel et al., 2020). Thus, the literature suggested increasing the possibility of getting customer feedback, and an entrepreneur needs to set out three key objectives: clear expectation, arranging email feedback, and sending customised responses for customers (Patricio, 2017).

Considering these ideas, it is also important to note that entrepreneurs and their managers use negative and positive feedback to improve their brand and services. Given that entrepreneur, customers explore social media to create content, inspire new customers by positive feedback and summon other behaviours with the products (Guha, Harrigan, & Soutar, 2018). This is because social media customers' feedback could help entrepreneurs embark on a new business, hence surviving and managing the negative impact on the business (Bocconcelli, Cioppi, and Pagano, 2017).

According to Singh, Shukla, & Mishra (2018), *"In terms of social media data analysis, three major issues are considered: data harvesting/capturing, data storage, and data analysis"* (p. 401). Following this, entrepreneurs must ensure that all customers' feedback is gathered and stored for analysis purposes to meet business goals. Thus, to investigate the barriers of supply chain market access from SMEs in the UK and India, Singh, Shukla & Mishra (2018) analysed social positive and negative thoughts of the consumers, as well as for the recognition of their problems/concerns related to food products and identified that feedback from social media represents the actual views of customers.

Also, to analyse how social media brand content induces customer opinions, Carlson et al. (2018) argued that customer value opinion influences their feedback and collaboration intentions. Cama, Herman, and Lambert (2017) analysed the keyword of customers feedback related to the brand and service of entrepreneurs and concluded that social media is the faster and most manageable channel to gather the information that may improve brand value and performance. Therefore, entrepreneurs should consider social media customer feedback important to improving profitability and explored customers' opinions to improve their products and service values.

2.3.7 Social Media and Gender

In recent time, social media and interrelated activities are quickly emerging, and the number of online users in women is more than the number of men as per one global study (Vollman, Abraham and Morn, 2010). Due to this fact, many possible differences could be experienced within social media. Advertisement agencies and media businesses have reported using the same and outdated ideology to know their audiences. Though, it has become challenging precisely in order to use these outdated patterns. It is essential to analyse what is associated with the social media and gender aspect when observing social media issues and how media influences gender.

Michaelidou, Siamagka, and Christodoulides (2011) argued that spending more time interacting and engaging online businesses may delay delivery services to a customer. To complete the analysis, the impacts between gender and social media strategies help not merely contemplate the quantity of social media users and the time spent on social media but also to compare the advanced social media with the former social media (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood, 2016).

Furthermore, females spent more time on social networking sites than males (Junco, Merson, & Salter, 2010). It is similarly essential to analyse the characteristic of women taking responsibility for the media, the growing fame of social media, and the connection between social media and gender. Male and female connects differently in real life, which indeed imitates how they employ social media. They update with different things, choose specific platforms and even use different language. Technical skills are the key solutions to effective social media marketing activities (Matikiti, Mpinganjira, & Roberts-Lombard, 2018; Garg & Pahuja, 2020). Social media marketing and the metrics associated with social media are becoming challenging (Michaelidou, Siamagka & Christodoulides, 2011).

According to Bailey et al. (2013), women are undoubtedly passionate about social media technology usage and used it in compelling ways to develop their social lives. There are multiple social media podiums to select from, such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat, Google Plus, Tumblr, Vine, and the massive collection of online dating sites, including Harmony. However, one key thing to remember about several such sites is that they are both corporate and mainstream. The past many years' pure social media trends were the development of the social media website Facebook. Facebook is the most rising and universal social media websites in the globe that offers several aspects for users to present the identity (Boupha et al., 2013), network (Webb et al., 2012), and maintain affairs.

The significant social media platform offers various forms to discover and recognise the associated persons, organisations, and businesses; after locating certain elements, users create a network, keep privacy, and update their products. Facebook may develop "*deeply integrated in users' daily lives through specific routines and rituals*" (Debatin et al., 2009, p. 83). One of the studies suggests that 81% of college students log in to their Facebook account daily (Sheldon, 2009) and spend an average of 49 minutes per day on the website. Moreover, Facebook acquired different social networking sites, including Instagram and Twitter, which enabled the users to post content simultaneously to many networking sites.

The selected social media specified descriptions described the specific utilisation ideas, such as ideas associated with a specific type of gender-based performances (for example, male and female using social media marketing). However, a connection between specific social media utilisation and performance acts they follow remain largely undocumented (Webb & Temple 2015). Moreover, Webb and Temple (2015) further suggested the future research to discuss this research gap would help marketing managers to know their online endeavours. Therefore, the current study will investigate gender performances in utilising social media marketing for their food SMEs.

2.4 Food Industry & UK

Wunsch (2020) reported that there are 5.9 million small and medium-sized private businesses currently running in the UK, out of 2.4 million SMEs were operating and about to complete their first century, and this private sector employs 27.5 million people. These private small and medium-sized businesses generate a revenue of over £4.14 trillion, the highest number of SMEs located in London (1.1 million). The revenue of private SMEs in the UK has improved by over £1 trillion inclusively since 2012 (Clark, 2020). The food industry includes the activities of food production, food products, food services and retailing.

The UK's entire food industry revenue is expected to reach £148 billion in 2020 (Wunsch, 2020). Despite a decline in 2009, restaurant businesses have shown a significant rise in the UK. In 2018, 88,848 businesses operating in the restaurant and mobile food service industry in the UK (Lock, 2021). In the UK, the restaurants and mobile food services experienced a bumper year in 2018 by producing £40 billion turnovers. This increment is more important than any other time during the reported period (Lock, 2021)

Despite a decline in 2009, customer spending power on cafes, restaurants, and related food shops in the UK significantly improved each year. In 2019, customer spending estimated approximately 100.52 billion British pounds. Notwithstanding its growth, the restaurant market in the UK continues to face challenges that have already begun to affect businesses. However, industry experts endure positive, proposing that customer's demand is still high and food trends change quickly, which means that there are yet more opportunities to be explored (Lock, 2021). The food industry, particularly the restaurant market, takeaway, fast-food, and online food bloggers, are increasingly contributing to the UK economy. The food industry is a vibrant industry with continuous improvements in customer needs (Wiengarten, Pagell and Fynes, 2011). Therefore, this means the food industry can acclimate marketing strategies and reshape the resources and opportunities (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). In today's food industry, procedures are the keys to enhance technologically advancement, characterised by mass production. Moreover, marketing is known universally (Trienekens et al., 2012). Globalisation, along with new marketing technological shift, consumption trends, and advance technology, has at the same time elevated concerns regarding the economy, society, and the environment (Zanoni and Zavanella, 2012).

Furthermore, the fast food restaurant industry has faced durable progress recently in response to new consumer trends, tastes and inspiring global economic conditions. Since the worldwide economic crisis and the decline in individuals' income globally, it has been seen a decrease in

expenditure on luxuries, i.e. going out for eating, which has raised customer choices low priced and more suitable food products.

There are many opportunities for success when straightening the marketing strategies to reach the customer (Manning, 2013) or different stakeholders (Wiese & Toporowski, 2013), such as entrepreneurial interests and actions. However, it needed to recognise which marketing strategies are employed and how these applications are followed in the food SMEs.

Therefore, customers are concerned with the food products they purchased, such as their origin (Trienekens et al., 2012) and how it is produced. Out of 1.8 million Muslims use the internet, in which males Muslim are approximately one million, whereas females Muslim are 840 thousand (Office of National Statistics, 2016). Office of National Statistics (2016) further reported that nearly 1 million Muslim male and females use the internet and found in economic activity means operate enterprises. Consequently, the vibrant UK food industry and the consumer behaviours demand the food industry as a strong research focus when exploring the different Muslim entrepreneurial experiences of using social media marketing.

2.5 Entrepreneurship Theories

2.5.1 Resource- Based View

In 1959, Edith Penrose developed theory known as RBV, which she claimed that resources are vital in constraining or allowing the organisational growth. Penrose described firm's resources as "*the physical things a firm buy, leases, or produces for its own use, and the people hired on terms that make them effectively part of the firm*" (Penrose 1959, p. 60). Since, Penrose developed these insights and continuous evolution of RBV. Several researchers have constructed and focused more explicitly on "strategic resources" (Amit and Schoemaker 1993). Strategic resources consist of value, imitation, rare, and non-substitute, which helps the firm achieve its competitive advantage (Barney, 1991).

The RBV has mainly applied theory in strategic management (Liang, You & Liu, 2010) and entrepreneurship (Kellermanns et al., 2014). However, many scholars have explored the role of the resources in the business' start-up and development stages, conceptualising resource-based theory. The RBV theory has been broadly applied to investigate the different business aspects: capabilities, routines and resources that are key to business performance (Goh, Prakash, & Yeo, 2007) and competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). The RBV theoretical concept explicates an organisation's resources may facilitate a competitive advantage if such resources are essential, valuable, perfectly imitable, and non-substitutable (Barney, 1991). Additionally, in achieving the highest performance and competitive advantage, firms require to manage their supports in line with these traits, which allow the firms to implement strategies (Solesvik and Westhead, 2010).

Past literature on the resource-based view (RBV) has developed significant theoretical perception in the organisational sciences (Barney, Wright, and Ketchen, 2001) and shown holding distinctive resources is a compulsory state for business and entrepreneurs to maintain their competitive benefits. Moreover, Resource-based theoretical approach of entrepreneurship advocates that entrepreneurial access to resources is a significant forecaster of venture growth and opportunity-based entrepreneurship. This theory importantly emphasises social, financial, and human resources (Aldrich, 1999). Therefore, resource access increases the entrepreneur's capability to perceive and perform the available opportunities (Davidson & Honing, 2003). Social, financial and human resources demonstrate three types of theories, which follow the resource-based theories of entrepreneurship.

There are four types of resources: identification, acquisition, integration, and utilisation, working together constantly and scientifically with opportunities development (Barney, 1991). It has pointed out identifying and analysing inside resources is the essential form of firms to know the strategy opportunities. They also argued that if one business finds few unique

resources, this business can uncover particular opportunities related to these resources. The complete procedure of identifying the opportunity carries on with the circle between resource acquisition and information collection. Thus, businesses seek to accomplish the unique ways to assign their firms' resources by constant information search and idea to understand opportunity development.

Holding the same standpoint view that useful resource possession and growth is supportive for business to enter in a good cycle of constantly seeking opportunities. Therefore, the primary purpose of entrepreneurship is to utilise the opportunities by incorporating resources (Shane, 2009). Many research scholars believed that in order to achieve their competitive advantages in specific market opportunities, entrepreneurs should accomplish the internal consistency of resources, business strategies and advance their changeable aptitudes according to the changing atmosphere by joining their accessible resources and new resources (Ireland and Hitt, 1999; Milgrom and Roberts, 1995).

Past studies have examined the digital marketing employment in small businesses from both sides the internal perspectives such as strategy, experience, attitudes, firm-specific factors, and external perspectives are environmental factors and infrastructure of the business (Dholakia and Kshetri, 2004). In the business context, the extensively employed theory RBV of the firm (Barney, 1991; Grant, 1991; Lockett and Thompson, 2001) advocates that resources are key dynamics of decision-making explanation in small businesses, on the other side, external features comparatively show low participation (Hawawini, Venkat, and Verdin, 2003). In 2010, Karjaluoto and Huhtamäki identified the reasons to implement digital means in SMEs firms under three different kinds: company-specific and management factors, environmental factors, and resource-related factors. Both have noted that these may perform either as inhibitors or as a facilitator of usage. This classification is followed in this study to understand the adoption of digital marketing in SMEs.

A high rise of RBV research in marketing in history appears suspect to get slow soon. As per the research conducted by Kozlenkova, Samaha and Palmatier (2013), existing resource-based theory study to identify unique insights to marketing realm and resources, recommend theoretical expansion or application of using RBV to marketing, and a significant direction and guidance is given for the future use of RBV in marketing. On the other hand, according to the exploratory study conducted by Dorminey, Dull and Schaupp (2015), examining the relationship between social media usage and market survey, the RBV approach is theoretical employed to that study a managerial disclosure of material information using social media marketing. It has found that RBV theory is consistent for managers to use social media as a resource aiming to increase the value through enhanced corporate image (Dorminey, Dull and Schaupp, 2015). It is further showing the positive association in-between social media usage and market survey. Future studies can explore refinements to applying the theory of RBV using social media changes and RBV theory extension to small and medium-sized firms, and social media employment should be explored (Dorminey, Dull and Schaupp, 2015).

2.5.2 Opportunity-Based Theory

Peter Drucker (1985) and Howard Stevenson & Harmeling (1990) are the main anchors of the opportunity-based theory of entrepreneurs. An opportunity-based conceptual approach presents a comprehensive theoretical framework for entrepreneurship research (Shane, 2000). Drucker (1985) argued, “*this defines entrepreneur and entrepreneurship, the entrepreneur always searches for change, responds to it, and exploits it as an opportunity*”. Moreover, according to these theories of entrepreneurs, which are not change inevitable but develop the opportunities that bring the change in consumer choices and technology (Drucker, 1985).

In recent times, there is no doubt that technology has become a key player making people’s lives easier; on the other hand, the entrepreneurs or opportunists are gaining benefit from this opportunity and launching new business plan on the market (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood,

2016). Entrepreneurship begins with the development of opportunities which is an entrepreneur's realm (Shane, 2000), while opportunity exploitation is a procedure that depends on entrepreneur decision— is generally the state of the organisation which, through its abilities, shapes opportunities into market results (Whittaker et al., 2009).

Figure 2: Opportunity-based Approach to Entrepreneurship (Shane, 2000).

Entrepreneurs employ social media as a marketing instrument because it helps them create an instant network of customers, which is key for business growth (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood, 2016). In addition, Social media marketing facilitates to form of a sustainable connection between firms and customers. Gender role in business researched by many scholars, males and females were considered mainly from entrepreneurship (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004; Vanessa, 2017), marketing perspective (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood, 2016). The opportunity-based theory of entrepreneurship literature provides a research flow, which can be linked to entrepreneurship and social media marketing study. However, there are many issues interrelated to social media marketing that obstacles the firms regarding the execution of social media planning are the lack of consensuses on how the innovative technology used and different platforms, and there has no proper guideline for entrepreneurs to utilise them (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood, 2016).

Latest technologies and new digital media devices point out that future research requests to centre on how entrepreneurs may employ these developments to construct sustainable reasonable benefit, earn market share, and enhance the customer preference and brand equity (Kannan and Li, 2017). This is based on study to investigate the role of both genders' male and female Muslim entrepreneurs towards the employment of social media marketing for their food business in the UK.

2.6 Research Conceptual Framework

The marketing strategy is the actions that should help the entrepreneurs accomplish the goals and objectives with the support of marketing activities. The proposed framework integrates entrepreneurial opportunities as sources of social media marketing and drivers of the strategy, particularly to identify both gender's experience as Muslim male and female entrepreneurs using social media marketing in food-related SMEs in the UK. This conceptual framework is summarised as follow:

Figure 3 Conceptual Model

The entrepreneurial opportunities are the keys to designing the entrepreneurial marketing strategies for the business. Social media marketing and Muslim entrepreneurs, in turn, affect the gender experiences, and all these changes develop new nascent information, which further creates new learning opportunities and may lead to the development of new theory. Therefore, it is pointed out that marketing strategy is an ongoing method of actions and reactions formed by entrepreneurs' opportunities.

2.7 Key Propositions Derived from Literature

A research proposition is an assertion about the ideas that can be considered right or wrong, indicating noticeable research phenomena. However, when a proposition designed to test empirically, it is known as a hypothesis.

In this study, the researcher decided to practice the propositions in the first phase of the study, and hypotheses will be tested in the second phase of the study for the following reasons:

1. The empirical side of the research is exploratory.
2. This study does not follow any previous research model and can be investigated from a more pragmatic lens, which will be more meaningful.

Social media and internet employment have changed how entrepreneur runs their businesses. Social media provide key opportunities to entrepreneurs in several ways, such as brand awareness. Entrepreneurs create social media business pages and profiles, such as Facebook page, Instagram page and Twitter account, which have become standard for many brands (Azar et al., 2016; Hammick and Ju, 2016). Therefore, the first and second proposition is as follows:

- **Social media is a new shift of today's era; therefore, it encourages entrepreneurs to create social media business pages and profiles such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat accounts.**
- **Social media encourages entrepreneurs to use popular social media platforms.**

The literature also focuses on the relationship of social media and social media marketing by Muslim entrepreneurs running food SMEs to influence business actions and serve their customers. Social media enabled the entrepreneurs to know what their customers are fascinated with, what they want, and then deliver useful advice, information, and content (Ryan, 2017). Social media helped and has a positive influence on businesses and their online presence. It is noted that business adoption and in line formed strategies for businesses are under research in recent studies. Therefore, the third proposition is as follows:

- **Muslim entrepreneurs heavily use social media marketing in food businesses (SMEs) to serve their customers.**

This literature review has significantly examined the emergence of entrepreneurship. Therefore, it can be said that these entrepreneurs have a positive influence on the UK halal food industry in general and digital entrepreneurship in particular. Thus, the fourth proposition of this study is suggested as follows:

- **Muslim entrepreneurs mainly using social media for their businesses that play a significant role in UK halal food industry.**

Moreover, one key theme is emerging from the literature review on social media communications states that Muslim entrepreneurs use social media as a marketing tool to increase customer interaction, customer engagement to receive feedback, and brand awareness. These entrepreneurs use these communication tools to identify the business opportunity within their target audience to achieve the business aims and goals (Opportunity based theory). Therefore, the fifth, sixth and seventh propositions of this research presented below:

- **Muslim entrepreneurs use social media marketing as a communication tool to increase the brand awareness of their businesses.**

- **Muslim entrepreneurs use social media marketing as a communication tool to interact with its customer.**
- **Muslim entrepreneurs use social media marketing as a communication tool to receive positive and negative customer feedback on food products.**

This literature advances the link between entrepreneurship and gender, that confirming the characteristics of entrepreneurs are not the only factors that impact business actions. Further literature argues that the essential characteristics of entrepreneurship are derived from the mythological figure of a mercurial personality; open-minded, strong-headed and sharp and pragmatic (Bruni, Gherardi and Poggio, 2004). Entrepreneurs also use their decision making, ethnic roles and cultural behaviours to engage with consumers. Thus, the eighth proposition of the study suggested as follows:

- **Gender features can influence the actions of entrepreneurs to identify the marketing opportunity and customer engagement.**

Furthermore, presented entrepreneurship literature in gender recognised male and female entrepreneurs is different in running the business. However, the fundamental qualities are their business goals, decision-making styles, controlling risks, financing business, management styles, networking ability, marketing business, motivations. One academic study carried out on the traits of gender that encourage environments, leadership, and a team essence can aid and enhance the entrepreneurship activity amongst both men and women (Krueger and Brazeal (1994). Therefore, the ninth and tenth proposition of this research are as follows:

- **Male and female entrepreneurs are benefiting from social media adoption and significant use for their business.**
- **Male and female entrepreneurs suggest that social media is very cost-effective and easy to maintain.**

Furthermore, the current literature review presented that entrepreneurs use social media as a low-cost platform to recognise markets and engage with consumers. It further highlights the entrepreneurial networking roles and identifies new markets in the context of social media. Therefore, many businesses use social media networking sites; they request their contacts or customers to join them (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). For instance, entrepreneurial networking proposes that several businesses use social media platforms to build the business. This academic literature review on entrepreneurial opportunity creation influences and directs this research to use opportunity-based theory (Shane, 2000) since it considers what is the entrepreneurial opportunity (social media), how it is decided (significant SM platforms) and how it is shaped to receive the results (social media marketing strategies). There is no doubt that technology has become a key player in recent times, making people's lives easier.

On the other hand, entrepreneurs or opportunists are gaining benefit from this opportunity and launching a new business plan on the market (Shabbir, Ghazi & Mehmood, 2016). However, the opportunity-based theory has discussed the entrepreneur's role in developing the opportunity and the benefits of entrepreneurial actions. Hence, the eighth proposition of the study suggested as follows:

- **Social media marketing is an opportunity for Muslim male and female entrepreneurs.**

Having said that, the research moved to the next chapter, a chapter of research methodology.

Chapter 3 - Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, a brief description of the used research methodology provided. This part presents the selected research methodology types, discusses, and justifies the appropriate research method for the study and subject. It will also inform the reader about the data collection techniques for the mixed methods approach. Moreover, the research approach, methodological design, research strategy, and data collection techniques discussed briefly to obtain and investigate findings to answer research questions and study objectives. It further discloses the sampling process used, the reliability of research, the validity of research, ethical consideration, research bias, and research limitation.

3.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to examine whether gender has any impact on Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards the use of social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. To explore the research aim(s), the objectives of this study are given as follows:

1. To explore the role of social media platforms usage by Muslim entrepreneurs in food businesses.
2. To investigate social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK.
3. To find out the gender experience of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs using social media marketing for their food businesses.

Based on the above research objectives, this research seeks out the answers to the research questions given as follows respectively:

RQ1: What are the roles of social media platforms used by Muslim entrepreneurs in the food industry?

RQ2: What are the social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK?

RQ3: What are the different gender experiences of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employing social media marketing for their food businesses?

3.3 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is a belief related to the research process in which the reviewed subject's information is collected, evaluated, and used in research execution (Salaberry & Comajoan, 2013). Research philosophy considered and play a vital role in executing the research work. The philosophical approach helps the research project to go in the proposed direction. Four different philosophies are appropriate for business and management research, such as realism, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism (Saunders et al., 2009). He further argued that research questions and research strategies could be demonstrated by linking the assumptions that followed such philosophical principles.

Robson & McCartan (2016) stated the realism philosophy understands that the aim of the subject matter controls individually ontologically. These aims exist on conceptual beliefs, practices and perception. The positivism philosophy emphasises evaluating the research work's subject, which matters from an investigation viewpoint (Salaberry & Comajoan, 2013). This type of philosophical approach focuses more on conducting structured research. Research works based on this philosophy shall combine both logical deduction and empirical researches.

3.3.1 Interpretivism

The Interpretivism philosophy emphasises more on human's viewpoint by considering them as a social factor. This philosophical research approach favours integrating human interest in the research work. Furthermore, "*Interpretivism epistemology is that researcher has to adopt an empathetic stance*" (p.107). Moreover, it is argued that "*An interpretive perspective is highly appropriate in the case of business and management research, particularly in such field as organisational behaviour, marketing, and human resource management*" (Saunders et al., 2007, p.107).

This interpretivism philosophy demonstrates that the researcher can attain a more profound understanding of the fact by taking social construction into account. These can be research instruments, languages and opinions. Similarly, interpretivism philosophy essentially focused on gaining information from human perception, and they formed an exclusive personal opinion on the same subject. Consequently, such research paradigms further help complete the research investigation correctly and have a proper foundation. This foundation provided the following of the research philosophies (Fischer & Nadeau, 2011, p.25).

In this research, interpretivism philosophy underpinned, which is known as a research paradigm focused on understanding (Cohen & Ravishankar, 2012). Although there are various developed philosophical approaches explored under the interpretivism paradigm (Mayasandra *et al.* 2006), it is believed, they are combined through analysing human interpretation, which is the foundation for the development of knowledge (Prasad, 2003). Due to this perspective's nature, the study pursues the main research aim instead of expressing a particular number of research questions. The study explores the impact of gender experience on Muslim Entrepreneurs incorporating social media marketing use for their food businesses in the UK.

3.3.2 Justification for following Interpretivism Philosophy

In this research, the Interpretivism philosophical aspects underpinned as it allows the researcher to understand the research area and the key informant's perceptions from their viewpoint. Fisher (2010) articulated the interpretative method mainly built on understanding how people in the community make sense of their world. Also, the interpretative method enables the researcher to know the key informant understanding of the subject specifically. The particular researcher focuses on gaining a deep understanding of the gender experience of Muslim male and female entrepreneurs.

Thus, this research required using a philosophy that enables the researcher to essence on human action. Moreover, the participants designate a philosophy that allows the research worker to form a personal meaning and interact with the world. That is an interpretivism philosophy paradigm (Saunders et al., 2009). This study explores both gender Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' role in social media marketing strategies, so interpretivism philosophy is suitable (Saunders et al., 2009). This philosophy advocated the researcher to understand better the opinion of Muslim entrepreneurs and social media marketing.

3.4 Research Approach

Bryman and Bell (2011) proposed two dissimilar approaches in-between academic theory and practical research, and both of them deal with results regarding reality? In light of the deductive approach, the researcher observes research interaction theoretically and present the statistical data (Ormerod, 2010). On the other hand, the inductive approach indicates theoretical framework is the foundation of understanding, which is formed from the literature review, respondents' responses, and innovativeness throughout the research process by ascertaining and recognising the new outcomes and pursuing reality (Bryman & Bell, 2011). The qualitative and quantitative research approaches have unique structures (Bryman & Bell 2011) and distinct purposes and contrasting characteristics to gather the respondents' data (Creswell, 2013).

Qualitative and quantitative research approaches are the two most essential investigation methods of research across all subjects (Doyle, Brady, & Byrne, 2009). The interpretivist paradigm majorly followed in the qualitative approach. The qualitative study undertakes a small portion of the sample and presents a wide range of results from one and each research participant (Bryman & Bell, 2011). It is usually intended to look at how and why things are remained as (Patton, 2002). On the other hand, the positivism paradigm mainly followed in the quantitative approach, and quantitative studies remain known as a set of numerical data and follow the deductive technique to discuss the hypothesis.

The third type of research approach is known as the '*mixed-methods*' approach that combined the qualitative and quantitative approaches (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004) in one study (Doyle, Brady, & Byrne, 2009). Therefore, Johnson & Onwuegbuzie (2004) have illustrated natural complement, a reasonable and a possible choice to deal with the disadvantages of quantitative and qualitative approaches when employed independently (Denscombe, 2008; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Compared to the independent single research approach, this research selected a mixed-methods approach. It is essential to understand both qualitative and quantitative research approaches and their features, which further increases the success of mixed-methods study (Jogulu & Pansiri, 2011).

As said earlier, the Interpretivism philosophical study approach selected for this study. This is because of the nature of this research and associated with Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' engagements and how they share their experiences about social media marketing uses for their food-related SMEs (Bryman & Bell, 2015). This research is exploratory. Its purpose is to identify and analyse the various social media marketing strategies that British Muslim entrepreneurs must employ to successfully engage and retain their customers. The measuring criteria for successful customer engagement and retention would depend on the increase in their sales volume of the given entrepreneurial business.

The target market equally divided into males and females. The proposed research will follow an exploratory sequential research design (Creswell & Clark, 2011) for exploring the research question and specifying conclusive solutions. It will also prove effective by laying a groundwork that will suggest future studies and provide the foundation for impressive research (Ridley, 2012). This study anticipated in-depth interviews and an online survey questionnaire; both instruments used to collect Muslim entrepreneurs' data. The researcher is following both inductive and deductive approach. An exploratory sequential research design follows two phases: qualitative and quantitative (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Thus, qualitative research applied an inductive approach, while quantitative research followed a deductive approach in this research (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012).

3.5 Mixed Methods Research Design

The research nature enforced the researcher opted for mixed-method research design after the philosophical underpinnings decided, which showed flexibility in offering multiple choices, options, and research approaches when carrying research process (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The research design presents the blueprints for the research author to use the mixed methods (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2009) and symbolises the events to gather, analyse, interpret, and report specified research (Creswell & Clark, 2007). Several research designs applied within the paradigm of mixed-methods approach (Creswell, 2013; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2009; Creswell & Clark, 2007); understanding research design natures is central to decide the design that most suitable for the proposed research and helpful in organising and providing comprehensive direction on the mixture of particular methods in research (Creswell, 2013). Mixed-methods research design comprises both qualitative and quantitative approaches and selected that the researcher could not depend on the interview data only, but also opted to undertake the online survey questionnaire to provide more detail, supporting and explaining the interview's findings (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). Consequently, mixed-methods

enable the researcher to explain their quantitative research findings alongside qualitative (Wheeldon, 2010).

Generally, there are six different prototypical versions of mixed-methods research design, such as the explanatory sequential design, exploratory sequential design, convergent parallel design, the embedded design, transformative design, and multiphase design (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Therefore, the research investigates both gender Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' role in using social media marketing strategies in the UK. Similarly, this particular research is *exploratory* in nature (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Thus, exploratory sequential research design most appropriate in this study (Creswell & Clark, 2011). For example, *what are the factors, why are they different? To what extent do they differ?* Following figure 4 presents an illustration of the current study.

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Figure 4 The Exploratory Sequential Design

Creswell (2013) explained exploratory sequential mixed methods design "*A design in which the researcher first begins with qualitative data and analysis and then uses the findings in a second quantitative phase.*" In general, employing this research design requires a detailed understanding and exploration of the research problem (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Venkatesh, Brown, & Bala (2013) clarify a sequential mixed method design is the aptitude to deal with

both exploratory and confirmatory research queries in the same study investigation. Although building and allocating importance to gender's experiences of male and female Muslim entrepreneurs related to social media marketing strategies, a questionnaire is employed to present the aim/objectives affirmation for the preliminary findings (Jogulu & Pansiri, 2011).

In this study, the selected approach strengthened by the reality that exploring the research problem involved more than one research phase. Terrell (2012) pointed out that findings were facilitated with the relationship of depth and breadth. Furthermore, it presents an in-depth view because it uses a qualitative approach to offer a meaningful view into the research problem and it widens the research to generalise the preliminary findings following the quantitative approach (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Briefly, this selected research design enabled the study with double rationales of extending one deeper understanding of the subject by conducting interviews with a small group and increasing the generalisation graph by then researching a more significant sample.

It is selecting an exploratory sequential mixed-methods design in research that allows the research author to cop limitations of the qualitative approach associated with generalising the results in a broad context by applying a quantitative method in the following stage. Following the same structure, the investigator seeks to study the aspects that focus on the qualitative research using a small sample size and afterwards looks at the known aspects recruiting a set of a significant sample size of respondents.

As shown in figure 3.1, this research followed an investigation under two diffident research distinct phases (Creswell & Clark, 2011). It is important to appreciate the core features of both qualitative and quantitative study approaches and vital to recognise the major problems, i.e., the priority of the research phase and sequence.

In this research, understanding the contextual importance and the emergence of new factors (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004) related to social media marketing utilisation by Muslim entrepreneurs in food SMEs, it is assumed that following qualitative phase first in this research considered useful for some reasons. Firstly, Cronholm & Hjalmarsson (2011) allow the study subject to be explored when phenomena have no significant amount of knowledge about the fact. Secondly, Creswell & Clark (2007), it is a constructive design where a smaller amount identified initially about the key variables studied. Lastly, it is also valuable as a research approach to get a further understanding before collecting a large amount of data via a survey (Creswell, 2013).

Due to these reasons, the research design initially incorporates qualitative research encompassing in-depth semi-structured interviews (Creswell, 2013) with participants, such as business owners and managers (Muslim entrepreneurs) running SMEs in the UK. The qualitative study initially provides the opportunity for the respondent's standpoint to the surface, facilitating an understanding of the rationales behind choosing to employ or not to employ social media marketing in their businesses. The preliminary findings from the qualitative research informed and laid the foundation to formulate the questionnaire for an online survey which generalised the initial findings (Creswell, 2013). More information regarding the implementation of this research, such as research instruments, data collection, data analysis, and interpretation, is presented in the following sections of the research.

3.5.1 Rationale for Mixed Methods Selection

Opted that research nature is exploratory, which seeks to recognise the employment of social media by Muslim entrepreneurs run food SMEs. Moreover, subsequently, create a research framework that provides guidance and direction on the uses of the latest technologies; applying one of the qualitative or quantitative approaches in research alone was not the idea that may provide a clear sense of the highlighted problems for the following reasons. Saunders, Lewis,

& Thornhill (2012) demonstrated that it would be somewhat questionable, presenting findings from just a quantitative study approach, as the qualitative research approach enables acquiring in-depth data analysis, mainly when it provides a natural setting or helps the researcher understand the behaviour of human from their standpoint.

Regardless of presenting an offer to the research author to get a deeper understanding and insights of the subject undertaken for research, a single qualitative research approach does not present a full view of the research problem (Bryman, 2003). Following this methodological approach, the researcher less competent to randomise the sample of the research. Consequently, it holds two main issues: a lack of repeatability (Schofield, 2002); and generalisability limitation of the study findings (Saunders, 2011; Gable, 1994).

In contrast, only a quantitative research approach faced criticism for exploring the research problems that build the attention of this study (Wang, Fu, & Duan, 2011), following a mixed-methods research design authorised by numerous researchers (Creswell & Clark, 2011; Cronholm & Hjalmarsson, 2011; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). A combination of qualitative and quantitative research approaches facilitates to offset the known limits linked with the single approaches (Cronholm & Hjalmarsson, 2011; Creswell & Clark, 2011) and develops the strong point of every single research approach producing effective and advanced research investigation (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Cronholm & Hjalmarsson, 2011).

Due to human behaviour and differences, males and females acting as entrepreneurs have different beliefs, values, and features that influence their gender using social media marketing strategies. Accordingly, the researcher used qualitative and quantitative approaches for its data collection (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, a mixed-methods approach presents detailed view of aspects that may influence social media utilisation. A qualitative research approach enables the aspects to be investigated by key respondents and acquire evidence on the prior unexplored subject (Hesse-Biber, 2010). A quantitative research approach looks for generalisability by engaging in a large sample size (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Creswell & Clark (2007) reported that a mixed-methods approach provides a significant opportunity for answering the research questions. It enables the researcher to explore the subject more effectively.

Moreover, to obtain significant research results (Jogulu & Pansiri, 2011; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004), the researcher selected the mixed-methods approach in this research for two purposes. Firstly, the initial use of social media and some research investigations addressing its employment in organisational settings (Parveen, 2012) suggests a need to explore in-depth examination and better understand the adoption of social media in food SMEs. Secondly, the research approach accumulated qualitative and quantitative approaches (Brannen, 2005) to effectively understand the problem of research (Creswell, 2013; Creswell & Clark, 2011;). Jogulu & Pansiri (2011) further support that it increases the research certainty, consequently advanced the research phenomenon and knowledge, and provides more relevant and trustworthy findings (Brannen, 2005; Cronholm & Hjalmarsson, 2011).

In the end, to recognise the aspects that affect the adoption of social media marketing in food SMEs, this investigation attempted to "*Fit together the insights provided by qualitative and quantitative research into an effective solution*" (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.16).

3.5.2 Research Strategy

The researchers debate the research strategies being qualitative or quantitative equally. Nevertheless, research strategies are not commonly exclusive; therefore, these can be linked with mixed methods research design (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2016). The researcher required a detailed understanding of the selected strategies best fit to research aim and objectives. The strategy of research offers the options of the style in which to build the research. Yin (2009) illustrated several distinct research strategies, for example, survey, case study, archival analysis, experiment, and history (Yin, 2009). The research questionnaire is an element that selects the research strategy (Yin, 2009).

Moreover, Yin's (2014) resources and time for the investigation also affect methodology selection. In this research case study and survey, both strategies for study phase 1 and study phase 2 followed respectively, it will be employed to support the mixed-method study. In-depth interviews and an online survey questionnaire will collect data from Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK in this research. In-depth interviews will be taken place in the United Kingdom. This has been explained additionally in the data collection part.

Epistemology philosophy links what establishes adequate knowledge in research (Saunders et al., 2009). In this study, the investigator employed an interpretivism approach. According to the research aim and research questions, the author anticipates attempting to understand the globe through the participants' eyes and recognise their standpoints once data is composed. This approach is highly suitable for this research, as every single Muslim entrepreneur is likely to pose a distinct interpretation for the question asked during the interview. On the other side, it may be required that the ethnographic approach is superior to understand respondents' behaviour by exploring openly to place where respondents reply accordingly. An ethnographic study takes a long time to gather data than an ordinary study. However, due to time constraints,

this type of research method is unsuitable for collecting accurate and sufficient data in a small portion of the time.

As the literature describes, "*Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible*" (Denzin & Lincoln, 2003, p.4); consequently, a qualitative method will be better suitable for collecting the data. It will also allow the researcher to identify the respondent's standpoint and study the 'how' and 'why' behind their digital marketing use.

3.5.3 Study Set-Up

Having chosen a suitable research design, as mentioned earlier in the first phase of the study conducting interviews is the primary data collection technique used. In this part of the research, the study organises to select and develop research tools. To accomplish the research aim, section 3.6.1 offers an overview of the research instrument, the in-depth interview, to justify its application as a data collection technique and then followed the more detailed discussion of using a specific research instrument as semi-structured interviews.

3.5.4 Case Study

Bromley (1990, p.302) argued that a case study is a "*Systematic inquiry into an event or a set of related events, which aims to describe and explain the phenomenon of interest.*" Similarly, a case study is useful in understanding an event or a topic in real-life and the answers? How? Why? Dudovskiy (2018) stated that the ability to record complex real-life experiences to research a subject to a greater extent is one of the benefits of applying a case study for a study. Also, a case study can produce understandings of a subject and its context, facilitating a comprehensive set of data to develop the theory (Saunders et al., 2016).

Many studies have been using a case study as a research strategy in business and management for a long time, highlighted creating reliable and generalisable theoretical contributions (Flyvberg, 2011). However, the study used a small size of sample as part of qualitative research. The research applied interpretivism philosophy followed the case study strategy to obtain detailed descriptions, analyse data, and connect with literature to improve, produce, or extend a theory (Saunders et al., 2016).

Sekaran and Bougie (2013) depicted that the case study strategy focuses on collecting data about a specific aim; therefore, in this study, Muslim entrepreneurs are selected. As discussed above, the chosen case study strategy can produce valuable insights through an in-depth research about the subject presenting a comprehensive set of data for analysis (Dudovskiy, 2018). Adopting a case study strategy will generate valuable data on the experiences of gender towards social media marketing strategies used by Muslim entrepreneurs, which can be analysed to present managerial implications to small and medium-size food businesses in the UK and contribute to theoretical knowledge.

The justification for using interviews as the other method of data collection is that as well as attempting to measure the differences of Muslim entrepreneurs running food SMEs, the research aims to capture key informants who are an important part of the debate on social media marketing uses. In-depth interviews provide the most appropriate method for extracting those views.

3.5.5 Survey (Online)

In research, many different research strategies can be used to design a research project. Some of these include survey, case study, grounded theory, action research, archival, and experiment research. These strategies belong either to the deductive tradition or the inductive tradition, although as Saunders et al. (2012) indicate, designating strategies to a single research approach is exceptionally simple.

This research deployed a second strategy as a survey involving the distribution of an online questionnaire. The survey strategy is generally related to quantitative research within a positivist paradigm. In contrast, in-depth interviews are connected to qualitative research within an interpretivist paradigm. However, as discussed earlier, the Five-point Likert scale used in the survey also generated percentage representations of the data.

The justification for using the survey strategy is evident as the study aims to explore the gender experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs using social media marketing for food businesses in the UK. In order to validate and generalise these gender experiences, access is required to large sample size, and a questionnaire seems the most appropriate and convenient way to gather this information, especially as it was not easy to conduct interviews directly with female entrepreneurs due to cultural background.

3.5.6 Sampling

The population in this study is only Muslim male and female entrepreneurs selected from all over England to explore the gender experiences in social media marketing uses for their businesses. It is argued that the sample size is equivalently vital during the process of data collection (Creswell, 2013). Probability and non-probability are the two foremost sampling techniques. The probability sampling technique is not very suitable in the qualitative study; however, this technique is not followed in this study (Marshall, 1996; Ritchie & Lewis, 2003). Marshall (1996) proposed three different sampling techniques for qualitative approaches: convenience sample, theoretical sample, and judgment sample. Saunders et al. (2012) non-probability sampling technique is suitable to undertake the qualitative research. In the intended investigation, non-probability sampling is employed. Besides, the sample size can be selected according to the study aim(s) and objectives.

This research followed non-probability sampling, which involves purposive sampling as a primary analytical tool to undertake this research (Creswell & Clark, 2014). It is suggested by Saunders et al. (2012) that the interview method is suitable to gather qualitative data in a non-probability sampling technique. Moreover, conducting 5 to 25 interviews is considered an appropriate sample size, where the investigator collects data through an in-depth interview method (Saunders et al., 2012, p.283). Creswell (2013) further supports that a sample size of 20 to 30 participants is vital to construct theory, but the sample size may be more significant, depending on the research problem. Hence, this research recruited 20 Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK for conducting the interviews. In this study, both non-probability purposive sampling techniques (Creswell & Clark, 2014) were applied because of the easy-access issue from the researcher side to get a deep understanding from the respondents. This is not only a cost-effective sampling technique, but it also takes a small portion of time when compared with different sampling techniques.

However, a purposive sampling method was used that involved convenience, and snowball sampling for this study due to the small sample size and the respondents were chosen because of their knowledge, capability, and experience on uses of social media marketing and strategies, and to obtain rich information on research questions and objectives (Saunders et al., 2012). The researcher selected participants who have knowledge and experience of employment of social media marketing and its strategies. Consequently, directors and senior managers selected for this research. Moreover, according to the Office of National Statistics (2016), Muslim entrepreneurs' majority population live in the East, Midland and north-west of England, such as Bradford, Leeds, Manchester, Birmingham, and London; therefore, the qualitative research limited population for interviews to England; but the online survey carried out across the United Kingdom.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

This research followed both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Data were collected using primary sources of data collection techniques (Crowther & Lencaster, 2012). The quantitative study comprises questionnaires and structured interviews; however, the qualitative study includes semi-structured/open-ended questions, in-depth interviews, observations, open-ended questionnaires. (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill 2012). Similarly, qualitative data enabled the researcher to gain personal insight by recognising the dissimilarities in opinions and values and used various human actions, whereas the quantitative research approach has offered the researcher understanding data about gender. Having said this earlier, the researcher conducted interviews with Muslim entrepreneurs and requested them to share their experiences regarding social media marketing and strategies that they are using for their businesses. This primary data was collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews and an online questionnaire. This further helped explore and evaluate comprehensive knowledge in social media marketing and its correlation with building the brand identity in the digital age in the UK (Ridley, 2012).

3.6.1 The Use of Interviews in This Study

Having said earlier, an interview technique as a research instrument was employed to collect the data in the first phase of the study. The interview technique is mainly followed as a research method in a qualitative study (Quinlan, 2011) in several different subjects, such as business research (Cameron & Price, 2009). It is believed that conducting intensive single interviews with a small sample prove significant as it investigates their perception and perspectives about a specific subject, course, or situation (Boyce & Neale, 2006, p.3). Interviews are a kind of conversation that happens between the interviewer and interviewee. It is *"Initiated by the interviewer for the specific purpose of obtaining research-relevant information and focused by him on content specified by the research objectives of systematic description, prediction or explanation"* (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2013, p.307).

Interview as an instrument of research has proved to produce rich data, particularly towards a research question (Schultze & Avital, 2011), and it is also known as a key instrument to collect the primary data for the study (Myers & Newman, 2007) used interpretive philosophical framework (Quinlan, 2011). In essence, an interview is a key of view exchanges (Kvale, 2008) about a subject of common interest between interviewer and interviewee, such as a value (Cameron & price, 2009), a method of learning (Edwards & Holland, 2013) and a 'societal relation' (Myers & Newman, 2007). Briefly, the interviewer connects with the interviewee directly to produce a complete contextual and authentic viewpoint of a research problem (Schultze & Avital, 2011). This helps the researcher discover the subject of research in a philosophical and significant way as the researcher gets the door to explore the interviewee's depth, detail, and personal experience instead of an apparent experience (Schultze & Avital, 2011). As the study aims to extract rich data by exploring social media marketing employment by Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK, conducting interviews in this study is vital for collecting the data. It is considered that the interview is a data collection instrument; the following stage will be a selection of approach to be used in the interview.

In particular, unstructured, semi-structured, and structured are the main types of interview in a research study (Edwards & Holland, 2013); however, all approaches share common characteristics and have many different issues in these approaches too, including adaptability and flexibility level (Cameron & Price, 2009; Myers & Newman, 2007). The qualitative studies widely followed the unstructured and semi-structured interview approach, whereas the structured interview technique frequently generates quantitative data (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). The semi-structured interview is undoubtedly prevalent in the two interview techniques in a qualitative study (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). Therefore, the nature of this research opts that a semi-structured interview approach is the best approach for data collection in this study.

Having decided semi-structured interview for this study is justifiable, as Saunders et al. (2012) argued that this data collection tool suggests an opportunity for the interviewees to build up their understanding of the research subject. Hence, it enables the interviewer to investigate subjects' perceptions (Daymon & Holloway, 2010). The semi-structured interview technique enabled the interviewer to employ a protocol of interview that comprises a prearranged open-ended questionnaire sheets (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). Therefore, it presents an upper level of flexibility (Cameron & Price, 2009) and provides a comprehensive direction for the researcher to explore respondents' views on social media marketing uses' critical issues. A pre-set of open-ended questionnaires following a semi-structured interview approach enables the interviewer to recognise the critical research problems interconnected to the subject (Daymon and Holloway, 2010).

Quinlan (2011) states that research comprises five essential kinds of interviews: one-to-one interviews, the telephone interview, the focus group interview, the photo-elicitation interview, and the online interview. However, the researcher explored the phenomenon of gender experience of Muslim entrepreneurs using social media marketing for their food business, examining in-depth knowledge, as per the nature of subject undertaking by the researcher, the researcher conducted one-to-one interviews, face to face interviews, and over the phone interviews with key participants (Quinlan, 2011). Concerning the first qualitative phase of the research follows a semi-structured interview technique, which looked suitable to allow interviewees to give in-depth and rich information about problems to use or not use the social media marketing for their business while exploring the gender experience of Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK.

3.6.2 Interview Protocol Guide Used in this Study

The literature on entrepreneurship, gender, social media marketing, and relevant theories was reviewed to develop the interview protocol questions (see Appendix 3). The questions were gathered from critically review of literature focused on entrepreneurs, gender-based experiences of employment, SM platforms, social media and marketing strategies in the UK food SMEs.

3.6.2 Data Collection Methods Used in this Study - Phase 1

Phase one, an initial and foremost qualitative data collection phase, encompasses in-depth semi-structured interviews with key informants. In this study, a total of 20 in-depth interviews were conducted with Muslim entrepreneurs. As stated previously, research investigation and its nature required qualitative and quantitative data to be collected to achieve the research objectives. The interviews further met the study's interpretive requirements and generated qualitative data based on the qualitative aspects of the study. The qualitative research method used to explain the social questions of research that employed a small number of participants to collect personal information.

There are many significant advantages of a qualitative study, both in standard and in this research:

- The participant's viewpoint (those being studied), what they comprehend as meaningful and essential was collected from the interviews;
- The researcher and what was researched have a close relationship. The researcher in qualitative study seeks a close connection with the people being explored so that he or she can openly recognise the area of research through their lens;
- The collected data and its analysis have a close relationship.
- This can be seen in chapter 4, where the findings are reported; and
- The qualitative approach helps to collect rich and deep data.

The summary of the first main phase involved in conducting the semi-structured interviews in this study are given as follows:

- An introduction to research (see Appendix 1) and consent form (see Appendix 2) were shared with a stakeholder who did participate in the research.
- Interview protocol guide (questions) for semi-structured interviews formed (see Appendix 3).
- To confirm the clarity and understanding of the interview questions, the researcher conducted one pilot interviews with stakeholders who did not take part in the 'real' set of semi-structured interviews (Quinlan, 2011, p.273). The pilot study did not let out any problem in participants' understanding of the questions or themes, so the researcher was sure to continue the main part of the interview to collect the data for the research. As was the case when listing questions for the survey and implied to prior, the researcher concluded that any questions reckoned as sensitive by participants on or personal note were escaped.
- In-depth interviews were then conducted with participants, as given in Table 2. These key participants included a different range of individuals encompassing eleven males and nine females. A brief profile of each interviewee and the rationale for their involvement are presented in Table 2.
- In two interviews with male Muslim businessmen face to face and one to one, the other nine interviews were conducted over the phone. On the other side, interviews with female Muslim entrepreneurs were conducted over the phone only because of cultural limitations. Consequently, organising interviews with female Muslim entrepreneurs was quite challenging.

Table 2: Profile of Research Participants

Interviewee(s)	Job Role	Gender	Location
Participant 1	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 2	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 3	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 4	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 5	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 6	Senior Manager	Female	Bradford
Participant 7	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 8	Director	Male	London
Participant 9	Director	Male	London
Participant 10	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 11	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 12	Director	Male	Birmingham
Participant 13	Senior Manager	Male	Manchester
Participant 14	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 15	Director	Male	Leeds
Participant 16	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 17	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 18	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 19	Director	Female	London
Participant 20	Director	Female	London

3.6.3 Transcriptions of Interviews

As discussed previously, a tape-recorder was used to record the interviews. All the recorded interviews were transcribed into Microsoft Word. Then interview transcriptions were printed out to begin the qualitative data analysis (a sample interview transcription can be provided upon request).

3.6.4 The Use of Questionnaire in this Study

In the part of the survey strategy, the online questionnaires associated with quantitative data collection. They are mainly employed to test hypotheses and answer the set questions using the data collected. Wiersma (1985) argued that the questionnaire is a list of questions in which participant is required to write or chose an answer that may be different from multiple choice to a comprehensive statement. It is further supported by Saunders et al. (2015) that in social research, the employment of a sample survey is a valuable and popular method. The study's questionnaire employment provides the researcher confidence over the research process (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015). Therefore, questionnaires give a larger quantity of collected data from a significant population cost-effectively. If the researcher understands the desires and how to measure the variables, questionnaires are known popular and efficient technique for collecting data. Lewis-Beck *et al.* (2004, p.2) stated that: "*Questionnaires are used to collect data that is unavailable in written records or cannot be readily observed.*"

There are two main types of questions in any questionnaire: structured or closed-ended questions and unstructured or open questions. In structured questions, respondents have to choose between set responses; it may consider as multiple choice. Such questionnaires are simple to complete as they do not ask for the extra effort on the participant's side. On the other hand, unstructured questionnaires involve open-ended questions.

This type of questionnaire does not limit the research participant to choose from a limited number of answers but instead requires them to provide their viewpoints, opinions, and thoughts openly. Unstructured questions are difficult for the participant to answer, and consequently, they are more time-consuming. There is no need to write a questionnaire as a list of questions; it can be structured as a scientific process developed for a particular purpose. That is why "*A questionnaire is a scientific tool; therefore, it must be constructed with great care in line with the specific aims and objectives of investigation*" (Oppenheim, 2000, p.37). Evans (2002) further adds, "*Statements on questionnaires collected through investigation must be relevant to the specific objectives of the investigation*" (p.71). Therefore, structured questions were only followed in this survey.

3.6.5 The Development of Questionnaire in this Study

This research followed exploratory sequential research design (Creswell & Clark, 2011). The qualitative study was initially conducted and analysed following the thematic analysis technique (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The critical review of literature focused on entrepreneurs, gender-based experiences of employment, SM platforms, social media and marketing strategies in the UK food SMEs and preliminary findings from the qualitative research informed and laid the foundation to formulate the questionnaire survey items (see Appendix 4), which generalised the initial and qualitative findings (Creswell, 2013). The qualitative categories and themes were obtained through qualitative data analysis and then subsequently quantised (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). The main themes developed from the interview's findings were presented similarly to the questionnaire survey. This study investigated several variables (i.e. SMU, SMI, SMC, BA, CFB and Gender Experiences) related to social media marketing, gender and entrepreneurship.

3.6.6 Data Collection Methods Used in this Study - Phase 2

Once phase one data was collected from interviews, the researcher moved on to phase two of the study. In phase two, mainly quantitative data collection was involved. A self-completion questionnaire was sent as part of the survey strategy applied for this study with key informants, the second data collection method. In this questionnaire, a list of close-ended questions provided the participants with multiple choice to express their opinions for this research (see Appendix 4). The researcher had already looked at the questionnaire carefully about what type of questions or themes can be observed as sensitive by participants on gender, ethnicity, and cultural note. This is because stating how Muslim male and female entrepreneurs run the business is a sensitive subject and often avoided.

Participants were contacted online in all six main regions of the United Kingdom to participate in the survey. As said above, Muslim male and female entrepreneurs who run a food business and use social media marketing were selected within the six key regions, such as Bradford, Leeds, Manchester, Birmingham, London, and Glasgow. The reason behind the participant's location and its importance in the United Kingdom context is presented earlier in section 3.5.6. The demographics were presented in the findings in chapter six, together with the participant's business profiles. All the questionnaires were sent online to the participant's social media business account, that further adds credibility and validates the participant's response after reviewing his/her social media platform for survey participation. That is how both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs were recruited to participate in the research. As stated earlier, the generated response rate of 28.70% was received, with 120 responses received out of 418 questionnaires: the participant's complete demographic information and findings presented in chapter 5.

3.7 Ethical Issues

In order to conduct this research, ethical and confidentiality guidelines followed significantly, as it was an important factor to conduct this research. The researcher was honest and transparent with the twenty interviewees and an overview of the research and rationale for the study provided. Firstly, the researcher has followed the academic Research Ethics Policy devised by the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), where the researcher is undertaking his doctorate thesis. At UWS, it is not allowed to commence any research until approved through its peer-reviewed ethical approval process. The approval process of research ethics is consistently reviewed and assessed according to suitable practice recommendations to undertake scholarly study and any legal requirements, such as the new law on data protection (GDPR). The ethical approval procedure understands issues such as anonymity, data protection, confidentiality, and consent. Additionally, the researcher provided the participant's consent sheet (see Appendix 2) before recording the interview (Saunders et al., 2012). In this sheet, the researcher sets out the research purpose that includes the research's aim(s) and objective(s) and highlights the voluntary nature of the research and participant's interview withdrawal option at any time.

This demanded to complete a research ethics form to commence a preliminary self-assessment concerning the ethical issues for this study. This practice significantly important in this study, as research stakeholders are cautious about their privacy and information. In this research, a complete application for ethical approval was submitted by the researcher. Once it was approved, then research commenced. Participant information sheets were given to all Muslim Entrepreneurs before participating in interviews. The researcher followed Creswell (2013) and Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) guideline for ethical considerations and confidentiality processes displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: Ethical Considerations and Confidentiality Protocol.

<i>Ethical Considerations and Confidentiality Protocol.</i>
1. Guarding the Interviewee's identity and information
2. Guarding the Interviewee's confidentiality and the collected data from the research
3. Guarding the Interviewee's anonymity
4. Declaring the purposes and intentions of the research
5. Must accept voluntary withdrawal from participant
6. Avoidance of any ambiguous and false data reporting
7. Manipulation of the results and implicating self-work
8. The approval of the participants in research involvement
9. Consideration of the effect of nature of data collection on participants

Source adapted from Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) and Creswell (2013).

The ethical approval process highlighted that the research participant's confidentiality and anonymity were ensured, and collected data managed securely and efficiently that protected the confidentiality and saved in folders on the laptop, which require a password to unlock and access the data and identity of participant that security safe the participant's data would not be revealed to any unauthorised person or party. Each participant's consent was collected before commencing the interview recording.

In terms of research ethics and data management, all the collected data stored safely, securely, and not in the range of any unauthorised person. The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All collected data from participants were managed in accordance with the provisions of this Act. Following new development concerning legislation, all collected data from participants will now be managed according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.8 Data Analysis

The data analysis is known as "*A process of piecing together data, of making the invisible obvious, of recognising the significant from the insignificant, of linking seemingly unrelated facts logically, of fitting categories one with another and of attributing consequences to antecedents*" (Moore et al., 2012, p.25). As stated above, two different sets of data were collected in this study: the first data set from in-depth interviews and the second data set from the online questionnaire.

3.8.1 Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data analysis interlinked with Interpretivism. Research participants' spoken sense about a phenomenon allows the researcher to recognise the experiences and socially developed meaning of the research objective (Saunders et al., 2012). Similarly, meanings are extracted from words (data) in a qualitative study; it is vital to analyse data collected carefully through patterns, themes, and behaviours (Dudovskiy, 2018).

The qualitative data in study phase 1 collected through interviews with the twenty Muslim entrepreneurs running food businesses in the UK. In the case of in-depth interviews with research participants, the interviews with both the male and female entrepreneurs were recorded using a researcher's digital recorder. These interview recordings were then played back, and each interview recorded was transcribed onto the Micro Soft Word file by the researcher. This process developed a comprehensive set of field notes. Two interviews were conducted in person with male entrepreneurs, and the rest of the eighteen interviews over the phone with both male and female entrepreneurs.

The qualitative data analysis comprises of developing findings instead of results (Bajpai, 2011). A simple semi-structured format was adopted in this qualitative data analysis to analyse the data through the well-known NVivo software. This enables the reader to pinpoint the responses derived from the interviewees. The researcher then includes their interpretation of each response and then draws comparisons with the other responses collected. The primary data gathered is further broken down to identify the main themes developed from the responses.

In this research, the qualitative method thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) analyses the in-depth interviews. Thematic analysis is a technique for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns or themes within data (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.79). Thematic analysis is a highly flexible analysis method that can be adapted for any research requirements in any particular area, such as exploring the respondent's experience (Cassell & Symon, 2013). However, in order to analyse the theme author will identify the key themes of each transcription. This method of analysis is specified because these techniques match with in-depth interviews in this paper. NVivo software will be employed to support these analyses. The six stages of thematic analysis were followed and encompass: the researcher familiarising himself with the data by transcribing and reading it; initial coding; searching for themes; revising themes; defining themes; defining and naming the themes; and analysing them systematically (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

The main themes developed from the research interviews were interrelated with the main themes developed from the online questionnaire. Other main themes from the data collected are then discussed later in the discussion chapter and linked to the presented conceptual research framework and the literature reviewed in chapter 2.

3.8.2 Quantitative Data Analysis

To analyse the quantitative data from an online survey, a well-known software package, SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences), was employed to the responses recorded to the questions. All the generated descriptive statistics were used to explain and make sense of the data collected. The produced descriptive statistics were predominantly percentages and frequencies, which were demonstrated via tables and graphs (Zikmund et al., 2010).

Two-way ANOVA analyses were conducted to find the impact and relationship between independent (SMU, SMC, SMI, BA and CFB) variables and dependent (gender, ethnicity and business types) variables; bivariate correlation analysis performed to test the hypotheses through SPSS software version 26. according to the emerged themes from the study.

Moreover, as discussed above in this chapter, the online questionnaire as a survey strategy was employed to collect data at stage two of this study due to time constraints, but not concerning this research's complex quantitative approach. Consequently, this is an exploratory sequential mixed-method research approach (Creswell, 2013) where the qualitative methods followed thematic analysis and offered the main results' validity and credibility in the quantitative study. Furthermore, there were no number of open-ended questions in the survey questionnaire.

3.9 Bias and Limitations of the Methodological Approach

Quinlan (2011) argued that bias, known as anything, infects the research. It is significant to understand the question of bias when undertaking research. Simply a researcher's feeling may initiate bias into the research. In this study, the researcher ensured that he conducted this study with an unbiased mindset and has not allowed his job experience as a social media marketing manager and being a Muslim researcher during this research there to allow his judgement to be clouded. Every single stage of this study has been carefully accounted for in research to minimise the biasness of the research process.

Therefore, a pilot study was undertaken for phase one of data collection, and further study passed through a comprehensive process for ethical approval. As an ethical and capable researcher, the researcher believes that he has guarded this research against researcher bias.

To render other potential biases linked with this study, i.e., participant bias, the researcher believes every attempt made to reduce these biases. In the case of participant bias, the researcher also believes that every attempt was applied to ensure that research participants were given an honest response in both interviews and online surveys.

Furthermore, the pilot study ensured that the interview questions and developed themes were clear and would not influence the responses provided in a particular direction. The researcher has taken extra care that enabled him to constantly check and consider that his point of contact and relationship with any participants would not affect the research interview in any way.

Sampling was initially considered another limitation of this research. In the case of sampling bias, the researcher has chosen the samples for both the interviews and online questionnaire accordingly with methodological rigour. However, the researcher could not collect the questionnaire's desired sample size in the second stage of the study because of COVID-19 since Coronavirus has majorly affected the entrepreneurs running food businesses in the UK and worldwide.

The validity of the research may come into question if it is deemed to be overly subjective. However, *"In cultural research, this way of thinking about validity is problematic because it is believed that knowledge is never value-free and that no method can deliver an ultimate truth about the state of matters in social life"* (Moisander & Valtonen, 2006, p.24). Clark (1998) further recognised that it is impossible to undertake any study, which may be free of the researcher's views and perceptions and the research.

Conducting interviews with female entrepreneurs was considered another limitation in this study. Since this research recruited both gender male and female participants, female Muslims were hesitant to let the researcher conduct face-to-face interviews due to cultural background. However, interviews with female entrepreneurs went smoothly and in an excellent manner over the phone. Consequently, female Muslim entrepreneurs feel much more informative and expressive over the phone.

The researcher found that time constraint was an important limitation in conducting the interviews with Muslim entrepreneurs in this research. The researcher also faced time management issues from the participant's side, so interviews were rescheduled on many occasions. Furthermore, the interview process was disrupted on many occasions, as one of the interviews was conducted inside the shop (Participant-2). Indeed, some interviews were carried out in two parts (Participant-12). In addition, that interview was carried out on a stop and start basis because the participant was required to serve their customers. It was observed that some of the participants had a limited number of staffs. Thus, future researchers should allow sufficient time to conduct the interviews (at least 3 or 4 hours) and set up the appropriate venue before their interview. Furthermore, the researcher should be prepared for the interviews so that no opportunity will be missed. Female respondents agreed to participate in the interview process instantly.

3.10 Reliability and Validity of Research

Bryman & Bell (2003, p.33) reliability is known "*By the extent to which the results of a study are repeatable. For a qualitative study, reliability is concerned with the degree to which the features of the study's design are congruent with the research inquiries.*" The reliability issue in research is significant as it refers to "*The accuracy and precision of the measurement and the absence of differences if the research were repeated.....for a research result to be reliable, a repeat study should produce the same results*" (Collis & Hussey, 2014, p.52).

This study focused on exploring the Muslim entrepreneur's gender experiences using social media marketing, and based on the literature review, a conceptual research framework was developed. Muslim entrepreneur's case study strategy followed with in-depth semi-structured interviews was considered suitable for data collection that would precisely assist in collecting the data from entrepreneurs.

However, the researcher needs to acknowledge that the reliability question is interpreted differently by the qualitative and interpretivism measures, such as research interviews do not need to be reliable in the positivist sense (Collis & Hussey, 2014, p.53). Instead, the emphasis is more on "*Establishing protocols and procedures that establish the authenticity of the findings*" (Collis & Hussey, 2014, p.53). Therefore, similar sets of interview questions following a semi-structured format were asked to ensure that the research results are reliable. In this research, clear protocols were implemented at every stage of the data collection to ensure the research's reliability. These protocols are made clear earlier in this chapter, where the data collection methods adopted are outlined.

The researcher needs to consider the validity of the research. Quinlan (2011, p.42) defines validity as "*...how logical, truthful, robust, sound, reasonable, meaningful, and useful the research in question is.*" The researcher feels confident with the test of validity in this study. There are two types of validity, such as internal validity and external validity. In the case of internal validity, the researcher developed the research questions for the interviews and the online questionnaire cautiously. This was done to ensure that the provided responses are related to the research aim(s) and objective(s). Furthermore, the findings and results are drawn from the collected data (Saunders et al., 2012, p.372).

In the case of a qualitative study, validity involves selecting the right conceptual questions. The case study research strategy was employed in this research; validating using construct validity was considered by the researcher. Uses of SM marketing by Muslim entrepreneurs evaluate the concepts that were based on an exhaustive literature review. Also, interview questions were derived from literature review concepts and validated by the researcher's supervisor. Moreover, in terms of survey validity, the questionnaire was also pilot tested, as described above in this chapter. This development followed accordingly with Quinlan's guidance (2011), who further stresses out features that a pilot study can increase the validity of data collected through the instrument, such as an online questionnaire or survey. Saunders (2012) also supported that how a pilot study may help a questionnaire's face validity. It emphasises the significance of the integrity of research conclusions (Bryman & Bell, 2003).

3.11 Summary

In this study, a mixed-method followed the exploratory sequential design, qualitative and quantitative, to study the gender experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs using social media marketing in small and medium-sized food businesses in the UK. With the qualitative approach being the initial and primary method. The employment of both approaches permits the rich knowledge of the subject and knowledge of the aspect being investigated. This chapter discussed the observed sitting for the qualitative and quantitative phases of this study, which involves developing instruments such as interviews and online questionnaires, data collection, sampling approaches, data analysis techniques, bias and limitation of the research, research reliability and validity. Figure 5 provides an overview of the research processes identified by the researcher in this research.

Figure 5 Overview of the Research Processes

Chapter four, which is the next chapter, will provide the interview (qualitative study) findings of the research.

Chapter 4 – Qualitative Findings

The main aim of this chapter is to present interview findings. This research's findings have revealed four main themes that explain how the gender experiences of Muslim male and female entrepreneurs towards the use of social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. The first theme of this section has explored social media elements and social media marketing strategies. The second theme entrepreneurial opportunities of Muslim entrepreneurs through social media communications. The third theme analysed the impact of both gender male and female entrepreneurs on whether there is any difference between them. The fourth theme will measure the entrepreneurs' social media marketing performance.

In this section, findings are presented from the in-depth interviews with research participants. The terms research participant(s) are used interchangeably throughout this section and chapter, as interviewers and respondents. The findings are presented based on the key themes that were explored in the interview guide. In total, 20 participants have interviewed out of 11 research interviewee(s) males and nine females; complete detail of each interviewee and the reason for their inclusion given in Table 3 of chapter 3. Appendix 5 provides the interview research participant's demographics details, such as gender, job role, location, etc. Quotes used in this chapter to highlight responses from interviewees or respondents are attributed to relevant research participant through reference to their designated code as categorised in Appendix 5. The names of each research participant were not revealed to keep their anonymity protected and comply with ethical requirements, as explained in chapter 3. However, reference to designated code when quoting will allow the findings to provide valuable insights into the source or origin of the response/comment and allow, where relevant, possible links between the research participant and the type of response/comment registered.

4.1 Elements of Social Media Marketing

In this exploratory study, the research explores the several elements of social media marketing by Muslim entrepreneurs that run the food businesses in the UK:

1. It sheds light on entrepreneurs, both male and female's social media perception.
2. It informs what types of social media platforms employed by the entrepreneurs in food SMEs in the UK.
3. It finds how social media used as a marketing tool by entrepreneurs.
4. It explores the social media marketing strategies applied by entrepreneurs.

4.1.1 Social Media Perception

Social media contributes in many different ways in the business and marketing for entrepreneurs; of the interviews, the researcher found several different views about social media perception. Participants have expressed their different views about social media perception that are given as follows:

“Social media for my mind is Facebook, networking, do networking with social media, we can share our views, we can make relationship basically for networking” **(Participant -1-M).**

“Initial perception is usually how are you posting daily updates, regular updates and online” **(Participant- 2-M).**

“So, when we talk about social media it means Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, Snapchat and all other online communities’ stuff” **(Participant- 3-M).**

“The social media mostly regularly used phenomena by people and businesses it is a platform where people and organizations communicate, interact, engage, and provide services to the target audiences” **(Participant- 4-M).**

“In today’s day and age, I believe social media is one of the biggest consumer attractions as it caters to millions around the globe. It helps people from various ends to connect. Although vast usage is harmful but that does not mean it unhelpful. Especially for the business environment it varies” **(Participant- 5-F).**

“Contact people more directly, contact with the customer in terms of a relationship I feel like a social media is something which is a key to business especially” **(Participant- 6-F).**

“Yeah social media digs in, I mean there’s some word of mouth through social media. Social media nowadays is a big thing, everything’s on Instagram and Facebook, snapchat. Everybody uses these social media, so I think it’s a good way of advertising” **(Participant- 7-F).**

“Social media is very important nowadays for marketing for any kind of business. Obviously, there are pros and cons of social media” **(Participant- 8-M).**

“Social media from the business perspective is strictly how you connect with the customers a lot. You can read their reviews; you can learn from the customers what they like or don’t like about an establishment and change things if needed. From the business perspective it has allowed us to engage more” **(Participant- 11-M).**

“My initial perception is that within the environment that we are operating, social media is very relevant and prevalent. A lot of the local eateries use social media to market themselves. The popular ones, of course, are Facebook, Instagram, which is very popular with food establishments, Twitter, not so much but definitely Facebook and Instagram. Snapchat is also being used but it’s not as prevalent as Facebook and Instagram” **(Participant- 12-M).**

“I think, social media for business, I think it’s a good tool to increase profits in terms that your brand gets out there and people are aware of it” **(Participant- 14-M).**

“Because social media, everyone is on social media. There is hardly anyone that doesn’t use social media so yeah, like Facebook” **(Participant- 15-M).**

“I actually think it is a really good thing, especially in the world we live in now as everything basically does revolve around social media” **(Participant- 16-F).**

“I think social media is one of the fastest growing platforms. It consists of quite a few different platforms and pages that people can use to grow, the top ones being Instagram, Facebook, Twitter” **(Participant- 17-F).**

“I think social media drives everything. You are nothing without social media I feel like it is required for your business and for things to be successful. That is why it is such an up and coming idea because it can create everything from nothing” **(Participant- 18-F).**

“It’s just a different way of approaching things on social media, it is not an instant source of income I would say” **(Participant- 19-F).**

“For social media, I think there are pros and cons. In terms of business I feel there’s a lot of growth and people that have made great livings and great businesses from using social media and I think that you can really focus towards a specific target market” **(Participant- 20-F).**

Figure 6: Social Media Perception (NVivo Codes)

Table 4: Social Media Perception

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Social media's perception is varied from entrepreneurs to entrepreneurs that includes it as a marketing tool, popular SM, and networking.	Social media perception	SM Views Popular SM Marketing tool

The first and utmost perception of social media was informed. Out of 7 participants revealed that they found social media helped the business to connect with their customers. Three participants followed this informed that social media enable us to engage, communicate and interact with customers as a marketing tool. Moreover, social media is good for networking (Participant-1-M) and regular updates (Participant-2-M). Out of 4 participants informed that their views about social media are, using and becoming available on Facebook, Instagram and Snapchat; this was further followed by 2 participants, included Twitter and YouTube.

They also mentioned that these platforms are very popular and proliferating. Social media is used for business success and marketing purposes (Participant-8-M, Participant-18-F, & Participant-20-F); social media has positive and negative effects on business. Findings indicate that entrepreneurs use popular social media for business and marketing purposes.

4.1.2 Social Media Platforms

Social media platforms enable entrepreneurs to use this opportunity to set up their online presence and interact with customers. The interviews revealed that the Muslim entrepreneurs are using many different kinds of social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, and Twitter, in the food businesses to market their products purposely see Figure 7. The following responses exhibit the entrepreneur's choices for social media platforms uses.

“First and mostly we used is Facebook, secondly use the google and thirdly I use TripAdvisor and fourthly I use some social networking tools for local areas called offer for local which is like a business direction which is very useful because mostly I stick on FB, google and TripAdvisor only three” (Participant -1-M).

“At this moment Instagram and Facebook okay” (Participant -2-M).

“As I mentioned in my earlier stage that all mainly used social media platforms and I am using for my business are Facebook Instagram YouTube Google plus and then very rarely Twitter” (Participant- 3-M).

“Mainly Facebook Instagram and a Snapchat for our business” (Participant- 4-M).

“Majorly I use Facebook, twitter” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, that would be Facebook Instagram Twitter we are also using a Snapchat now on and we are going to be used a lot more going forward and also videos of YouTube” (Participant- 6-F).

“Mainly Instagram and just sort of, yeah, I do put sometimes on Facebook but mainly Instagram” (Participant- 7-M).

“Right now, we use mostly Facebook and Instagram. We also have a Twitter account, a website and an email list” (Participant- 8-M).

“We are on everything. Facebook, Instagram, twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, Snapchat and there is a new platform called TikTok” (Participant- 9-M).

“I use only Facebook; I find that Facebook works well for me” (Participant- 10-F).

“Right now, we are using Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and the Google business page as people can still share photos on it when they are your establishment” (Participant- 11-M).

“We are actively using Facebook and Instagram” (Participant- 12-M).

“We are only using Instagram and um, Facebook. Just 2 of them” (Participant- 13-M).

“I am using Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and TripAdvisor” (Participant- 14-M).

“Mainly 2—Facebook and Instagram” (Participant- 15-M).

“At the moment I use Instagram, that’s the main one that I use. WordPress is just a little blog that I have on the side” (Participant- 16-F).

“At the moment it is only on Instagram for myself however I am currently in the making of producing a website/blog that will include a lot of my previous work, for example, my full reviews, restaurant visits, my invites and PR. All of this will be concluded on one page on one platform, but it will work alongside my Instagram” (Participant- 17-F).

“Just Instagram but I think I have a Facebook page that is automatically connected to it, so anything uploaded to the Instagram goes onto the Facebook page, but my main focus is Instagram” (Participant- 18-F).

“As for now it is only Instagram that I use but I do plan on expanding to YouTube” (Participant- 19-F).

“Currently I am using Instagram as my main platform and I am currently making a website but at the moment Instagram is the only thing that is active” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 7: Social Media Platforms (NVivo Codes)

Table 5: Social Media Platforms

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Social media platforms are known as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat & YouTube. Muslim Entrepreneurs consider these platforms to be easily accessible, commonly used and have many features.	Social media platforms	Facebook marketing Instagram marketing Twitter marketing Snapchat marketing YouTube marketing

The majority of the 18 participants informed that Instagram was the major social media platform. Out of 15 participants, this indicated that Facebook was the major social media platform in the food industry. Six participants informed that Twitter is mainly used social media platform, Snapchat and YouTube both are also getting popular social media platforms according to other entrepreneurs (Participant-3-M, Participant-4-M, Participant-9-M Participant-16-F, & Participant-19-F). Moreover, 2 participants revealed that Google plus and TripAdvisor are the least used social media platforms.

On the other hand, 3 of the participants informed that they only use the Instagram channel for food business because food pictures only attract customers, so they only prefer Instagram as a preferable social media platform. The findings from three female entrepreneurs indicate that they are building websites/blogs on the side where they can bring all reviews and restaurant invites to one place. Consequently, it can help them manage easily (Participant-16-F, Participant-17-F & Participant-20-F).

When further asked, the entrepreneurs provide the reasons for choosing these specific social media platforms. The following responses revealed the entrepreneur’s reasons for social media platforms uses.

“Yes, the first reason Facebook has the largest customer data base, I believe 99% our customer has FB account. Most of them use their FB account regularly” (Participant -1-M).

“No. 1 It is the most generally used platforms Number two it is easily accessible for overall customer number three is the accessible for all our businesses number for apart from this Snapchat customers regularly checks on us” (Participant -2-M).

“There are many reasons behind this selection, firstly these are most powerful social media platforms and tools which are known as social media that are easily accessible, secondly word-of-mouth every single person is using Facebook, Instagram and all the professional people use Twitter. Thirdly All social media are free to use and easy to use and so on” (Participant- 3-M).

“Facebook Social media we use to let the customers to know about our business where we are based what we do therefore Customer can call us and leave us a message via Facebook page. Instagram social media platform We use to share the updates to the customers and the audience on the other hand side Snapchat videos to increase other followers” (Participant- 4-M).

“I have chosen these because these are the most common used and accessible platforms that caters to mostly everyone” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes and these are the most popular if you read the blogs and everything that’s like the most people signed up to, you know what Facebook have a very high percentage of followers users and the Instagram if I am saying basically they’re going to use the most popular site which will gave them the more exposure” (Participant- 6-F).

“I mean I daily check Facebook and I daily check Instagram so to me they are both the same, but I see other people using Instagram more than Facebook” (Participant- 7-F).

“Like I said, I think it is really important to use social media for your business, whatever business you have” (Participant- 8-M).

“I just think that’s the way the world is moving at the minute. It’s instant, everybody seems to be on some type of social platform now. If it is not Instagram, people are on Facebook. If it’s not Facebook, it’s just something people have access to that within seconds and the world, everybody well, I would say, 70-80% of people who have a mobile device will be on social media” (Participant- 10-F).

“After we took over these pages, we started realising the benefits that you can get through this, we were able to communicate with customers easily. It was seen as another means of communication from our perspective” (Participant- 11-M).

“I think Instagram is the mostly used social media platform these days. And Instagram has become such a big market to sell your products.... they don’t have a special shop like Facebook where you can buy and put all of your products, you can just upload your pictures. But the best way to sell your product nowadays is Instagram” (Participant- 13-M).

“I think that covers everything. Facebook, Twitter and Instagram cover all people. Because a restaurant, you’re not saying to people, you’re saying to people who want to eat, and this is where I cover most of the demographic” (Participant- 14-M).

“The reason for that is the people on Instagram they like to share it on Facebook at the same time. That makes it a lot easier to you know, to do that” (Participant- 15-M).

“To be honest, I made a Snapchat for the food page, but I didn’t really get a good response as not many people were adding it. I think people preferred to see the stories on Instagram. I have a Facebook page as well, but it is not used as much because I find Instagram works best” (Participant- 16-F).

“I have chosen Instagram because my target audience is mainly those in their mid-teens up until young adults. That’s why I solely chose Instagram for me to start off on and to go with it to reach my target audience” (Participant- 17-F).

“It is the most versatile; it approaches a lot more people, people my age and people interested in food use Instagram more than any other social media” (Participant- 18-F).

“Initially it was very user friendly and another important thing that it has is a lot of privacy that you can hold as long as you can make it personal while remaining professional. YouTube and Facebook, I feel is not very professional even though as a lot of people do it, but I don’t feel comfortable doing it. On Instagram I can post pictures and use stories and other aspects of Instagram that interest me” (Participant- 19-F).

“I have had previous experience on Instagram, and it is the platform I have most experience with” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 8: Social Media Platforms (NVivo (codes) Mind Map)

Table 6: Social Media Platforms

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Social media platforms are known as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat & YouTube. Muslim Entrepreneurs consider these platforms to be easily accessible, commonly used and have many features.	Social media platforms	Easily accessible Commonly used Have extra features

Out of the six entrepreneurs, findings depict that social media platforms are easily accessible; therefore, social media enabled us to communicate and quickly reach customers. Adding to this, participant-1-M and Participant-10-F both highlighted that 70% to 80% of customers who have access to mobile phones use social media platforms and are free to use. This was followed by five entrepreneurs indicating that these are the most commonly used social media platforms. On the other hand, out of 4 participants informed that social media enabled the entrepreneurs to target the customers according to their needs. Participant-19-F social media further added social media provided much privacy that makes it personal while remaining professional. Moreover, such platforms have many new features to reach customers via posts, stories and direct messaging. The majority of respondents mentioned that social media platform helped entrepreneurs get the benefits from social media uses as they provided entrepreneurs with the opportunity to become visible to customers.

Therefore, the findings suggested that Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat and YouTube are the primary platforms used in small and medium-sized food businesses by Muslim entrepreneurs (See Figure 7). Furthermore, the results also indicate that most female entrepreneurs observed that Instagram is significant and Facebook is the second leading social media platform. Female entrepreneurs further added that Instagram is the platform where they feel familiar and most experienced. Whereas the majority of male entrepreneurs observed

Facebook as the major and Instagram is the second leading social media platform. As indicated by participant-6-M, Facebook has a very high percentage of followers and users than any other social media platform.

Social media and its employment transformed the entrepreneurial business methods of running their businesses. Social media offers several key entrepreneurial opportunities; entrepreneurs create social media pages, i.e. Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter accounts. Therefore, the first and second proposition answered and given as follows:

P 1: Social media encourages entrepreneurs to create social media business pages.

P 2: Social media encourages entrepreneurs to use popular social media platforms.

4.1.3 Social Media as a Marketing Tool

Social media plays an important role in marketing the food business with prospects and customers. Social media enabled entrepreneurs to run a successful business; participants informed that social media as a marketing tool is the most productive way of running a business in today's world. The following responses provide the entrepreneur's marketing purpose and utilisation of social media.

“This is the only productive way in today's world to communicate and interact with the customers” (Participant -2-M).

“And the most important thing is it also help you to grow your business in many ways social media can help your business Easily accessible all new and all products online visible to all the customers they can buy online they can contact you they can review you they can share your Visible information to their friends and families etc.” (Participant- 3-M).

“So, I would say this is a need for every single business do use of social media marketing for their business purposes and engaging with the customers to communicate with our customers to update our customers to show them what we are doing being local with our audiences” (Participant- 4-M).

“Everything is online. Yes, of course. Social media has become a backbone of every single business. If you're not on social media, you will find it hard to sustain your business” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes like I said there is a need to reach out to the customer who are not aware of my Lahore, therefore we really want to get the brand out there as well as we have to make sure we have to offer we want to show off the product we have and the environment and atmosphere produced there yes” (Participant- 6-F).

“6-7 Years ago. We didn’t actively use it to market the business, but we had pages set up. No one was actively looking over them” (Participant- 11-M).

“We looked at competitor analysis while researching. Also looking at their marketing strategies and what they were doing, the main platform that they were using was social media. We also spoke to some freelance consultants who said that social media is the way forward for your company to promote itself. Then we researched it and decided that we should take the step towards using social media as a marketing tool for the business” (Participant- 12-M).

“I think this is the most effective and most direct way to interact with your customers nowadays. Because everything is going online” (Participant- 13-M).

“But I think social media is something that increases the brand awareness, and it also increases your awareness of where you are, and I think that’s what brings people into the restaurant. And I think it’s really useful if you want to reach new people, social media is the new way forward” (Participant- 14-M).

“The reason I know it helps is because we have so many people coming in and they show me the picture on the video and they say you know I’ll have this. so basically, that means obviously they did check your social media because otherwise they won’t show me the picture” (Participant- 15-M).

“Of course, I started it in 2016 but that doesn’t mean I started it as a business but more of a hobby. Slowly as my followers increased that’s when I had companies and brands reach out to me to work with them. It was a very slow start to be honest and it has taken time” (Participant- 16-F).

“I feel like social media is a great stepping-stone for you to start and build on” (Participant- 17-F).

“This is an important tool that you need for a business otherwise you cannot reach out to different people that you want to reach out to whoever you want to reach out to. I feel that this is an integral part of a business” (Participant- 19-F).

“This current food business is very new for me, so I am exploring and making contact and seeing what other people are doing” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 9: Social Media as a Marketing Tool (NVivo Codes).

Table 7: Social Media as a Marketing Tool

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Social media, as a marketing tool, enable entrepreneurs to communicate, interact, and increase their brand awareness.	Social media as a marketing tool	Brand awareness Interaction Communication Everything is social media

The majority of the 6 participants informed that social media had helped their businesses boost brand awareness; thus, social media supported their businesses to become successful. Participant-15-M added that customers visit the sites after exploring social media pages and order by showing the food pictures. This was followed by 3 participants that social media is the most productive way of interacting with customers online; another 2 participants added that social media make them easy to communicate with customers. On the other hand, out of 4 participants revealed that social media is the way to be in a food-related business. It highlights that everything is going to be online since social media has overtaken the market. Participant-12-M further added that after researching and analysing competitors' marketing techniques and freelancer consultations, social media marketing is the way of moving forward.

Therefore, the findings revealed that the Muslim entrepreneur's main aim is to use social media marketing to increase brand awareness, customer interaction, customer communication, and the more the brand are aware of customers, the more it will increase business success and sustainability.

4.1.4 Social Media Marketing Strategies

- **Analytics**

Analytics is the most widely used tools for designing a strategy and measuring its performance; it is free, simple to set up, and compelling. These analytics enabled the entrepreneurs to design the social media marketing strategy and understand what type of audience to target and which types of marketing activities need to run to reach customers to achieve their marketing goals.

Below are the responses that depict the entrepreneurial techniques for social media marketing. Responses are as follows:

“At this moment I don’t use them because I do have google app downloaded to my iPad and Facebook app, they give me every week some kind of statistics. How many clicks I got it in particular location and how many customers visited me” (Participant -1-M).

“Yes, we do use their social media marketing tools such as a Google analytics and Google ads words and it basically help us to get the insights that are for us who have actually visited our website and how much time and what activities they had while they were visiting our website” (Participant- 3-M).

“To be honestly not at the moment this is a small business and the only running a few social media networks like our Facebook” (Participant- 4-M).

“I have heard about the klout and the Hootsuite but I’m not actually using them because of Facebook and google gives us the basic insights to target the right audience that helps us to increase the business performance” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, I do I use schedule tool that allow me to generate the report which is great” (Participant- 6-F).

“No” (Participant- 7-F).

“There’s so many tools that you just have to go and kind of adopt and use, Like Hootsuite is like a social app” (Participant- 9-M).

“Well just by looking at it to see how many people it’s reached. The organic reach, then the page reach, and how many new followers, how many new likes I’ve got, how many

comments I've got on the back of it. So, that's gives me a good indication of the posts that are working, the posts that are attracting people" **(Participant- 10-F)**.

"The company we outsource for our social media, I don't remember the names of the tools, but I have seen some of them being used. I remember seeing Hootsuite, but I can't remember the other tools" **(Participant- 11-M)**.

"No, I don't know I don't, I got my, own excel sheets from my own sales and stuff" **(Participant- 13-M)**.

"Only the Facebook one where it's the generic you know, reach and share stuff. Nothing else" **(Participant- 14-M)**.

"No. the only thing that I do check is you know because on social media when you do the paid advertisement, it gives you a report every day" **(Participant- 15-M)**.

"I have heard of them recently and I am quite interested and am looking into it. At the moment I wouldn't say I have used them as such. However, through Instagram, they do have their own analytics anyway" **(Participant- 17-F)**.

"As for now I run it on my own but there are some tools for management on audience review and how posts are doing on Instagram, so I look at those stats. This is called Insights" **(Participant- 19-F)**.

"I am not really sure, but I have used paid promotion before. Like when your ad goes onto other people's stories so you would have to pay Instagram a small charge for your post to show up in other people's feeds. I have used that before and I have noticed that the posts that I do that for do a lot better but I don't want to pay for every post so I am just trying to be as consistent as possible and hopefully the audience will come itself" **(Participant- 20-F)**.

Figure 10: Social Media Marketing Strategies (Analytics, NVivo Codes)

Table 8: Social Media Marketing Strategies (Analytics)

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Analytics are the most widely used tools for designing a social media marketing strategy.	Social media marketing strategies	Analytics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook insights • Instagram insights • Target customers

The majority of the 6 participants indicated that they follow the Facebook insights to market the business. These insights provide the demographics of the customer, which helps to design the marketing strategy. Of the interviews, 3 participants followed this and informed they use Instagram analytics to look at the follower’s demographics to reach target customers. Another 2 participants added that they are using google analytics and google AdWords to investigate their behaviours. However, out of 2 participants informed that they are not familiar with these tools; therefore, they do not use them.

The findings show that the significant majority of entrepreneurs focus on using analytical tools such as Facebook insights and Instagram insights (see Figure 10). However, some of the entrepreneurs shown a lack of technical skills. When further explored how these analytics and techniques help measuring social media marketing and its progress. All the participants as indicated below:

“Yes these automation tools specifically the marketing tools are very helpful these tools help to design the marketing strategy to target the audience and the interact with the customers what type of food promotions and marketing strategies should have designed to keep in touch with the customers to grow the revenue” (Participant- 3-M).

“Not using these marketing tools at the moment so I don’t think so these would be saying helpful at the moment sorry about this question brother” (Participant- 4).

“Yes, very helpful. It allows us to see how well we did” (Participant- 6-F).

“I do not know” (Participant- 7-F).

“It might be useful to have that and look at stats. We actually get monthly reports from our outsourced partners and while we don't use them, they probably use them to generate the reports” (Participant- 11-M).

“Well, they just, they just tell you how much people view your page or like your page, that's it” (Participant- 14-M).

“Yes, for sure as I do feel like without assessing your target audience and knowing where you are standing it makes it harder for you to be able to aim” (Participant- 17-F).

“Yes, for Instagram it is helpful, but they get complicated” (Participant- 19-F).

“Instagram has made it quite simple to do that. For example, if you want a post to reach 50,000 people you would maybe pay £5 per day for a week. If you click on your post on Instagram you can monitor how many people have seen it, how many people have clicked it, how many people have sent it to others, so you get the statistics on Instagram” (Participant- 20-F).

Firstly, 10 participants simply informed the employment of analytical tools, so out of 8 participants indicated that each platform provided the insights accordingly to design and measure the social media marketing strategy. Also, out of three female entrepreneurs only suggested the social media analytics tools to measure business performance is helpful. Participant 19 female entrepreneur added that analytics' employment enhances the marketing skills and experiences, which enables looking at customers from different angles to target them. At the same time, most of the seven male entrepreneurs used many different tools to measure the marketing performance, which ultimately helped the business grow and devise the best practices to market the product.

The results also indicate that entrepreneurs who have knowledge and experiences of analytics utilisation significantly perform and design their marketing strategies. A deeper understanding and knowledge of utilisation enhances social media marketing experiences. However, half of both male and female Muslim entrepreneurs indicate a lack of technical knowledge to measure marketing strategies' performance or do not know how to utilise these tools.

- **Sponsored ads**

Sponsored social media marketing on famous social media platforms and targeting right and specific customers are very significant and helpful. Social media paid advertisement has shown an increment for the brand. Regular posting on social media by entrepreneurs allows them to engage with the customers; this engagement helped the businesses to boost quickly (see Figure 11). Participants who recorded their responses are given below:

“Yes, I pay as I said I use paid campaign mostly and yes organic very good, but it takes long time to boost your business, but FB campaign is very faster and quicker” (Participant -1-M).

“It is very difficult question, and yes, the male has some advantages physical advantages. And whereas female have some kind of a lot of problems, in respect to campaign there wouldn't big differences for FB and Google they can run the campaign. It is not a big deal and it is not issue” (Participant -1-M).

“Not as of yet, paid ads not at the moment” (Participant -2-M).

“It is always good to pay to play in such cases. I would say paid advertising is very helpful for the businesses who have started from the scratch and also it is helpful for the big brands to hold their customers all the time” (Participant- 3-M).

“Yes, these ads are very cost effective as it increases the customer engagement” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, we do only the post we believe has meaning behind it. Yes, that is kind of one message out there for audience then we will put money on to it, so these ads could be Facebook ads and Instagram ads, I haven't done twitter ads” (Participant- 6-F).

“No” (Participant- 7-F).

“Most of the time we use Facebook ads that we pay for and only done Instagram ads a couple of times” (Participant- 8-M).

“I pay for promotion of content right. So, if we have a video, we will promote that video because we want to have eyeballs on that video.... and it creates an experience. Like sriracha doesn't do paid advertising it's just word of mouth” (Participant- 9-M).

“Oh yeah, of course I do, yeah” (Participant- 10-F).

“We have used them in the past” (Participant- 11-M).

“Not anymore. We used to do it 1st year but we don't do it anymore yeah” (Participant- 12-M).

“Yeah, I do, I do. But I only do that only when I got new products otherwise I don’t” **(Participant- 15-M).**

“Yes. I took some pictures of chips for them and I got paid per picture and these pictures have been used to market their business” **(Participant- 16-F).**

“The more you invest in it, the bigger engagement you are looking to get back but I have only done it on the smaller scale” **(Participant- 17-F).**

“No, I have never tried it” **(Participant- 18-F).**

“Sometimes I do, I have done two ads for now but not much. You can post an ad for different companies” **(Participant- 19-F).**

“I think so I think I will. It is not something that I am cancelling out; I am open to be using them again” **(Participant- 20-F).**

Figure 11: Social Media Marketing Strategies (Sponsored Ads, NVivo Codes)

Table 9: Social Media Marketing Strategies (Sponsored Ads)

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	Social media paid ads is a significant feature that helps entrepreneurs to target the right customers to engage.	Social media marketing strategies	Sponsored Ads

The majority of the 16 entrepreneurs, both males and females, informed that they used social media paid advertisement for marketing considered an effective marketing tool. These entrepreneurs found Facebook ads, Instagram ads, Twitter, and YouTube ads are essential marketing tools to engage with customers (see Figure 11). As indicated by participant-17, a female entrepreneur stressed out that to get a more significant engagement level with targeted customers, make sure to have a good amount of budget to fund the campaign that will ultimately benefit the business. Participant-5 further added this. These ads were very cost-effective, which enabled a greater level of customer engagement.

On the other hand, as indicated by participant-3, social media paid ads help new businesses because these ads ensured maximum reach to customers. Participant-8 male entrepreneurs added that Instagram ads are more significant than Facebook ads because in the food business because young people are more attractive and use Instagram than Facebook or any other social media platform.

Consequently, the findings indicate that Instagram ads, Facebook ads, Twitter ads, and YouTube ads are part of a social media marketing strategy used in small and medium-sized food businesses by Muslim entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the results also indicate that most female entrepreneurs observed these ads are cost-effective and can increase customer engagement if funds allocated accordingly. Whereas, majority of male entrepreneurs observed that these social media paid ads for marketing are very beneficial, especially for new businesses and considered Instagram is more attractive than any other social media platform since it is for food business.

- **Social media trends**

Participants believed that an entrepreneur's marketing activities rely on understanding the latest social media trends, which is looking at insight and analytics. These skills enable them to maintain a good knowledge of this understanding, which depends on their social media experiences and usage. However, participants highlighted that such understanding and trends help the entrepreneurs to develop social media marketing for customers according to their behaviours and preferences. As indicated by all participants below:

“Yes, we have nearly 700 Facebook followers on our FB page. This is very good and for example this month we do very well, sometimes we go live and when we do new dishes” (Participant -1-M).

“There are many social media communication trends we are following regularly and it depends on each and every single social media platforms the one we use for our businesses, for examples The trends on Facebook Is going to live showing the people what you are doing in your kitchen, On Instagram we created the contents and follow with the link to the blog, on Twitter you follow the hashtags” (Participant- 3-M).

“As I said earlier Our main social media is a Facebook handle the most key communication trends we follow on Facebook is we always go live what we do in our kitchen is like when we have a large order another kitchens we always put our Facebook alive add on the let the customers know what we’re doing and how we are doing in our kitchen” (Participant- 4-M).

“We have hashtags, go live, communication trends, link forwarding and so on. Also, we keep up with our competitors to see the trends they are following” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, I do follow the latest blogs to be honest like TOS and HUB like that they set the most latest trends are coping about social media and on top of that she coached me on my master classes to saw social media webinar and master classes that I am aware of up and come in what change been made to social media” (Participant- 6-F).

“Yeah, I do I have quite a few followers and I follow other people. On Facebook I’ve got loads of friends, so people do see” (Participant- 7-F).

“Yeah, I do follow some of my competitors or other people who are in the same kind of industry be halal food, you know, most of the time I think we all can follow each other just to see what everyone else is doing. That's kind of similar in any kind of business that you can you know” (Participant- 8-M).

“I think you just have to be on top of things and how people communicate” (Participant- 9-M).

“Not really, no” (Participant- 10-F).

“That’s the responsibility of the outsource team” (Participant- 11-M).

“Instagram is quite popular with images, but I don’t actually deal with this aspect of the business; my brother deals with it” (Participant- 12-M).

“We don’t follow any trends, we have um, just to communicate with people, we got our own following. We got our own like, people anything who follow us, so we just, we just do business which is suitable and comfortable for us” (Participant- 13-M).

“what we will do is we will post pictures, post uh comments, we will post uh we will use emails, we use our website, that’s how we communicate with people” (Participant- 14-M).

“No, no. we do not” (Participant- 15-M).

“Personally, I don’t follow the trends at all because I just find it a little boring and I prefer to create my own content instead of following trends” (Participant- 16-F).

“Recently I have looked into it a bit more. I have not been that into trends however I do try to follow hash tags and raise more awareness through hash tag use” (Participant- 17-F).

“I don’t really follow any” (Participant- 18-F).

“Of course, definitely, I follow a lot of food bloggers and initially when I started, I did not know that this was how it would be but as soon as....., there is a lot of teamwork there are many collaborations going in” (Participant- 19-F).

“Through direct messages, just one to one at the moment” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 12: Social Media Marketing Strategies (SM Trends, NVivo Codes)

Table 10: Social Media Marketing Strategies (SM Trends)

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Elements of social media marketing	SM trends are the newest way of social media marketing strategy to engage with customers.	Social media marketing strategies	SM Trends

The majority of the 16 participants revealed that they follow the latest marketing trends to communicate and interact with customers. Out of 4 participants informed that each platform has a different approach to following the marketing trend to engage with their customers, such as Facebook allowed entrepreneurs to live from the kitchen, Instagram helped create the content and followed the hashtags. Out of 3 participants found another trend, which was following back each other online helped the entrepreneurs to know about market and customers behaviour and preferences what else is going on their ends (participant-7, participant-8, & participant-19). Participant-19 female entrepreneur further added that reviewing the restaurant food in collaboration with competitors helped entrepreneurs increase brand image and food visibility for the customers and followers from their post feeds. However, out of 4 entrepreneurs informed that they do not follow any marketing or social media trend, as indicated by participant-13, they have good numbers of followers on social media platforms, so they regularly communicate with them according to their business goal.

Thus, results inform that important social media trends are observed going live on Facebook, following hashtags, creating content on Instagram and following back each other on social media platforms. Furthermore, entrepreneurs' working together in collaboration is the newest trend by entrepreneurs to review the restaurant's food, ultimately increasing business brand awareness.

The relationship between social media and social media marketing by entrepreneurs influences business action. Social media enabled the entrepreneurs to know what their customers are fascinated with, what they want, and then deliver useful advice, information, and content (Ryan, 2017). Social media helped and positively influenced food businesses and their online presence. It is noted that business adoption and in-line formed strategies for businesses are under research in recent studies. Therefore, the third proposition is answered as follows:

P3: Muslim entrepreneurs heavily use social media marketing in food businesses (SMEs) to serve their customers.

The study explores the sample of Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK food industry. The researcher finds that the uses of social media have a positive impact on the experience of Muslim entrepreneurs. Thus, considering that the entrepreneurial experiences are fundamentally based on the employment of social media uses, this study also suggests observing the relationships between social media uses and entrepreneurial experiences. Thus, the propositions; P1, P2 and P3 accumulatively construct the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Use of social media and marketing has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial experience.

4.2 Entrepreneurial Opportunity

4.2.1 Social Media as a Marketing Opportunity

Social media's marketing role is to use it as a communication tool that enables entrepreneurs to reach their customers and makes their products online visible to those who don't know their product. It is used as a tool that creates brand awareness and promotes businesses. Thus, it creates communication, engagement, brand image, and customer retention, but minorities to grow as well. In fact, social media usage and entrepreneurial opportunity as a communication tool are so diversified that they can be used in whatever way best suits the needs of the business. All the participants' responses are given as follows:

“Of course, Because we use one of the key words which is HALAL. On our website it says HALAL. Social media networking we say it is HALAL also” (Participant -1-M).

“it is an opportunity for every single entrepreneur whether it is a Muslim or a non-Muslim whether I am a Muslim, non-Muslim, Hindu or whatever” (Participant -2-M).

“Indeed, social media is a big opportunity in 2019 for every single business and for every single person regardless it is a Muslim entrepreneur or a non-Muslim entrepreneur.... I would say social media is a very powerful tools in this era and the Muslim community is a minority in the UK, so this is how they can significantly get benefits from this opportunity by making their businesses available online and communicating with their audience or help them to grow exponentially” (Participant-3-M).

“There is no doubt social media is one of the biggest opportunities in today’s world for every single person and a Muslim entrepreneur are also one of them they must have to utilize them in a right way to get them self on top of the list” (Participant- 4-M).

“Social media marketing as I have said earlier is an opportunity. Muslim entrepreneurs can also use it to promote their businesses and raise their brand awareness” (Participant- 5-F).

“I think social media is everything” (Participant- 7-F).

“I think it's a big opportunity for anybody, not just Muslims but any kind of entrepreneur” (Participant- 8-M).

“Oh absolutely. It’s an amazing opportunity, so that’s why I think it’s an amazing opportunity and if you have the right team, the right tools, sometimes it takes more than one platform to do what you want to do” Participant- 9-M).

“Uh, well, I think it’s just um, for me, because I’m not that tech savvy, I just think it’s very powerful. It’s a very powerful tool because you do not have to wait for things to reach people, you can get to people straightaway” (Participant- 10-F).

“We want to provide this information easily to our customers by making sure we are available on all the high-profile social media platforms so people can engage with us, give reviews and ask questions” (Participant- 11-M).

“I see it as a marketing tool. I don’t see it as an opportunity. I see it as a marketing tool to keep your business in front of the customer” (Participant- 12-M).

“I think for all the businesses. Every type of, everything you can do. People are watching social; people are watching more social media than watching any biggest news channel or any music channel” (Participant- 13-M).

“Yeah, I think yes. I think social media is a good platform to increase uh, your brand out there, to the wider market” (Participant- 14-M).

“Definitely opportunity. I think it’s a cheaper opportunity as well” (Participant- 15-M).

“For Muslims, it is a great opportunity. I have a few friends that like to sell through social media stuff like halal sweets and do calligraphy” (Participant- 16-F).

“Yes, I do feel like it is one of the best ways to grow regardless of background or whether you are Muslim or not. You won’t be able to know who is behind a certain page unless you want to make yourself aware on that, it is a really good way for you to grow naturally with no setback of discrimination” (Participant- 17-F).

“It helps Muslim businesspeople, like it helps everyone else, but at times when the market doesn’t necessarily cater for the Muslim community as a Muslim, I can cater for that and provide the niche for that community” (Participant- 18-F).

“A lot of Muslim women are not allowed to work outside; this can be a way out and many people have talents in cooking. I have seen a lot of bloggers daughters who have made these accounts for their mothers [...] It gives you the confidence to start something” (Participant- 19-F).

“For Muslim entrepreneurs specifically, I feel like it has created a lot of awareness for Muslims and I think that other people can also see so that we can normalise things that maybe people don’t see often or don’t know about such as halal food.... I don’t think we should single out the Muslims; this can apply to any group. It can be any minority or anything that there isn’t that much awareness about can use social media to promote themselves” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 13: Social Media as a Marketing Opportunity (NVivo codes)

Table 11: Social Media as a Marketing Opportunity

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Entrepreneurial Opportunity	Social media as a marketing opportunity, which is considered a powerful marketing tool that increases brand awareness and communication regardless of gender and ethnicity.	Social media as a marketing opportunity	SM marketing tool Brand awareness Communication SM for everyone

The majority of the 7 participants mentioned that social media marketing is the most significant opportunity today and a powerful tool for entrepreneurs. Of the opportunity, entrepreneurs benefit in several ways, such as they are directly engaging with their customers online. It instantly reaches people by getting page likes, post comments, and content sharing. This is cost-effective marketing compared to traditional marketing, which is expensive and time-consuming and less effective. Participant-4 added that Muslim entrepreneurs from small and medium-sized businesses must use social media to lead the market. This was followed by 6 participants that indicated social media opportunity enabled the entrepreneurs to increase the brand awareness instantly and quickly due to SMM.

Additionally, social media made the business virtually available, so people can engage, leave food reviews and ask many questions about product and foodservice. Social media enabled the customers to buy things online and change the consumer behaviour about Halal products due to its excessive online availability, as indicated by participant-16-F. However, out of 5 entrepreneurs stressed out that this marketing opportunity has no issue with gender and ethnicity. Both majority and minority can benefit equally and promote businesses. Social media empowered and confident to run an online business.

Therefore, results indicate that both males and females suggested that social media is the most significant marketing opportunity for entrepreneurs who run small, medium-sized food businesses in the UK (see Figure 13). The majority of participants informed that social media as a marketing opportunity helped increasing brand awareness and communication with the customers.

4.2.2 Social Media Benefits

Social media marketing significantly different from traditional marketing strategies, Social Media Marketing (SMM) provides several advantages. First, it offers a platform for entrepreneurs to present products to customers and receive feedback and suggestions. Second, its adoption makes it easy for entrepreneurs to engage, communicate and interact with customers, which increases the brand online, and these available tools can customize for their particular needs. Third, all this is done at nearly zero cost compared to traditional marketing technique as most of the social media platforms and sites are free to use. Participants responses recorded as follows:

“I don’t want to distinguish the male and female if there is an opportunity to create new customer, it is an opportunity to create customer data base, it is an opportunity to know more about customer preferences” (Participant -1-M).

“So, as an entrepreneur the adoption of social media benefits us in many way” (Participant -2-M).

“I would say social media can help us to grow our businesses quickly. It can also help us to find out the target audiences. It can also help us to communicate, engage, interact and facilitate our customers. Social media can also help us to build an online community for a business which again can help to reach out to all our customers” (Participant- 3-M).

“Being an entrepreneur as we can get many benefits from social media adoption, such as we can promote our small businesses on a large scale, we can also get engage with other customers, we can also communicate with our customers [...] We also created a social awareness by feeding the local people quality food” (Participant- 4-M).

“There are no issues of gender to be honest. Everyone can and are using it for their business purposes. The benefits are same if you are a male or female in my opinion”

(Participant- 5-F).

“I don’t think that really matters, I mean, I don’t think it does” (Participant- 7-F).

“I think for my particular business, I benefit a lot from social media because it's the way I communicate mostly with my attendees our Festival” (Participant- 8).

“Social media enabled to us to have direct contact with tens of thousands of people. We couldn’t have gotten the database of all of these users ourselves. Social media has helped us see who to target in the future, what channels they use” (Participant- 11-M).

“You have to regularly use it otherwise the effectiveness will fade away” (Participant- 12-M).

“Gender does not make any difference on social media” (Participant- 13-M).

“I think from social media, you can only get out of it what you can put in. There are many people who have major Instagram accounts, Facebook profiles but they are not active on it. The more you put into your social media, the more you will get from it. So, you know, you use it wisely” (Participant- 14-M).

“I don’t think that there is a limit. The only reason for that is, it depends on how you do your business” (Participant- 15-M).

“I feel like personally, I have never really had any pros or cons. I have never felt like there was anything to do with gender. It has been fine for me” (Participant- 16-F).

“Through the use of different analytics or through followers and growth. I do feel like you can have a focused approach on what you want to achieve personally, as well as being able to take it onto a bigger scale” (Participant- 17-F).

“Being more consistent and using it more as there are times where I don’t use my Instagram for weeks and even months at a time. Your followers need consistency and to grow you need to keep doing it” (Participant- 18-F).

“I think they can do wonders. I have seen a couple of bloggers starting by posting pictures of their food and gained many followers then they began to sell food and began catering and that became massive” (Participant- 19-F).

“I am not really sure how to answer that question” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 14: Social Media Benefits (NVivo codes)

Table 12: Social Media Benefits

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Entrepreneurial Opportunity	Adoption of social media facilitates entrepreneurs to communicate, engage, interact with customers. It can maximise the benefits of proper skill and knowledge applied to social media utilisation.	Social media benefits	Communication Engagement Interaction SM skill & knowledge No gender issue

Adopting social media benefits the entrepreneurs in several ways, such as growing business instantly, promoting business, communicating and engaging with customers, and listening to the customers. The majority of the 5 participants revealed that social media adoption helped the business communicate and interact with customers directly. This was followed by another 5 participants indicating that social media adoption benefits the business and the right skills and knowledge to utilise social media. Participant-14-M added that businesses must update content on social media regularly and constantly to get the maximum return.

Participant-17-F and 18-F further supported that business growth really depends on a focused marketing approach and consistency for posts that followers and customers look at online. However, out of 5 participants informed male and female orientations have no influence on adopting social media for marketing, but being female entrepreneurs, noticed female customers

prefer to be served by females because they feel it is easier to order as indicated by participant-7-F.

Therefore, the results indicate that both male and female entrepreneurs suggested that the adoption of social media is beneficial for small, medium-sized food businesses in the UK. Regularly updating social media content can increase business growth and followers. Both genders, male and female, do not influence social media marketing adoption.

4.2.3 Social Media Contribution

The easily accessible social media helps the entrepreneurs get the benefits from social media uses. It offers the opportunity to set the goals and objectives to achieve. These exclusive social media features enable these entrepreneurs to design anticipated targets to attain. However, it is found that participants have different goals and objectives to succeed in business and personalise social media uses. Out of the key objectives is to have more followers on social media pages. Participants responses are as followed:

“We are up to date enough whether we are in a place for them go and update to the friends” (Participant -2-M).

“Social media marketing has Made it easy for us to run the business....and most significantly since we have a build our Facebook page we have gone up and the sales has been increased to 40 to 50% and secondly the Instagram helped out our business by increasing followers” (Participant- 3-M).

“Yes of course social media is a key player of our business it has really contributed in our business in many ways such as we have a large number of followers on our Facebook please go and check our website you will see that how large number of followers we have [...]” (Participant- 4-M).

“Yes. Especially Facebook. It is easy to promote the menu and the offers. It catches the eye of a lot of younger generation. Such as students nearby” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes we have the people coming into the branch they say we have visited us sometimes online Or if you are running a campaign which is working really well online alongside the branch so we can see that why we have added up on social media, this sort of impact from the branch as people are coming in today to the branch from social media, okay?” (Participant- 6-F).

“I would say a little bit” (Participant- 7-F).

“We are quite a busy business anyway but certainly it did help improve the customer services and customers experiences” (Participant- 11P-M).

“What we noticed is that when we have a marketing campaign for certain periods then there is an uplift in sales and footfall in the restaurant from the marketing we do on social media” (Participant- 12-M).

“Definitely, because of it, I won’t say contributed. I would say everything is done by these 2 platforms because from putting on our products to these people [...] So, I think these 2 platforms were the most effective platforms to sell our products” (Participant- 13-M).

“Yes” (Participant- 14-M).

“Definitely, definitely. I think it’s very um, it’s very helpful” (Participant- 15-M).

“I would say so yes. The opportunities that I have had through Instagram I probably would not have had if I were just working a normal job. I feel like without Instagram, without social media I would probably have never done half of the stuff that I have” (Participant- 16-F).

“Yes, because without it, it wouldn’t exist at all” (Participant- 18-F).

“I think it has as people begin to approach you as you have put that image out there and it is there for people to see and approach you if they think their product can be represented by you or as I also do reviews for restaurants so if the restaurant thinks that my reviews have been honest and out there. If I don’t present it well obviously, they won’t contact me” (Participant- 19-F).

“I think Instagram was the main marketing for my business back then when I sold my paintings and artworks, all my customers were through Instagram and even right now it is my main source of communication with other people” (Participant- 20-F).

When further asked about specific social media contribution in food SMEs, participants responses are as followed:

- **Specific contribution**

“Facebook marketing and Instagram marketing pretty much a half of the customers know about it and actually the act upon our sale so are based on that we have got a good read that whatever they do that happen however we present our-self online That’s how the customers perceive us” (Participant -2-M).

“As I said earlier each of single social media channels have significantly contributed towards the growth of business. I would say all platforms are very important and very significant for every single business and it is helping all the local businesses to grow very rapidly” Participant- 3-M).

“All I would like to say the Facebook has it really contributed in our business sale since we have joined a Facebook page and sale revenue has been increased. Secondly Instagram page has helped our business to expand and create the brand Awareness” (Participant- 4-M).

“Yeah so Facebook is a very good platform get out of awareness tell stories and news I think the platform [...] And I also say it is a very aesthetic way to please them in the eyes of viewers” (Participant- 5-M).

“So, obviously that’s payable, that comes at a cost, but I have found that has worked for me. Not necessarily instant, but it has worked where people has seen your Facebook and if they shared my page, it then reaches, well it just multiplied” (Participant- 10-F).

“If we didn’t have that I don’t know the impact of that, maybe more phone calls or people would look at other venues where people could communicate to with social media” (Participant- 11-M).

“Facebook is good for displaying mainly menu’s, pictures, videos and information. You can target a market with Facebook whereas Instagram rather than target marketing you just display more information via pictures and videos” (Participant- 12-M).

“Facebook, I think that both contributed in exactly the same way. There isn’t any difference, the only thing is that Facebook, on Facebook, we did paid advertisement in the beginning in the 1st year. So, we used little bit offer, paid advertisement and many people, came to our page with the paid advertisement” (Participant- 13-M).

“Oh Facebook, Instagram is where we showcase our food by pictures, um, what our food looks like. So, people see the food, looks nice, they will hopefully come to the restaurant” (Participant- 14-M).

“I get invited to a lot of networking events through social media so attending these events has helped me meet new people that may have small business, or are in marketing and PR. I feel like it has helped me network and grow a lot” (Participant- 16-F).

“My business has grown since I started on Instagram and then deviated away from there so yes. I also think it is about consistency as well as the platform you use, and I think Instagram is the best platform” (Participant- 18-F).

Figure 15: Social Media Contribution (NVivo codes)

Table 13: Social Media Contribution

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Entrepreneurial Opportunity	There are several different types of social media contributions: increase in followers, Increase in sales, Facebook contribution and Instagram contribution.	Social media contribution	Increase in followers Increase in sale Facebook contribution Instagram contribution

The majority of the 6 participants found social media contributed to increased business revenue and many followers. Participant-3-M added they had seen a 40% to %50 increments in the business sale because of social media marketing. Participant further supported this- 12-M that social media paid campaigns played a significant role in increasing the business sale. This was followed by 5 participants revealing that social media made the businesses aware and out in the market to everyone, such as online, local residents, competitors and many more.

This was the result of active and consistent online customer engagement. Participant-17-F added that Social media contributed to halal small food businesses to spread widely where people can have multiple options to go and eat and experience the food. Moreover, social media helped businesses present online in an efficient and better way, resulting in better service and food quality, as indicated by participant-15-M and participant-19-F.

Therefore, interviews indicate that social media platforms i.e. Facebook and Instagram, have contributed to small and medium-sized businesses. However, Facebook contributed to business sales, targeting the audiences and brand awareness because Facebook enriched with more detailed features that provide an extra description to the post. Moreover, male entrepreneurs are more inclined towards the use of Facebook. On the other hand, female entrepreneurs mainly used platform is Instagram that contributed to creating content and display the food pictures, which further included better presentation and increased brand awareness. However, participant-4-M supported that Instagram helped the business to increase awareness and followers.

The results further suggested that technology is a key player in recent times, making entrepreneur's lives easier. On the other hand, entrepreneurs as opportunists have gained benefits from social media marketing opportunity. However, the opportunity-based theory has discussed the entrepreneur's role in developing the opportunity and the benefits of entrepreneurial actions. Thus, the proposition four and fifth are answered as follows:

P4: Social media marketing is an opportunity for Muslim male and female entrepreneurs.

P5: Muslim entrepreneurs mainly using social media for their businesses that play a significant role in UK halal food industry.

Social media marketing as an entrepreneurial opportunity enabled Muslim entrepreneurs to communicate for their products on social media. The results indicated that these entrepreneurs used these social media communication tools to help the business identify the opportunity within their target audience to achieve the business aims and goals. Social media marketing as communication is further highlighted in next section 4.4.4 and suggested the hypothesis.

4.3 Gender Experiences/Orientation

4.3.1 Social Media Goals

Social media is not merely a powerful marketing tool, but it can also have enhanced almost every small and medium-sized business area. Social media is a significant channel for brand awareness, increasing business social media page likes and followers, and increasing business sales and customer engagements. Social media enabled the entrepreneurs to set different goals for their businesses; research participants have informed their goals individually and recorded responses below:

“Yes we are planning a campaign Starting in May targeting specifically all the new students are accompanying to the Manchester most specifically the university students are coming for the September sessions by their first years or the final years we are targeting them and we have set up a specific budget on the basis of Facebook and Instagram, To target and engage them attract them and we will make them aware of our brand” (Participant -2-M).

“Yes, I have a social media goal for our business. I want to see my business Facebook page will get 10,000 likes in the next six-month time and previously we have set out a goal and we have achieved it” (Participant- 3-M).

“We have set a goal for a business to become a local legend into the region with the help of social media” (Participant- 4-M).

“Oh yes. If you want to be ambitious in your business, you have to have certain goals to achieve” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes We set ourselves goals, I mean some of them quite hard to achieve due to analytic and the algorithm change on Facebook for example today for the phone to increase our followers, yeah that is the one of the goal” (Participant- 6-F).

“I don't have a specific goal. We obviously try to gain more followers. On Facebook we currently almost 7000 followers and I have a personal goal of getting 10,000 followers but I'm not trying to push towards it” (Participant- 8-M).

“Yeah, for example on Facebook, I have 4.5 thousand followers. I'd like to reach, well to me, I'd like to have 10,000 followers within 3 years” (Participant- 10-F).

“Not in terms of numbers or achieving a target number of likes. If any customers send us queries, we aim to respond to them effectively and quickly. If anyone leaves a review, we try to respond to that as well” (Participant- 11-M).

“So we are looking to rebrand and have a fresh new menu for customers.... This is what we are looking to do” (Participant- 12-M).

“I don’t have any particular goal to make it the biggest business on social media but it’s working though, so I’m happy with it” (Participant- 13-M).

“So, the competition will be tag 4 people you’d like to bring to the restaurant and share it. Hopefully that will increase the brand awareness, the restaurant as well” (Participant- 14-M).

“I would say my Instagram goal would of course be to gain more followers because the more followers you have means more money and more influence” (Participant- 16-F).

“In terms of future goals I would like to grow my page even more to the point that I run my own website and people can come back and use it a guide for them and to be known in the halal food industry and to be able to grow within that” (Participant- 17-F).

“Not really, it is just something that I enjoy doing. I have not really set any social media goals” (Participant- 18-F).

“When I initially started my goal was to reach maybe 1000 followers and as for now, I am going for more and more. I feel that there is no stopping once you start, I guess the goals keep increasing. Now I want to expand to YouTube to increase my audience and things like that” (Participant- 19-F).

“I want my account to be interactive and it to be a sort of community, so I am more connected to the people that are on my page” (Participant- 20-F).

When further researcher tried exploring different set goal and objectives and asked their social media future marketing plans. Participants responses are as followed:

- **Future plan**

“We couple of month ago; I am trying to build up my own social networking page for local people” (Participant -1-M).

“I can’t tell you too much I don’t know myself much whatever the campaign to launch in May still have a few months left” (Participant -2-M).

“Yes, we are planning to adopt a new social media goal in the next three months” (Participant- 3-M).

“We have not set any social media goal for next 12 months’ time....,” (Participant- 4-M).

“We would like to improve our Instagram page and the offers for Facebook” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, our plan is just going to maintain the what we are currently doing as well as making improvement you know we generate more ideas, we got very good design team on our side which allow us to run the good content about our story behind my Lahore. That story going to told more on social media ahead” (Participant- 6-F).

“Our main goal would be the Facebook and Instagram ads” (Participant- 8).

“I think I’m spending around £50 a month on Facebook, but I think its maybe time to increase it to £100. Hopefully I do believe that my business would grow by another 30-40%” (Participant- 10-F).

“The only thing I can say is that we are going to incorporate it into the daily system that works within the restaurant to respond to customer reviews quicker than spending 1 hour on it or a couple hours a day on it. Being able to respond to it using a unified point of sales system” (Participant- 12-M).

“I think right now we will just be doing what we are doing, no special plans for it. we are doing well, and we are going to follow and keep doing what um, what we can give the best right now” (Participant- 13-M).

“No plan, for me it’s simple” (Participant- 15-M).

“As I said, I am really looking into YouTube at the moment, once my equipment arrives, I will begin YouTube” (Participant- 16-F).

“I have put a lot of effort in my food page and sometimes in the past with certain reviews I had done were just temporary so it was a wasted effort so I want to put it somewhere where people can fall back onto to read” (Participant- 17-F).

“In the next year, definitely I want to promote more” (Participant- 18-F).

“One is to introduce YouTube to my Instagram so that my videos are available on YouTube because I mostly post pictures on Instagram and I want a proper video of my posts so people can always go to my YouTube to go to the whole video” (Participant- 19-F).

“By then I do want to have a Facebook page and a twitter but at the moment Instagram is doing fine so I don’t think it will be anytime soon that I open these other pages. I just want to focus on one platform and creating a community on it at the moment” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 16: Social Media Goals (NVivo codes)

Table 14: Social Media Goals

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Gender Experiences/Orientations	Social media empower the entrepreneurs to increase the number of social media followers, business sale and brand awareness.	Social media goals	Increase in followers Increase in sale Brand awareness

The majority of 10 participants informed that their social media goal is to increase the number of followers that help their business grow. The second largest number of participants indicated that they are using social media to increase business sales. This was followed by 5 participants informing that their main social media goal is brand awareness; this is the top reason entrepreneurs use social media. Participant-12-M added that due to the nature of business such as food and customer demand, it is found online business rebranding will give a new edge in the market.

Therefore, the results suggest that both male and female entrepreneurs increased Facebook followers, whereas only female entrepreneurs were depicted, especially in Instagram followers. However, one of the female entrepreneurs informed that she does not want to increase the

followers, but an interaction the page that keeps the flow of business up. On the other hand, one male and female entrepreneurs indicated using many more robust social media platforms. Two male entrepreneurs suggested that paid advertisement is their next social media goal to reach the maximum reach since Instagram and Facebook help the halal food business.

4.3.2 Social Media Significant Platforms by Gender

Social media is by far the most popular channel available to small businesses. It allows the entrepreneurs to select the different essential platforms, which help share the information with targeted customers and benefit the businesses in many ways. Muslim male and female entrepreneurs inform their choices for choosing significant social media platforms. Participants responses are given as follows:

“I would say FB and Google and it also depends on customer review. In my view I would say FB, Google and TripAdvisor” (Participant -1-M).

“It’s just the way how do you use it doesn’t matter which platform you use how are uses it depends how do you engage with the customers” (Participant -2-M).

“According to my experience in social media marketing for my business I would suggest the Facebook marketing is more significant in terms of local businesses Instagram and Snapchat or the big social media network channels which can help the business to grow rapidly quickly on a large scale if you have a large budget” (Participant- 3-M).

“I would suggest every single social media platform is a significant for the business [...] I would go for the Facebook marketing the reason of Facebook marketing is every single person is using Facebook. So, this means that Facebook has one of the largest sets a database in social media world so I would go for the Facebook” (Participant-4-M).

“Facebook at the moment is bigger in attracting customer for my business. And as I have said, male and female in social media does not matter. That is what I would like to believe” (Participant- 5-M).

“I think Instagram, I think I would rate it as 8 and maybe Facebook as 7” (Participant-7-F).

“I have noticed and use Facebook mostly because Facebook is also graphic based as well as Instagram” (Participant- 8-M).

“I think hands down Instagram. It is specifically for that, following what you are doing, and their algorithms favour you if you have good content” (Participant- 9-M).

“Well for Facebook you mean, for my business, are you talking about my business or general businesses?” (Participant- 10-F).

“From our perspective, Facebook is quite big. Our following on Facebook is significantly more than Twitter or even Instagram so it has had quite an impact on our business” (Participant- 11-M).

“Instagram at the moment” (Participant- 12-M).

“I think for business, Facebook and Instagram is a way better thing than any of the social media network” (Participant- 13-M).

“Oh, I would say Instagram or Facebook” (Participant- 14-M).

“I don't know like to be honest, like I said I use Facebook, so I think Facebook is one of the biggest [...] so I think you know snapchat, Instagram, these are obviously very popular right now, but I think there is more people on Facebook than on Instagram or um Snapchat all these” (Participant- 15-M).

“I would definitely say Instagram and YouTube. I feel like they are the most used and I feel like you can always get your product and message across through both channels” (Participant- 16-F).

“Personally, I think Instagram is one of them main and biggest ones for my field and me. I would also say Facebook is really good as well as you do suit another age range, but it is a bit different to Instagram” (Participant- 17-F).

“Instagram is definitely one of them and also Facebook, depending on the target market” (Participant- 18-F).

“I think YouTube and Instagram are very good tools, especially Instagram because it a very secure platform and it keeps your data very secure and you can obviously use it to expand to a writing blog or a blog on YouTube” (Participant- 19-F).

“I'm only familiar with one platform so I haven't really branched out into other social media platforms. I do really recommend to every small business, start up or entrepreneur that they have to be on Instagram. I do really feel that having that platform is essential” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 17: Social Media Significant Platforms (NVivo codes)

Table 15: Social Media Significant Platforms

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Gender Experiences/ Orientations	Male and female entrepreneurs have different experiences to classify significant social media platforms.	Social media significant platforms selection	Significant platforms by male Significant platforms by female

The majority of the 20 participants articulated that Facebook and Instagram are the most significant social media platforms used for small, medium-sized food businesses by Muslim entrepreneurs. However, out of 8 male entrepreneurs emphasised that Facebook is the most significant social media platform because it is the biggest platform for every person using this platform.

On the other hand, out of 7 female entrepreneurs informed that Instagram is the most significant social media platform. Participant-19-F and 20-F added Instagram is the only platform that is more secure and suitable for small food business. This was further supported that Instagram is becoming the most famous platform because it caters for the right and favourable contents for business and customers, as indicated by participant-16-F.

Therefore, findings suggest that both Facebook and Instagram are importantly employed in social media platforms. However, male entrepreneurs suggest Facebook, whereas female

entrepreneurs suggest an Instagram social media platform for small, medium-sized food businesses.

4.3.3 Social Media Problems and Solutions

Social media as a marketing tool is the most effective way to increase business awareness and guide entrepreneurs to run businesses efficiently. However, as expected, social media might have some associated problems. These problems can be common or particular to the business and gender. If a social media strategy is executed efficiently, then a business grows and achieves its overall goals. Participants responses are given as follows:

“Yes sometime, some dodgy customers” (Participant -1-M).

“Yes, I know yes because it is very difficult tough job to specifically to reach your target audience first when you are new to Instagram and Facebook are marketing policies allows you actually It is augurated by them created by them specifically” (Participant -2-M).

“I think there are no big problems but however there are some technical issues. we use the social media such as on the Facebook page initially they have not given us a call button which can customer easily click on to the bottom and a call straight way to the restaurant to place any orders” (Participant- 3-M).

“Yes, sometimes we do for different kinds of problems such as the positive and the negative feedback, second thing is competitors strategy impact on our business, third Repetitive and confused post sometimes create a problem is not to attract more customers and down the sale” (Participant- 4-M).

“Marketing with Facebook ads is actually costly and less productive” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, I would say that this is very time-consuming it is also risky as well as social media as you use it” (Participant- 6-F).

“No, not really” (Participant- 7-F).

“Not really, I mean so far, our particular specific business is good. Okay, good. We need it. I haven't had a major issue or problem with it” (Participant- 8-M).

“I mean the problems are always there, tech problems, constraints, even like the algorithms, that are driven by those platforms themselves so there is always going to be that kind of problems” (Participant- 9-M).

“Not really, no. It's been straightforward. I think it's been very easy; it can be sometimes frustrating when there is nobody to speak to if there is a question, but I

think it's pretty idiot proof it's very easy to follow, it is very easy to use" **(Participant- 10-F).**

"Managing the expectation of your customers and followers is quite a challenge more so than a problem because they expect us to be there 24/7 and reply to their queries within seconds or minutes" **(Participant- 11-M).**

"The main issues that we have found is that there are a lot of people that like to leave fake reviews" **(Participant- 12-M).**

"No, I don't think so. I don't think so there is any problem while using social media" **(Participant- 13-M).**

"No" **(Participant- 14-M).**

"No, no" **(Participant- 15-M).**

"A brand wanted me to do a cooking tutorial to promote something. I did this but I clear at the start because it was hard for me to trust them because it was all done through email so I could do the work and not get paid for it.... I still haven't been paid. This would be the only problem I have faced so far" **(Participant- 16-F).**

"I wouldn't say that I have had any problems as such" **(Participant- 17-F).**

"Yes, I feel like there is competition as there are other bloggers doing the exact same thing as me. When new places open it is quite repetitive, so it is harder to be original with the same content" **(Participant- 18-F).**

"Sometimes it is a bit demotivating as it is a lot of work and gaining followers take a lot of time. There are many times when you feel down and feel like quitting. This is the only disappointment as it is a very slow process but when it starts hitting the mark it grows instantly. As for time consuming" **(Participant- 19-F).**

"With Instagram, sometimes you can have spam accounts or algorithm problems" **(Participant- 20-F).**

After exploring investigation of social media marketing problem faced in food SMEs, participants have informed, and responses are as follows:

- **Barriers of social media**

"Yes, sometime the barriers I would say tiny of barriers because some time you want to create offer and you need some resources. You need some extra time to think and time is barrier" **(Participant -1-M).**

"I mention Before the policies has been introduced by Facebook and Instagram it's another granted by them which priorities certain artists over poster over others on others so this is a barrier that That everybody is facing at the moment" **(Participant -2-M).**

“I don’t think so there is any barrier use of social media being a male however there are few barriers which can force them to use the organic social media usage for their businesses which has a low impact on the business sale as paid campaigns are costly and less productive” (Participant- 3-M).

“I don’t think so being a male I would be facing any barrier which prevent me the use of social media marketing accept few negative Comments” (Participant- 4-M).

“The barriers are general that I have mentioned in the previous question that you have asked. Apart from that in today’s day and age, gender does not create any barriers” ((Participant- 5-F).

“It is hard at the beginning because you see, if you’re not very familiar with the app things, then you don’t know how to go along” (Participant- 7-F).

“Not really no, I don’t think I have any barriers to date” (Participant- 10-F).

“No, not” (Participant- 11-M).

“Time, I think is a barrier. Spending time on it. That’s the only barrier” (Participant- 12-M).

“No, I don’t think so” (Participant- 13-M).

“Not really, no. Because social media nowadays is very user-friendly. Everybody can set up a profile, have a page, it’s very simple. I think Facebook is also very easy in that it wants you to be on them, so I think it’s a good platform” (Participant- 14-M).

“Not really” (Participant- 15-M).

“I have never really had any barriers, the only thing that come sometimes put you off are negative comments or messages” (Participant- 16-F).

“Not really, no” (Participant- 17-F).

“No, not really. I think being anonymous is a barrier as if you show who you are it is more successful but I want to remain anonymous but that has its challenges as I think it is a bit impersonal” (Participant- 18-F).

“I don’t think so far there is a difference between being a male or female on this platform” (Participant- 19-F).

“I think absolutely not... I think that is really empowering actually and that it is a great way for people, even if some women are stuck at home that it is a great way to get yourself out there” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 18: Social Media Problems (NVivo codes)

Table 16: Social Media Problems

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Gender Experiences/ Orientations	There are number of social media problems, such as algorithm, time consuming, fake reviews and technical lacs.	Social media problems	No problems Algorithm Time-consuming Fake reviews Technical lacs

Out of 5 participants found no problems while using social media marketing for the small and medium-sized food businesses; however, one female entrepreneur who was new to social media as a marketing tool found a technical learning process. On the other hand, four entrepreneurs informed that changes in an algorithm are causing them to achieve the marketing objectives. This was followed by another 4 participants that fake reviews and negative comments; these negative activities put the business down and leave a nasty footprint among customers and followers. Moreover, entrepreneurs also found that social media is time-consuming. Some entrepreneurs lack the technical skills to use social media as marketing tools, as indicated by 3 participants.

Consequently, the results from interviews indicate that majority of the male entrepreneurs have no problems using social media, which means they are technically skilled. The majority of male entrepreneurs observed fake reviews and negativity are the main problems of social media. The exact number of male and female entrepreneurs observed time-consuming and algorithm are social media problems. All the participants have informed that being a different gender, there is no barrier to the use of social media in today's date. Moreover, female entrepreneurs supported that social media is empowering female to employ social media; in fact, there are many females active in the online food businesses as indicated by participant-19-F and participant-20-F. However, both male and female entrepreneurs found technical problems and negativity that are still not a barrier to using social media marketing for business.

4.3.4 Social Media Experiences

Male and female entrepreneurs' employment of social media are dissimilar due to their gender.

Such experiences are reported as followed:

“And I do believe that they always do the good reviews to our restaurant and recommend to us some customers” (Participant -1-M).

“We had a very good very good experience it all depends on how to use it how do you target it” (Participant -2-M).

“I would say we should have to follow latest trends that give a business boost and generate a true lead. Secondly, I would say Audience and the customers attention play a very significant roles in many ways, so it is very good for the business” (Participant- 3-M).

“I think I would have shared all the possible information in regard to the use of social media marketing for the business thank you very much for taking me to this interview” (Participant- 4-M).

“Up till now the experience I would say has been good. There are positives in terms of getting the customer attention, but we also have to keep monitoring our competitors” (Participant- 5-F).

“So on any, Instagram or Facebook, you can get any random people and they are not genuine people they just want free cake or they want discount all the time so they will criticise your work so you need to be very firm on that” (Participant- 7-F).

“Most people post pictures of their food on social media, so it is important as it is directly related” (Participant- 8-M).

“Social media, yeah, I think you just have to put yourself, depending on your business and what you are trying to do” (Participant- 9-M).

“For me, what was key is to monitor it very carefully and grow it organically, and I didn’t want to go crazy with marketing immediately because I could only grow it at the same rate of the team members that I had” (Participant- 10-F).

“From our perspective, it has really been a learning experience for us, finding out what the customers want, what type of updates they want to see” (Participant- 11-M).

“I don’t think so I have any other experience apart from this one. I have seen it is right now the best way to market your product, and this is right now the best market to make your sales and that’s it” (Participant- 13-M).

“No that’s it really. I think social media is something we rely on, and it’s become the modern way of doing things. The modern way of getting your business out there” (Participant- 14-M).

“Again, a lot of social media is just to get the word out there quickly” (Participant- 16-F).

“Everyone starts off from somewhere and you have to believe in yourself and the success you can gain out of it as long as you put your true and honest mind to it, it will definitely come back at you” (Participant- 17-F).

“If you start it, do your research and know your market well. Always be consistent as it is the only thing that helps you grow” (Participant- 18-F).

“In my own experience, as I started with social media, I feel that it is the only way I can reach out to people as for now, so it is very integral to me” (Participant- 19-F).

Figure 19: Social Media Experiences (NVivo codes)

Table 17: Social Media Experiences

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Gender Experiences/ Orientations	There are two types of social media experiences, such as male experiences and female experiences.	Social media experiences	Male experiences Female experiences

From social media experience, it is found out that male entrepreneurs focusing on the latest trends followed on social media, which also emphasised designing the marketing strategy that helped the businesses reach the targeted customers, resulting in brand awareness. From this perspective, consumer behaviours and preferences enabled the entrepreneurs to design the marketing strategy indicated by male entrepreneurs (Participant-11-M).

On the other hand, the results indicate those female entrepreneurs are similar in designing the marketing strategy to target the customers. Additionally, entrepreneurs must market them regularly and consistently on social media, as added by participant-16-F.

The results indicate that gender has several impacts on the entrepreneurial use of social media in food SMEs in the UK. It is evident that both male and female entrepreneurs have revealed different social media goals and informed significant social media platforms and their business utilisation.

The above results from Section 4.3 confirm that characteristics of entrepreneurs directly influence and impact business actions. Therefore, findings suggested gender recognised male and female entrepreneurs are different in terms of running a business. Furthermore, evidence found that entrepreneurs used social media as a low-cost platform to recognise Halal markets and engage with consumers. It further highlighted the different entrepreneurial roles and identified new markets in the context of social media utilisation. Therefore, many businesses used social media networking sites; they request their contacts or customers to join them (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). Therefore, given below propositions answered as follows:

P5: Gender features can influence the actions of entrepreneurs to identify the marketing opportunity and customer engagement.

P6: Male and female entrepreneurs are benefiting from social media adoption and significant use for their business.

P7: Male and female entrepreneurs suggest that social media is very cost-effective and easy to maintain.

Thus, the propositions; P5, P6 and P7 accumulatively construct the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Gender features have a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

4.4 Performance Measurement

4.4.1 Brand Awareness

The usage of social media marketing by Muslim male and female entrepreneurs for their businesses found that both gender's main aim of using social media is to increase brand awareness. Following responses are informed by these entrepreneurs:

“The overall aim of using social media engaging with customers and bringing them to restaurant and make some money” (Participant -1-M).

“Coming back to your second question again it's engaging the best most productive way for a local small business to engage with the customers” (Participant -2-M).

“Main aim of using social media is business sale, customer engagement, brand awareness and ahead of the competition” (Participant- 3-M).

“The main of using social media is keeping our customer up-to-date, business sustainability, new business trend, staying with the world, business expansion and brand awareness” (Participant- 4-M).

“To have a successful local business. That would attract as much people as possible by serving them a variety of food” Participant- 5-F).

“I would say to connect with our guest easier. Connecting with existing customers and potential customers as I say that would be one of our main aim to be honest. We want everyone to know about us” (Participant- 6-F).

“I think it is a good way of advertisement. I share on Instagram on Facebook, I think even putting anything on WhatsApp status people see it, because all your contacts can see, and a large number of people respond to that” (Participant- 7-F).

“Well just to grow the business. It's as simple as that” (Participant- 10-F).

“Again, it is the digital day and age, everyone is using it. People will ask questions on Instagram or Facebook and our aim will be to get out to the customers and getting our information across to them as fast and accurately as we can” (Participant- 11-M).

“The main aim would be to drive more sales, and more awareness” (Participant- 12-M).

“Main aim of social media is brand awareness. The more the brand is aware, it will increase my profits” (Participant- 14-M).

“Main aim is to raise awareness as many as possible obviously for your business” (Participant- 15-M).

“My aim is to get my cooking videos out there. That is something I enjoy doing” **(Participant- 16-F).**

“My main aim is to hopefully try and grow as big as I can to try and achieve my goal of helping people find halal food wherever they go in the northwest region of the UK” **(Participant- 17-F).**

“Gaining more and more followers. Also genuinely informing people about good food and helping local business out as well that struggle to get the word out about their food as the food industry is very hard because it is a very competitive business and new places need exposure so as a blogger I can help them with that” **(Participant- 18-F).**

“So, the main aim for my business is to create awareness for healthy eating and to reach as many people as possible. Social media is the best form of marketing in my opinion because it reaches so many people” **(Participant- 20-F).**

Figure 20: Social Media Aim (NVivo codes)

Table 18: Social Media Aim

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Performance measurement	Social media's main aim is brand awareness that enabled businesses to engage with customers.	Social media aim	Brand awareness

The majority of the 14 participants informed that social media marketing majorly used to increase brand awareness. Female participants running online food blogs play an important role in creating awareness by informing them, as indicated by participants-17-F, 18-F and 19-F. This was further supported by a female entrepreneur (participant-16-F) that the contents she produced were interesting; therefore, sending food videos out in the market helped increase brand awareness. Besides, participant-4-M informed that sharing the latest and newest information on food provided the update to customers on products that increased brand awareness. On the other hand, participant-2-M and participant-3-M found that their social

media engagement with customers informed the customers to call in the restaurants, which have increased the business sale and business expansion as indicated by participant-4-M.

Therefore, the study results indicate that social media marketing uses played an important role in increasing brand awareness. Both males and females are equally using social media, informing the customers. Hence, proposition eight is answered as follows:

P8: Muslim entrepreneurs use social media marketing to increase the brand awareness of their businesses.

Thus, the propositions P8 constructs the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Brand awareness has a significant positive impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

4.4.2 Social Media Interaction

Social media interaction involves entrepreneurs in sharing information with customers. Social media interactions are associated with the use of social media by the entrepreneur. These interactions are reactive and proactive, i.e., social media interactions enabled the entrepreneurs' reactions to the customers when they have messaged them and sharing and posting information reaching out to the customers via social media. Responses of the participants are given as follows:

“On Instagram Facebook ask them questions answering the questions in gauging engaging with them” (Participant -2M).

“We always interact with customers via Facebook Instagram Snapchat by introducing new promotions do you offer us new products and so on. We also interact with other customers on national holidays and summer holidays and we also keep our customers up to date with the latest trends like a football matches update etc. We also interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback and we also listen to complaints if anything creates inconvenience to the customers” (Participant- 3-M).

“We always welcome the feedback from our customers to listen them, on Instagram we always put and share the food pictures/videos to see how the followers are

looking at our food posts” (Participant- 4-M).

“There are number of ways. It depends on where the customers are and as to which portal, we are using. Each portal has different interactions” (Participant- 5-F).

“Yes, if someone message us directly then we will directly respond them back. Any type of review left we respond back” (Participant- 6-F).

“just by direct messaging or if they got my number, they will just WhatsApp me or send me pictures of the product that they want” (Participant- 7-F).

“Direct messaging, you know, comments, likes, when people like our post, if they are not already following us, we ping them and then say “Hey, follow us” right, and if they leave a comment, so it’s just an interaction” (Participant- 9-M).

“My response with them is very personal, it’s very friendly whenever somebody comments, they will always get some reaction from me, they will get a comment form me, if it’s a user on Facebook, they get a reply back immediately” (Participant- 10-F).

“Normally, we just post on social media. We don’t actively engage in any of the conversation on public social media forums” (Participant- 11-M).

“We just, honest, we just have to, there is no other option to interact with them, you just have to upload your pictures, and that’s the only way you interact with them” (Participant- 13-M).

“Posting them, okay” (Participant- 14-M).

“Uh there is one girl that works it for us” (Participant- 15-M).

“Through personal messages on Instagram. That is the only way to be honest” (Participant- 16-F).

“Through posting actual content, whether it is a brunch post or a fine dining post and try to get people to comment on there” (Participant- 17-F).

“I upload stories and reply to their comments” (Participant- 18-F).

“They do message me through DMs on Instagram. If they have any query or anything, they write to me and I ask permission to post about it then send a link to them or just reply with a message” (Participant- 19-F).

“I think being interactive is really important. For example, if I get a comment, I will always ask questions or interact. If somebody likes my page I will go and check out their page so we can have that line of communication going” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 21: Social Media Interaction (NVivo codes)

Table 19: Social Media Interaction

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Performance measurement	There are several ways in which Muslim entrepreneurs interact with customers on social media, i.e., direct messaging, sharing daily posts, uploading food pictures and introducing promotions.	Social media Interaction	Direct messaging Sharing posts Uploading food pictures Introducing promotions

Of those, the majority of 7 participants disclosed that messaging directly to customers is the most significant way of interacting on social media. Moreover, social media interaction is found interesting when entrepreneurs reply to the comments and likes on shared posts. Participant-11-M further supported this that entrepreneurs' interaction via 1-1 messaging about the product's price and availability gives more privacy. Observation made that different platforms suggest different approaches interact, such as Facebook, helped interact on feedback comments and Instagram suggested dealings as indicated by participant-4-M. This was followed by 4 participants that indicated that sharing regular posts on social media enabled the

customers to interact, further added by participant-17-F and 18-F informed that uploading stories and post on the wall feeds allow customers to interact via likes and comments. On the other hand, uploading food pictures regularly on social media is also an important social media interaction activity, as indicated by participant-11-M.

Consequently, findings indicate that both male and female entrepreneurs prefer interacting on social media via direct messaging and uploading food pictures. In contrast, female entrepreneurs observed sharing social media posts regularly considered the most significant social media interactions. Hence, propositions P9 is answered as follows:

P9: Muslim entrepreneurs use social media as a communication tool to interact with their customers.

Thus, the proposition P9 constructs the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Customer Interaction has a significant positive impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

4.4.3 Customer Feedback

Social media marketing depends on customer's feedback and rating about the products and services used. This feedback enables entrepreneurs to discover high-quality and trending content. Also, these feedbacks navigate suggestions to the entrepreneurs for designing and formulating social media marketing strategies. Positive and negative feedbacks have importance for entrepreneurs to run social media marketing. Participants responses are as followed:

“Yes, we follow, if you have any time please look on our FB review, even on very last review for the bad experience we said we you had any bad experience please let us know we will look into it” (Participant -1-M).

“We do keep the file of all the feedback positive and negative to see how we can improve to see other weaknesses our strong point” (Participant -2-M).

“First of all, we appreciate all the feedbacks from every single social media site we take it very seriously and we would try to help out to all our customers promptly.

We take their feedback on serious note and work truly to give the reply and the solution to anybody or any customer had any complaints regarding anything” **(Participant- 3-M).**

“We regularly monitored the customers feedback by Answering their enquiries. We welcome the positive feedback’s and we appreciate it we also send them a good thought for being so nice to us that we also welcome the negative feedback’s and we also try to help the customers to make them happy and resolve any issues which has caused any inconvenience” **(Participant- 4-M).**

“As I have said earlier, we have a team that brings me the suggestions and we answer to them individually. Also, we appreciate feedback that is monitored on regular basis” **(Participant- 5-F).**

“Yes, we monitor on KPI sheet weekly. Like I said Monday when I go through those comment once I found a comment and it is negative. We record it on separate sheet. Then I send it the senior management to make sure it goes to original branch. Make sure the store manager finds out what happened that day and wouldn’t happen it again” **(Participant- 6-F).**

“I normally receive messages, lots of messages saying that oh um, because they end up having my number because they are my regular customers and uh if they...yeah” **(Participant- 7-F).**

“We use an official feedback survey. We use the SurveyMonkey platform where we send a survey to our mailing list and the survey is also posted onto our social media platforms” **(Participant- 8-M).**

“Um, basically, it’s just under the reviews. I just look at the reviews you get a good idea of what most customers are saying about us. I think we had about 350 reviews and um, they are all you know, we’ve got 4.9 stars out of 5 stars for our review and that is tremendous” **(Participant- 10-F).**

“There are quite a lot of feedback we receive whenever we post things, people will engage with it, comment on it. Again, this is usually done by the outsourced company” **(Participant- 11-M).**

“We just respond to them accordingly” **(Participant- 12-M).**

“We’re already in contact with them, through the messages obviously. Whatever feedback they give us regarding our product, regarding our service, we just try to improve our work and that’s it I think” **(Participant- 13-M).**

“I do Comments, emails, Instagram messaging” **(Participant- 14-M).**

“I don’t. well like I said the only thing I check is uh, if there is positive feedback you know, obviously I read them but uh, I’m more focused on if there is a negative feedback, which so far we didn’t really have a negative feedback” **(Participant- 15-M).**

“After I post on my Instagram, a day later I will look through each and every comment and try to narrow down what people are saying, if the feedback is good. If the post hasn’t done well, then I need to look at that post and look at the reason behind this” (Participant- 16-F).

“Feedback can come in different ways. It can be verbal, it can be written as comments to a picture, a reply to a story or even through a personal message. I keep on top of all my messaging that happens on the platform and try to reply to everyone and even when I don’t reply I will always acknowledge it” (Participant- 17-F).

“I don’t, I don’t think I can monitor it as the feedback is not directed at my page, I don’t really take it into consideration” (Participant- 18-F).

“There are negatives and positive comments on posts and I get a lot of responses and recently I received a message from a follower that was following me for a very long time who was visiting London from the Middle East and he wanted me to write down five or ten different halal food restaurants because he was visiting for the first time. I wrote a very extensive email writing back to him and he was very grateful, and he told me that once he does make the trip that he would tag my account” (Participant- 19-F).

“I do want to look more into an option on Instagram I don’t know whether it is through Instagram or another application where you can get your followers to send feedback or even on Instagram I have put polls on Instagram where I ask what kind of content my followers want to see and I put a poll or a Q&A type thing where they can put their answers in. This gives me feedback” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 22: Social Media Feedback (NVivo Codes)

Table 20: Social Media Feedback

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Performance measurement	Positive and negative feedbacks are two types of SM feedback; entrepreneurs appreciate the feedback received, considered it key to respond via direct messaging.	Social media feedback	Positive feedback Negative feedback Appreciating feedback Direct messaging

Of the interviews, most 6 participants informed that they received positive and negative feedback about their food products and services. Participant-2-M added positive and negative feedbacks files that were organised separately to monitor the weaknesses and strengths. Participant-8-M and participant-9-M both indicated using different tools, such as SurveyMonkey and Hootsuite, to monitor the feedback. This was followed by 3 participants who observed that they appreciate the feedback, whether positive or negative. Participant-4-M further extended this that we replied the positive feedback to appreciate the customers. On the other hand, if found negative feedback or any inconvenience, the direct response made to resolve the issue as indicated by participant-2-M. Moreover, another 3 participants informed that direct replies and messages are more suitable for resolving the feedback issues.

Therefore, the results indicating that both males and females observed positive and negative feedback from social media use. Moreover, male entrepreneurs found themselves more involved directly in contact via direct messaging, appreciating feedback and resolving the issue. Whereas female entrepreneurs look at post insights, further observing the post likes, comments and shares. Hence, the proposition 'P10' is answered as follows:

P10: Muslim entrepreneurs use social media marketing to receive positive and negative customer feedback on food products.

Thus, the proposition P10 constructs the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Customer Feedback has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial experiences.

4.4.4 Social Media Uses for Communications

Content marketing is generated during the interview and generates related content posted onto social media platforms to engage with customers and ascertain the markets. The participants informed that creating and sharing these contents regularly across the social media profiles enabled the businesses to increase their customer's attention. Moreover, shared relevant contents on social media profiles such as food pictures enabled the entrepreneurs and customers to comment on each other content that consists of mutual interaction and provide good advice to design the strategy. When further asked how do you communicate with your customers on social media platforms, then participants replied, and responses are as follows:

“Social media marketing for the business use is more like a how do you engage with the customers how do you keep your customers update about your daily products and daily updates” (Participant- 2-M).

“We regularly update every single platform, so we maintain all the Channels regularly” (Participant- 3-M).

“Social media marketing we use in a number of ways for the Facebook page but on Instagram page we share all this information about all new products and the current menu to the customers to let them know what we are up to” (Participant- 4-M).

“We have a marketing team and a page admin that are instructed on daily basis to promote the offers, new products and so on” (Participant- 5-F).

“We actually use them on manually” (Participant- 6-F).

“From the social media perspective, we add updates to our pages that are mainly customer driven” (Participant- 11-M).

“My brother is the main marketing director” (Participant- 12-M).

“I ordered equipment for YouTube in quarantine and I am still waiting for it to come in the post. In WordPress I write my blogs there and I get feedback from my followers if they do go on my website and they can DM me and tell me new ideas and stuff like this” (Participant- 16-F).

“In day-to-day use, I use stories and posts” (Participant- 17-F).

“Uploading stories so people can see where I am currently and interacting with other bloggers so their followers can come across you” (Participant- 18-F).

“There are a couple of tools such as creating stories, posting pictures of food or reviews every week or day whatever suits you best. Then there are tools like highlights that you can keep on your profile for people to approach later” (Participant- 19-F).

“It takes a lot. I have my hash tags, times in the day that I post, I have my content that I am going to post ready, I have my DM’s that I am always checking” (Participant- 20-F).

When further explored how do you monitor these social media communications, responses are as followed:

“Every day and every hour” (Participant -1-M).

“Every single morning every single evening every single day we constantly Monitoring I have an Instagram on the Facebook page constantly looking at engagement of the hashtags the tags checking the feedbacks the good comments and the bad comments good messages and bad messages anything like I said before it’s all good it means engage with the place” (Participant -2-M).

“We maintain and manage all over social media sites for other business regularly daily every day in the morning and evening” (Participant- 3-M).

“Every day regularly we maintain our social media site to communicate with our followers [...] but this is the kind of entertainment when you look after your followers” (Participant- 4-M).

“Yes, all the sites are updated daily. It basically depends on which social media site gets major attention. As of now, we are focusing mainly of Facebook by updating our promotions” (Participant- 5-F).

“Okay every Monday I check thoroughly through all of the social media, so I go on every single of our pages and look from week ahead. So, we go week per week check and make sure every single thing has responded back too” (Participant- 6-F).

“I mean, Facebook, last 2 weeks I’ve been really busy, but I’ve not put anything on Facebook but um I put it on Instagram. So, I regularly update Instagram” (Participant- 7-F).

“On Facebook we try to post every couple of weeks. On Instagram we try to post every few days. We are more active on Instagram than Facebook” (Participant- 8-M).

“Oh, like I don't know, every hour of every day. As always, it's 24/7” (Participant-9-M).

“For communications? Um every day? It's monitored every single day. So, as I said because I have a mobile device, as soon as I get a message, it gets responded to immediately because I get a notification on my phone” (Participant- 10-F).

“A couple times a week, sometimes multiplies times a day. If you would average it out, you would see it being done at least once a day. Facebook and Instagram much more than Twitter” (Participant- 11-M).

“Again, my brother will deal with that. He does it via a company” (Participant- 12-M).

“Oh every 3-4 hours. If you are on social media and you want to be working on social media, then you can't uh, make a special time, once a week or twice a week. You have to be there every single day because then how you are going to make your money”? (Participant- 13-M).

“I pay somebody just £100 a month just to monitor them” (Participant- 14-M).

“After every 2-3 days. I said social, for the social context, you know, it's really good. So yeah, I think if you want, the quickest way to spread your message I think its social media” (Participant- 15-M).

“Every single day” (Participant- 16-F).

“On a daily basis really, I am really active on my social media” (Participant- 17-F).

“It is always there but I can go months without using it so not every often” (Participant- 18-F).

“Very regularly, every night I make an effort to take out an hour to deal with the messages and queries that I receive. This I have to do quite often otherwise it piles up pretty badly” (Participant- 19-F).

“.....” (Participant- 20-F).

Figure 23: Social Media Uses for Communication (NVivo codes)

Table 21: Social Media Uses for Communication

Theme	Definition	Sub-theme	Codes
Entrepreneurial Opportunity	Social media equipped the entrepreneurs to generate relevant content and communicate regularly.	Social media uses for communications.	Content marketing Regularly update Sharing posts Follow Hashtag

Six participants acknowledged that social media uses enabled the entrepreneurs to generate the relevant contents to interact with their followers creating food posts. These interesting communication contents helped the entrepreneurs interact and engage in different ways, such as creating stories, posting food pictures, and reviewing food quality and business services, consequently attracting them to share the same content and spread the experiences. Three entrepreneurs followed this informed effective and productive communication required daily and regular social media updates.

Participant-20-F further supported this that regular account monitoring provides insights to look at audiences that had visited the business page enabled to cater new strategy. She also informed that hashtag was an important strategy that enabled the entrepreneurs to create the unique contents. On the other hand, out of 2 entrepreneurs, one male and one female entrepreneur, they outsource to utilise social media marketing strategies. Entrepreneurs are busy looking at business management and outsource can work along with overall business goal and strategy.

Participants-3-M and 4-M both informed that they had created business social media profiles as an initial point to communicate with customers for their products and services. In the start, they manage to advertise through personal profiles and social media. They regularly update their customers for their business activities, including updates about national holidays as indicated by participant-2-M. One of the main communication activities entrepreneurs employed is to increase brand awareness and customer engagement in social media marketing, utilising social media analytics and taking expert advice from freelance consultants (Participant-12-M). Participant 2 mentioned that social media marketing for communication is how to engage with customers and update them about products. Another participant informed that he had expert advice on social media usage for his business; freelancers informed that customer's shopping behaviours had been changed since the social media evolved; to communicate with customers, entrepreneurs only need to present the business online to see whether customers are satisfied. The majority of participants informed that they regularly update all the social media channels for communications. Adding to this, some participants said that they update these social media platforms daily, even twice a day. Female participants were found more active in updating social media platforms.

Therefore, the research results indicated that both male and female entrepreneurs observed a significant role of social media communication in their food businesses. Moreover, the majority of entrepreneurs found regularly posting food pictures is an interactive social media communication. Hence, propositions P11 is answered as follows:

P11: Muslim entrepreneurs use social media as a communication tool to engage with customers.

Thus, the proposition P4 from section 4.2.3 and P11 suggest the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis: Social media Communication has a significant positive impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

4.5 Summary

This chapter presented the findings that emerged from the data analysis and individually discussed the four connected main themes generated inductively from the data regarding in-depth interviews. The findings of this chapter further informed the quantitative study. Therefore, quantitative results from the study are discussed in the following chapter. Summary of key findings from in-depth interviews is presented on the next page.

Summary of Key Findings from In-Depth Interview Key Information.

In this section, summary of the key findings presented emerged from the interviews that were undertaken with Muslim male and female entrepreneurs runs food businesses in the UK. The main aim of presenting this section is to provide the list of key findings emerged from the interview findings. The main aim of this study is to examine the gender impacts on Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards the use of social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. The key findings that were emerged from qualitative study can be summarised according to the research objectives as follows:

Research Objective 1: To explore the role of social media platforms usage by Muslim entrepreneurs in food businesses.

- The study identified that Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and Snapchat are the primary social media platforms used in small and medium-sized food businesses by Muslim entrepreneurs.
- Entrepreneurs are inspired to create their own social media pages and business profiles for food SMEs.
- Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat are platforms where entrepreneurs easily share food pictures and interact with customers to increase brand awareness of products and services.
- The results indicated that entrepreneurs suggested that the adoption of social media is beneficial and the most significant marketing opportunity for small and medium-sized food businesses in the UK.
- Interviews findings indicated that social media platforms had increased followers and brand awareness to small and medium-sized food businesses.

Research Objective 2: To investigate social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK.

- Social media as a marketing tool is the most significant constructive pathway of communicating with customers online, as social media marketing tools promote accessible communication with customers online.
- Female entrepreneurs believed that paid marketing such as sponsor ads (strategies) enables the businesses to attract customers and encourage entrepreneurs to pay serious attention to sponsored ads that mainly improve business performance and customers satisfaction.
- This study identified content marketing, regular updating, hashtags, introducing promotion and direct messaging on various platforms as the core elements of social media communication.

Research Objective 3: To find out the gender experience of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs using social media marketing for their food businesses.

- The study confirmed that female entrepreneurs are now competing with male entrepreneurs in social media marketing strategy.
- Female entrepreneurs claimed that social media insights and analytics tools helped to analyse business performance and customer behaviours.
- Male entrepreneurs claimed that social media analytics helped to create marketing strategies that promote business improvement.
- Male entrepreneurs' key goals in using social media are to gain more customer, revenue and promote brands awareness.

- Surprisingly, female entrepreneurs claimed that organisations must gain more customers, promote brand awareness on social media, create plans, and focus on a specific social media platform for successful business marketing.
- Entrepreneurs have a lack of technical skills, which is a barrier to social media marketing. Hence, male and female entrepreneurs require technical skills to use social media marketing tools to communicate, interact, engage and create brand awareness.
- The majority of the female participant agreed that involving in social media business stimulates brand awareness that enlightens customers about the company's products value.
- Female entrepreneurs encouraged their competitors and believed SMM in Halal food could proliferate by supporting each other.
- It was understood that responding to customer feedback through direct messaging is the best way to reduce customers' negative word of mouth and improve their satisfaction.

Chapter five, which is the next chapter, will provide the survey (online questionnaire) findings of the research.

Chapter 5 – Quantitative Findings

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the survey from an online questionnaire presents the results undertaken with Muslim entrepreneurs run small and medium-sized (SMEs) food businesses in the UK. In order to make it easier to digest the findings from the fieldwork carried out, the findings were presented in two different chapters. In the previous chapter of the study – the first of the finding's chapters - the findings from the primary data collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews with key informants/stakeholders and interviewees with Muslim entrepreneurs run small and medium-sized food businesses in the UK. The second of the finding's chapters - the findings from the data collected through the survey analysis, formed by the aim of this study based on interviews conducted with Muslim entrepreneurs run small and medium-sized food businesses in the UK.

A comprehensive approach for methods, processes and protocols were used to collect the data, presented in the methodology chapter.

5.2 Findings from Survey Questionnaire

In this chapter, the results from the online questionnaire presented. Firstly, the demographics characteristics of the research are presented. However, this study presented Descriptive Statistics and Inferential analysis; to conduct this analysis, SPSS version 26.0 was used.

As discussed above, the research process of data collection from administering the questionnaire has already been noted in chapter 3. In summary, the survey questionnaire was sent online to the Muslim entrepreneurs' social media profiles run small and medium-sized food businesses in the UK. A total of 120 respondents completed the questionnaire. In the questionnaire, all questions were closed-ended, and participants were allowed to select their choices from the Five-point Likert scale (see Appendix 4).

5.2.1 Demographic Information of the Participants

Participants' demographic information is vital to determine whether participants are the proper representative of the targeted population in generalising purpose (Salkind, 2010). The basic information of the demographics covers participant's gender, ethnicity, age group, job role, location, business type and business foundation. In addition, the information on demographics can be beneficial in several ways. It enables the reader to relate the results with the targeted population and compare the target population's variances. It helps the researcher generalise the results (Hammer, 2011).

Table 22: Showing the Distribution on the Participant's Gender

<i>Gender</i>				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	83	69.2	69.2	69.2
Female	36	30.0	30.0	99.2
Prefer not to say	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 24: Gender

The above Table 22 shows the distribution of the gender of the participants from where the majority of the respondents, 83(69.2%) of the total participants, were male while 36(30.0%) were female.

Table 23: Showing the Representation of the Participant’s Ethnic Group

<i>Ethnicity</i>	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
British Muslim	14	11.7	11.7	11.7
British Pakistani	65	54.2	54.2	65.8
British Indian	8	6.7	6.7	72.5
British Bangladeshi	8	6.7	6.7	79.2
Other Muslim	25	20.8	20.8	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 25: Ethnicity

The above Table 23 shows the distribution of the ethnicity of the participant from where it can be seen that the majority of the respondents that participated in the study, 65(54.2%) of the total participants, claimed to be British Pakistani. Twenty-five participants followed this were another ethnic Muslim. Out of 14 participants were British Muslim, eight were British Indian Muslim and British Bangladeshi Muslim.

Table 24: Showing the Distribution on the Participant’s Age Group

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-24	16	13.3	13.3	13.3
25-34	54	45.0	45.0	58.3
35-44	45	37.5	37.5	95.8
45-54	4	3.3	3.3	99.2
55+	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 26: Age Group

The above Table 24 shows the distribution of the age group of the participants where the majority of the respondents, which account for 54(45.0%), claimed they fall within the age range of 25-34years; 45(37.5%) claimed they fall within the age range of 35-44years. Therefore, we can conclude that most of the respondents who participated in this study are within the age range of 25-44years old.

Table 25: Showing the Distribution on Participant’s Job Role

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Director	68	56.7	56.7	56.7
Senior Manager	52	43.3	43.3	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 27: Participant’s Job Role

The above Table 25 shows the descriptive statistics for the participant’s job role. The majority of the respondents who participated in the study, which account for 68(56.7%), claimed that they are Directors, while 52(43.3%) claimed they are senior managers.

Table 26: Showing the Distribution on Participant's Location

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
London	9	7.5	7.5	7.5
Birmingham	56	46.7	46.7	54.2
Manchester	44	36.7	36.7	90.8
Bradford	1	.8	.8	91.7
Glasgow	2	1.7	1.7	93.3
Overall UK	8	6.7	6.7	100.0
	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 28: Participant's Location

The above Table 26 shows that the largest percentage of the participant, which accounts for 56(46.7%), claimed their location in Birmingham, followed by 44(36.7%) of the total participant claiming their location in Manchester. The location with the minor participant includes Bradford which account for 1(0.8%) of the total participant and Glasgow which account for 2(1.7%).

Table 27: Showing the Distribution on Participant's type of Food Business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Fast food	16	13.3	13.3	13.3
Restaurant	51	42.5	42.5	55.8
Takeaway	12	10.0	10.0	65.8
Desserts	13	10.8	10.8	76.7
Online Food Blogger	26	21.7	21.7	98.3
Wholesaler	2	1.7	1.7	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 29: Type of Business

The above Table 27 shows the distribution of the type of food business the participants are involved. Most of the participants, about 51(42.5%) of the total participants, claimed the type they are involved in the restaurant business, and 26(21.7%) of the participants claimed they are into the food business of online food blogger. There were 16(13.3%) participants found in the Fast food business. Moreover, 13(11%) participants belonged to desserts shops, 12(10%) participants have takeaway places, and 2(2%) participants were wholesalers.

Table 28: Showing the Distribution on how long the Participants have been Running the Business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1-3 Years	49	40.8	40.8	40.8
4-6 Years	46	38.3	38.3	79.2
7-10 Years	19	15.8	15.8	95.0
11+ Years	6	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Figure 30: Business Foundation

The above Table 28 shows the descriptive statistics on how long the respondents have been running their business from where 49(40.8%) of the total participant said between 1-3years; 46(38.3%) claimed between 4-6years while 19(15.8%) claimed it is between 7-10years and 6(5.0%) claimed they have been running the business for more than 11 years.

5.3 Descriptive Statistics

In this section, descriptive statistics of the study presented, including empirical items, minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, for one each measurement item. It focuses on the first order constructs as follows. The descriptive analysis of predictable variables was performed and the overall view of the different indicator of entrepreneurial experiences among British Muslim entrepreneurs.

Firstly, the antecedents of the element of the social media marketing that comprise of social media uses. Secondly, gender orientations for gender experiences towards the opportunity and social media uses provided. Finally, the performance measurements have four primary constructs, such as social media communications (SMC), social media interaction (SMI), brand awareness (BA), and customer feedback (CFB). As stated above, central tendency such as mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) of the variables is presented. The mean is known as average value of the variable and standard deviations helps to measure the dispersion of the variable. It can be observed that the sample of participants for this questionnaire is 120 respondents. Furthermore, the values of the average denoting the Likert scale ranges are as follows:

- Highly Significant = 4.21 – 5.0
- Significant = 3.41 – 4.20
- Neutral = 2.61- 3.40
- Not Significant = 1.81-2.60
- Not Highly Significant = 1- 1.80

The five-point Likert scale is considered an interval scale, therefore used to measure the predictable variables. So, the mean is considered significant or not significant. The value of the mean from 4.21 to 5.0 considers the mean is highly significant. The value of the mean from 3.41 to 4.20 consider the mean is significant. The mean value from 2.61 to 3.40 consider the

mean is neutral; the value of the mean from 1.81 to 2.60 means not significant, and the value of mean from 1 to 1.80 means not highly significant. The Interval scale is shown in Table (29).

Table 29: Analysis of Five-Point Likert Scale

	Scale	Interval length	Lower Limit	Upper limit	Interval
Strongly agree	5	0.80	4.21	5.0	(4.21: 5.0)
Agree	4	0.80	3.41	4.20	(3.41: 4.20)
Neutral	3	0.80	2.61	3.40	(2.61: 3.40)
Disagree	2	0.80	1.81	2.60	(1.81: 2.60)
Strongly disagree	1	0.80	1.0	1.80	(1.0: 1.80)

Note. 5 strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neutral, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly disagree. Results; highly significant (4.21:5.0); significant (3.41:4.20); neutral (2.61:3.40), not significant (1.81:2.60); not highly significant (1:1.80).

5.4 Element of Social Media Marketing

5.4.1 Social Media Uses

This section will be analysing and explaining the questions under the theme of elements of social media marketing. These questions are as followed:

1. I use SM to engage with customers
2. I use SM to keep customers updated about my products
3. I use SM for networking
4. I use SM to build relationship with customers
5. I mainly use Facebook for my food business
6. I mainly use Instagram for my food business
7. I mainly use Twitter for my food business
8. I mainly use Snap-chat for my food business
9. I use all SM channels i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter & Snapchat

10. I go live with my followers to interact with them
11. Social media is very cost effective
12. I use SM Social media paid ads that are very helpful
13. I keep my customers up to date with the latest trends

Social media uses under the theme of the element of social media marketing (SMM) consisted of thirteen scaled questions that focused on how Muslim entrepreneurs employed social media uses on their small and medium-sized food businesses. One each question of social media uses was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1) Strongly disagree to 5) strongly agree (see Table 29). The average scale mean value of the question ranged from 2.11 to 4.33. The standard deviations ranged from 0.677 to 1.335. The highest scale value questions were “*I use SM to engage with customers*” (Mean = 4.33), “*I use SM for networking*” (Mean = 4.33), “*I use SM to keep customers updated about my products*” (Mean = 4.22), and “*I use SM to build relationship with customers*” (Mean = 4.20).

The second highest scale value questions were “*Social media is very cost effective*” (Mean = 4.01), “*I mainly use Instagram for my food business*” (Mean = 4.00), “*I keep my customers up to date with the latest trends*” (Mean = 3.97), and “*I use SM Social media paid ads that are very helpful*” (Mean = 3.87). There was a considerable amount of agreement shown among these questions “*I use all SM channels i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter & Snapchat*” (Mean = 3.33) and “*I mainly use Facebook for my food business*” (Mean = 3.28). The result indicates that the entrepreneurs tend to be neutral to slightly in agreement with the statement. On the other hand, the lowest rated items with the scale mean value of three questions such as “*I mainly use Snap-chat for my food business*” (Mean = 2.20), “*I mainly use Twitter for my food business*” (Mean = 2.11) and “*I go live with my followers to interact with them*” (Mean = 2.11). Social media uses scale descriptive statistics is presented in Table 30.

Table 30: Descriptive Statistics of Social Media Uses

Social Media Uses	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I use SM to engage with customers</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.3333	.67778
<i>I use SM to keep customers updated about my products</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.2250	.77202
<i>I use SM for networking</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.3333	.63950
<i>I use SM to build relationship with customers</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.66862
<i>I mainly use Facebook for my food business</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.2833	1.33589
<i>I mainly use Instagram for my food business</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.0000	1.05321
<i>I mainly use Twitter for my food business</i>	120	1.00	5.00	2.1167	1.16087
<i>I mainly use Snap-chat for my food business</i>	120	1.00	5.00	2.2083	1.33408
<i>I use all SM channels i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter & Snapchat</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.3000	1.12720
<i>I go live with my followers to interact with them</i>	120	1.00	5.00	2.1583	1.31568
<i>Social media is very cost effective</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0167	.96130
<i>I use SM Social media paid ads that are very helpful</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.8750	.89407
<i>I keep my customers up to date with the latest trends</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.9750	.84478

Figure 31: Social Media Uses

The above graph in Figure 31 shows the distribution of the participant's responses on the social media marketing used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK. The graph also displays the thirteen questions under this theme: element of social media marketing. It can be observed that for the questions 1 to 5 and 10 to 13, the majority of the responses by the participants are agreed, the second highest response for this set of questions is strongly agree to every variables of measurement except for few where majority of the participants do not agree that they mainly use Twitter for their food business. Also, approximately 64.1% of the total participants do not agree that they mainly use Snap-chat for the food business, while 71.6% do not agree that they go live with their followers to interact with them. The result from the table revealed that 62% of the total participants claimed they mainly use Facebook for their food business; 64.2% also claimed they mainly use Instagram for their food business while 43.3% of these total participants claimed they use the entire social media channel which includes Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Snapchat for their food business.

5.5 Gender Orientations

5.5.1 Gender Experiences

This section analyses the questions of gender experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs explored under the theme of gender orientations. These questions are as followed:

1. Social media is an opportunity in today's world for Muslim entrepreneurs.
2. Social media adoption has benefited my business a lot.
3. Social media helped me to know more about customer preferences
4. I have already set up my next social media goals.
5. I regularly maintain the social media sites.
6. I regularly update the social media sites.
7. I don't have any barriers using social media for my business.

Entrepreneurial experiences under the theme of gender orientation consisted of seven scaled questions focused on what experiences of Muslim male and female entrepreneurs towards social media use on their small and medium-sized food businesses. One each question of social media uses was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1) Strongly disagree to 5) strongly agree (see table 29). The average mean value of the question ranged from 3.35 to 4.60. The standard deviations ranged from 0.58 to 1.08.

The highest scale value questions were “Social media is an opportunity in today’s world for Muslim entrepreneurs” (Mean = 4.60), “*Social media adoption has benefited my business a lot*” (Mean = 4.36), and “*Social media helped me to know more about customer preferences*” (Mean = 4.30). On the other hand, the second highest scale value questions were “*I regularly update the social media sites*” (Mean = 4.00) “*I regularly maintain the social media sites*” (Mean = 3.89) and “*I don’t have any barriers using social media for my business*” (Mean = 3.89). There was a considerable amount of agreement shown on the question, “*I have already set up my next social media goals.*” (Mean = 3.35). The result indicates that the entrepreneurs tend to be neutral to slightly in agreement with the statement. Overall results indicate that entrepreneurs perceived social media as a great opportunity and have benefited in many ways. Moreover, they do not have any barrier while using it for marketing. Entrepreneurial experiences descriptive statistics are presented in Table 31.

Table 31: Descriptive Statistics of Gender Experiences

Gender Experiences	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Social media is an opportunity in today's world for Muslim entrepreneurs.</i>	120	3.00	5.00	4.608	.58404
<i>Social media adoption has benefited my business a lot.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.366	.64734
<i>Social media helped me to know more about customer preferences</i>	120	3.00	5.00	4.300	.65594
<i>I have already set up my next social media goals.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.350	1.08968
<i>I regularly maintain the social media sites.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.941	.84312
<i>I regularly update the social media sites.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.000	.86966
<i>I don't have any barriers using social media for my business.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.891	.90559

Figure 32: Gender Experiences

The above graph in Figure 32 shows the distribution of the participant's responses on the Entrepreneurial experiences in the food UK. The graph also displays the seven questions under this theme: gender orientations. It can be observed that for all questions, the majority of the responses by the participants are strongly agreed, the second highest response for this set of questions is agreed to every variable of measurement except one question “*I have already set up my next social media goals*” where the second large majority of the participants are neutral. Also, approximately 66% of the total participants strongly agree that social media is a great

opportunity for the food business, while 50% strongly agree that social media adoption has increased the business.

The graph's result revealed that 40% of the total participants informed that they highly significantly regularly update social media and do not have any barrier to use, while 30% of the respondents agree to this significance. 43% of the participants strongly agree that they regularly maintain the social media platforms, whereas 27% of participants are only agreed for their food business.

5.6 Performance Measurement

5.6.1 Social Media Communications

This section explains the analysis of the social media communication questions provided under the theme of performance measurement. These questions are as followed:

1. I communicate with my customers to see if they are happy with my services
2. I follow the hashtags to communicate with customers
3. I follow the customers' like on my shared post to communicate with them.
4. I follow the customers' comments on my shared post to communicate with them.
5. In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote offers.
6. In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote new products.
7. I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge with customers.
8. I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge between customers and the business.

Under this theme of social media communication, eight scaled questions focused on what types of social media communication Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employed on their small and medium-sized food businesses. Each one question of social media communication was rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1) Strongly disagree to 5) strongly agree (see Table 29). The average mean value of the question ranged from 3.35 to 4.60. The standard deviations ranged from 0.58 to 1.08. The highest scale value questions were “*I communicate with my customers to see if they are happy with my services*” (Mean = 4.14), and “*In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote offers.*” (Mean = 4.13). On the other hand, the second highest scale value questions were “*In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote new products.*” (Mean = 4.06) “*I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge with customers.*” (Mean = 4.05 and “*I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge between customers and the business*” (Mean = 4.03). This was followed by and revealed a good amount of agreement on these questions “*I follow the customers’ like on my shared post to communicate with them*” (Mean = 3.70), “*I follow the customers’ comments on my shared post to communicate with them*” (Mean = 3.70) and “*I follow the hashtags to communicate with customers*” (Mean = 3.42). The result indicates that the entrepreneurs have shown a good amount of agreement with these statements. Overall results indicate that entrepreneurs observed social media communication enabled the relationship between customers and business. Moreover, they acknowledged that hashtags, likes, and comments on shared posts are productive communication activities. Social media communication descriptive statistics are presented in Table 32.

Table 32: Descriptive Statistics of Social Media Communication

Social Media Communication	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I communicate with my customers to see if they are happy with my services</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.1417	.67731
<i>I follow the hashtags to communicate with customers</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.4250	1.34516
<i>I follow the customers' like on my shared post to communicate with them.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.7083	1.11819
<i>I follow the customers' comments on my shared post to communicate with them.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.6917	1.11367
<i>In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote offers.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.1333	.82943
<i>In order to communicate with customers on social media, I promote new products.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.0667	.83750
<i>I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge with customers.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.0583	.85303
<i>I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge between customers and the business.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0333	.80891

Figure 33: Social Media Communications

The above graph in Figure 33 shows the distribution of the participants' responses on social media communications by Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK. The graph also displays the eight questions under this theme: performance measurement. It can be observed that for the all questions the majority of the responses by the participants are agreed, the second highest

response for this set of questions is strongly agree to every variable of measurement. Also, approximately 57% of the total participants in questions one and 47% of the participants on questions number 6, 7 and 8 agreed that regular social media communications built the bridge between customer and business and promoted the new products communicate with customers. The graph's result revealed that approximately 30% of the total participants strongly agree to the above all statements.

5.6.2 Social Media Interactions

This section will be analysing and explaining the questions under the theme of performance measurement. These questions are as followed:

1. My social media enable information-sharing with others.
2. I usually post on social media to interact with customers.
3. I generally share the posts on social media from other customers that are tagged to our profile.
4. I mainly interact with customers via social media by introducing new promotions.
5. It is easy to provide my opinion through my social media to my customers.
6. I upload food pictures on social media that is the way to interact with customers.
7. Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about products.
8. Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about services.

Under the theme of performance measurement, social media interaction consisted of eight scaled questions that focused on how Muslim entrepreneurs interact with their customers on social media in small and medium-sized food businesses. Social media interaction, each question was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1) Strongly disagree to 5) strongly agree (see Table 29). The average scale mean value of the question ranged from 3.63 to 4.34.

The standard deviations ranged from 0.727 to 1.099. The highest scale value questions were “*I upload food pictures on social media that is the way to interact with customers.*” (Mean = 4.34), and “*Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about products.*” (Mean = 4.21). This was followed by another three questions such as “*I usually post on social media to interact with customers*” (Mean = 4.18), “*My social media enable information-sharing with others.*” (Mean = 4.16) and “*Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about services.*” (Mean = 4.16). On the other hand, highest scale value questions were “*I mainly interact with customers via social media by introducing new promotions.*” (Mean = 3.99), “*It is easy to provide my opinion through my social media to my customers*” (Mean = 3.98), and “*I generally share the posts on social media from other customers that are tagged to our profile.*” (Mean = 3.63). The result indicates that the entrepreneurs showed a significant and good agreement with the social media interaction statements. However, entrepreneurs prefer uploading food pictures, and direct messaging about food products is the most significant interaction. Social media interaction scale descriptive statistics are presented in Table 33.

Table 33: Descriptive Statistics of Social Media Interaction

Social Media Interaction	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>My social media enable information-sharing with others.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.166	.79212
<i>I usually post on social media to interact with customers.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.183	.75574
<i>I generally share the posts on social media from other customers that are tagged to our profile.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.633	1.09953
<i>I mainly interact with customers via social media by introducing new promotions.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.991	.87443
<i>It is easy to provide my opinion through my social media to my customers.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	3.983	.82994
<i>I upload food pictures on social media that is the way to interact with customers.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.341	.72756
<i>Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about products.</i>	120	1.00	4.00	4.216	.80108
<i>Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about services.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.166	.75963

Figure 34: Social Media Interactions

The above graph in Figure 34 shows the distribution of the participants' responses to Muslim entrepreneurs' social media interactions initiatives in the UK. It can be observed that for the all questions the majority of the responses by the participants are agreed, the second highest response for this set of questions is strongly agree to every variables of measurement except one question "*I generally share the posts on social media from other customers that are tagged to our profile*" where second majority of the participants responses are neutral. Out of questions 1, 2, 4, 5, 7 and 8, 50% of the total participants agree that social media enabled the entrepreneurs to share the information to interact with customers, posting and sharing on social media, and one to one messaging for interaction for products, while 36%, 35%, 28%, 27% 40% and 35% of the respondents agree on this statement respectively. The graph's result revealed that 90% of the total participants informed that they are agreed that they "*I upload food pictures on social media that is the way to interact with customers*" out of 45% responses strongly agree to this statement.

5.6.3 Brand Awareness

This section will be analysing and explaining the questions under the theme of performance measurement. These questions are as followed:

1. I use SM heavily for my business brand awareness.
2. Content of my social media seems interesting.
3. Content of my social media is the newest information.
4. I pass the information on products from my social media profiles to my customers.
5. I use SM to inform my customers.
6. Using social media is very trendy.
7. Social media helps to customise the products.
8. Social media helps to customise the services.

Table 34 displays descriptive statistics of the eight questions under the themes of performance measurement; brand awareness. It is found out that the average scale mean value of each question ranged from 4.00 to 4.37. The standard deviations ranged from 0.649 to .864. Overall it can be observed that all the questions such as “*Content of my social media seems interesting*”; “*Using social media is very trendy*”, and “*I use SM heavily for my business brand awareness*” under this theme have a mean (M) values 4.37, 4.35 and 4.21, respectively that are above the value of 4.21.

This indicates the results are highly significant. The mean values of the other questions such as “*Content of my social media is the newest information*”; “*I pass the information on products from my social media profiles to my customers*”; “*I use SM to inform my customers*”; “*Social media helps to customise the products*” and “*Social media helps to customise the services*” indicate that the results are significant with mean values between 3.41 and 4.20. Therefore, results indicate that entrepreneurs significantly and mainly practice social media uses for their brand awareness. However, entrepreneurs found social media is very trendy, and the contents they shared significantly helped the businesses increase brand awareness.

Table 34: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Awareness

Brand Awareness	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I use SM heavily for my business brand awareness.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.2167	.80108
<i>Content of my social media seems interesting.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.3750	.64901
<i>Content of my social media is the newest information.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.1167	.76897
<i>I pass the information on products from my social media profiles to my customers.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.1000	.76036
<i>I use SM to inform my customers.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0667	.74171
<i>Using social media is very trendy.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.3500	.76312
<i>Social media helps to customise the products.</i>	120	3.00	5.00	4.1667	.66526
<i>Social media helps to customise the services.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0083	.86477

Figure 35: Social Media Brand Awareness

The above graph in Figure 35 shows the distribution of the participant's responses on the brand awareness initiatives by Muslim entrepreneurs running food businesses in the UK. The graph also displays the eight questions under this theme: performance measurement; brand awareness. It can be indicated that the majority of the responses by the participants are agreed, the second highest response for this set of questions is strongly agreed to every variable of measurement. The graph's result revealed that 84% of the total participants informed that they are agreed that "*using social media is very trendy*" out of 52% of responses strongly agree with this statement.

5.6.4 Customer Feedback

This section will be analysing and explaining the questions under the theme of performance measurement. These questions are as followed:

1. Social media helps the businesses to receive the positive feedback about the products.
2. Social media helps the businesses to receive the negative feedback about the products.
3. Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine positive feedback about the products.
4. Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine negative feedback about the products.
5. I directly respond them back if someone message me on social media.
6. I interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback.
7. I interact with customers to listen the complaints if anything creates inconvenience to them.

The descriptive statistics of the eight questions under the themes of performance measurement: customer feedback was presented below in Table 35. Customer feedback's one each question was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1) Strongly disagree to 5) strongly agree (see Table 29). The average scale mean value of the question ranged from 3.90 to 4.41. The standard deviations ranged from 0.727 to 1.099.

Overall it can be observed that, highest mean value questions were, such as "*Social media helps the businesses to receive the positive feedback about the products*"; "*Social media helps the businesses to receive the negative feedback about the products*"; "*Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine positive feedback about the products*" and "*Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine negative feedback about the products*" under this theme have a mean (M) values such as 4.41, 4.38, 4.25 and 4.208 respectively, observed and noted that these mean values are above the value of 4.20.

This indicates the results entrepreneurs significantly shown the agreement to the statements. While the mean values for the other questions such as “I interact with customers to listen the complaints if anything creates inconvenience to them”; “I interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback”, and “I directly respond them back if someone messages me on social media” indicate that the results are significant with mean values 4.07, 4.01, and 3.90 respectively.

Table 35: Descriptive Statistics of Customer Feedback

<i>Customer Feedback</i>	N	Mini	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Social media helps the businesses to receive the positive feedback about the products.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.4167	.69310
<i>Social media helps the businesses to receive the negative feedback about the products.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.3833	.67592
<i>Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine positive feedback about the products.</i>	120	1.00	5.00	4.2500	.79123
<i>Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine negative feedback about the products.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.2083	.79806
<i>I directly respond them back if someone message me on social media.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	3.9000	.98219
<i>I interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0167	.88861
<i>I interact with customers to listen the complaints if anything creates inconvenience to them.</i>	120	2.00	5.00	4.0750	.81129

Figure 36: Customer Feedback

The above graph in Figure 36 shows the distribution of the participant's responses on the customer feedback initiatives by Muslim entrepreneurs running food businesses in the UK. The graph also displays the seven questions under this theme: performance measurement; social media customer feedback. It can be observed that for the all questions the majority of the responses from the participants were strongly agreed. The second highest response for this set of questions is agreed to every variable of measurement except question number five, "*I directly respond them back if someone message me on social media*", where the second majority 31% of the participant's responses were neutral.

The graph's result revealed that 92% of the total participants agree that they "*Social media helps the businesses to receive the positive and negative feedback about the products*" out of 50% responses strongly agree to this statement. The results are also indicating that 85% and 82% of participants agreed to questions number 3, "*Social media helps the businesses to receive the negative feedback about the products*" and 4 "*Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine positive feedback about the products*" out of 43%, and 42% are strongly agreed to the statement.

5.7 Measurement of Constructs

The measurement model comprises six latent variables: social media uses, social media communication, social media interaction, brand awareness, customer feedback, and entrepreneurial experiences. Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the overall fit of measurement items in the conceptual model. The SPSS Version 26.0 was used to run the analysis. Based on correlation analysis results, the measurement model useful in assessing the reliability of measurements, internal consistency, convergent validity and discriminant validity.

5.7.1 Response Rate

A total 418 Directors/Owner/Senior Managers of food SMEs in the UK were surveyed. Out of 120 responses from online questionnaires were received, yielding a response rate of 28.70%; however, only 117 responses used and three responses were not used. Out of 3 non-usable responses were eliminated before inferential data analysis because they have only 1 response per empirical item such as 'Prefer not to Say' from 'Online Food Blogger' received one response, 'Wholesale' received two responses (1 male and 1 female) and this is not sufficient amount of responses in an empirical item to perform the analysis in SPSS 26.0. Therefore, these there were eliminated. The exclusion of 3 eliminated responses reduces the overall response rate to 28%.

5.7.2 Reliability

Reliability can be described as "*the degree to which it measures are free from error and yield consistent results*" (Peter, 1979). Reliability tests are useful and helpful, ensuring that specific measures would receive similar results when applied repeatedly to the same object. Several studies suggested that assessment of results for each statement of the measurement scale is the preferred test for assessment of individual item reliability (Hair et al., 2016). In this study, 51 questions such as statements out from total 59 were used to measure six dependent variables and seven independent variables. There are independent variables such as gender, ethnicity, and business types since they have a moderating effect on the six dependent variables and the interest of the research.

- **Internal Consistency Reliability**

Having said that, SPSS software Version. 26 was performed to find out the reliability of constructs by estimating the value of Cronbach's alpha. Internal consistency is the degree of intercorrelations between the different statements and variables to measure the same concept (Bijttebier et al., 2000). There are two main techniques, such as Cronbach's alpha and

composite reliability coefficients, to assess the internal consistency reliability (Peterson and Kim, 2013). Hair, Ringle and Sarstedt (2011) suggested a threshold value of 0.7 for internal reliability and consistency of the items. However, any value less than 0.60 is considered unreliable for further analysis. The value of Cronbach's alpha at 0.70 was considered satisfactory (Nunnally, 1978). However, in the analysis, Cronbach's alpha value used to measure the reliability, and estimated the constructs in the current research ranged from .742 to .863, all the Cronbach's alpha values have shown more significant than 0.7 in Cronbach's alpha, which reveals a good level of internal consistency (Nunnally, 1978). Therefore, the results from the data indicated an acceptable level of internal consistency shown in Table 36.

Table 36: Cronbach's Alpha Value

Predictable Variables and Items	Cronbach's Alpha Value (Variable)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (Item)
Social Media Uses (SMU)	0.82	
SMU1		.813
SMU2		.813
SMU3		.816
SMU4		.812
SMU5		.835
SMU6		.823
SMU7		.808
SMU8		.799
SMU9		.810
SMU10		.799
SMU11		.821
SMU12		.816
SMU13		.811
Social Media Communications (SMC)	0.86	
SMC1		.853
SMC2		.859
SMC3		.834
SMC4		.841
SMC5		.862
SMC6		.850
SMC7		.844

SMC8		.843
Social Media Interactions (SMI)	0.78	
SMI1		.753
SMI2		.739
SMI3		.796
SMI4		.778
SMI5		.759
SMI6		.746
SMI7		.759
SMI8		.752
Brand Awareness (BA)	0.858	
BA1		.863
BA2		.857
BA3		.835
BA4		.824
BA5		.826
BA6		.841
BA7		.834
BA8		.843
Customer Feedback (CFB)	08.23	
CFB1		.812
CFB2		.817
CFB3		.791
CFB4		.803
CFB5		.790
CFB6		.786
CFB7		.791
Entrepreneurial Experiences (EE)	0.79	
GE1		.791
GE2		.759
GE3		.777
GE4		.814
GE5		.736
GE6		.742
GE7		.774

5.7.3 Validity

Convergent validity assesses the asked questions or statements relationship to its construct and to other variables of the study (Hair et al., 2006). The assessment of the convergent validity can be found measuring the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Moreover, the value of 0.50 is the minimum recommendation to verify the convergent validity of specific construct (Chin,1998). Below Table 37 displays the AVE estimated results, which further confirms that outcomes meet the suggested criteria (such as minimum value of 0.50) of convergent validity suggested by (Chin, 1998). Inspection of correlation type indicates that factors that have relationship as constructs have positive and significant correlations. Thus, we can conclude that the scales have convergent validity.

Table 37: Table 5.16 Pearson Correlations and Square root of Average Variances

		SMU	SMC	SMI	BA	CFB	EE
SMU	r						
	p						
SMC	r	.698					
	p	.000					
SMI	r	.723	.721				
	p	.000	.000				
BA	r	.672	.752	.736			
	p	.000	.000	.000			
CFB	r	.550	.662	.657	.668		
	p	.000	.000	.000	.000		
EE	r	.670	.679	.639	.779	.607	
	p	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Note: The bold diagonal values are the square root of average variance extracted & p<0.05.

5.7.4 Discriminant Validity

Duarte, Alves and Raposo (2010) stated that discriminant validity measures latent constructs' distinctiveness and other variables. Since this study found all the constructs and variables highly correlated, therefore, discriminant validity cannot be performed

5.8 General Linear Measurement Model

5.8.1 Normality Test

The normality test of dataset is another assumption of MANOVA analysis. However, this specific assumption has less important when dealing with large sample of data, because in such cases chance of deviation are less (Darlington and Hayes, 2016). Moreover, regression analysis and correlation matrix can be completed when data distribution is not only normal, but a linear relationship exist among variables (Hair et al., 2006). This can be conducted testing the statistical value of skewness and kurtosis (Hair et al., 2006). Adding to this, skewness presents symmetry information while kurtosis provides the reflection on the ‘peakedness’ of the distribution (Pallant, 2016). The data may be significant and considered normally distributed when skewness and kurtosis measured the range of ± 2 values (Field, 2000). Thus, this study does not follow the graphical approach to examine the normality of data, but a table provided with measured values (Field, 2000). The Table 38 provides the confirmation that data collected for this research is normally distributed. Therefore, this evidences the qualification of data normality assumption.

Table 38: Normally Test Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Er of Skewness	Kurtosis	Std. Er of Kurtosis
SMU	120	46.0250	7.49842	.925	.221	.669	.438
SMC	120	27.2250	4.97466	-.113	.221	-.846	.438
SMI	120	32.6833	4.22474	.012	.221	-.164	.438
BA	120	33.4000	4.27500	-.074	.221	-.959	.438
CFB	120	29.2500	3.95617	-.139	.221	-.560	.438
EE	120	28.4583	3.83898	.047	.221	-.559	.438

Prior to conduct the two-way MANOVA, a Pearson correlation analysis was conducted between all of the dependent variables to test the assumptions of MANOVA that all the

dependent variables would be correlated with each other. As, correlation matrix can be seen in the Table 39, significant correlated patterns were observed among all the dependent variables, means that all the dependent variables were highly correlated with each other, suggesting the MANOVA appropriateness.

Table 39: Correlations Matrix of Control Variables

Control Variables		SMU	SMC	SMI	BA	CFB	EE	
Gende r	SMU	Correlation	1.000					
		Significance (2-tailed)	.					
		df	0					
	SMC	Correlation	.707	1.000				
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.				
		df	117	0				
	SMI	Correlation	.723	.730	1.000			
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.			
		df	117	117	0			
	BA	Correlation	.684	.749	.748	1.000		
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.		
		df	117	117	117	0		
	CFB	Correlation	.565	.657	.675	.661	1.000	
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	
		df	117	117	117	117	0	
	EE	Correlation	.669	.691	.638	.796	.629	1.000
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		df	117	117	117	117	117	0

5.8.2 MANOVA Factorial Analysis: Two-Way MANOVA Analysis

A factorial two-way MANOVA analysis was performed to compare the main effects of independent variables (IVs) such as gender, and business types (BT) as well as on their interaction effects on the all dependent variables (DV) such as social media uses (SMU), social media communication (SMC), social media interaction (SMI), brand awareness (BA),

customer feedback (CFB) and entrepreneurial experiences (EE). There was a significant difference between gender and business type (BT), when considered jointly (gender*business type) not statistically significant on the variables social media uses (SMU), social media communication (SMC), social media interaction (SMI), brand awareness (BA), customer feedback (CFB) and entrepreneurial experiences (EE), taking Walk's Lambda in account $\Lambda = .849$, $F(6, 102) = 3.022$, $p = .009$, partial $\eta^2 = .15$, $\Lambda = .542$, $F(24, 357) = 2.857$, $p = .000$, partial $\eta^2 = .14$ and $\Lambda = .702$, $F(24, 357) = 1.022$, $p = .428$, partial $\eta^2 = .05$ respectively. Statistical results were presented in Table 40.

Table 40: Multivariate Test

Effect		Value	F	df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercep	Pillai's Trace	.982	939.804 ^b	6.000	102.000	.000	.982
	Wilks' Lambda	.018	939.804 ^b	6.000	102.000	.000	.982
	Hotelling's Trace	55.283	939.804 ^b	6.000	102.000	.000	.982
	Roy's Largest Root	55.283	939.804 ^b	6.000	102.000	.000	.982
Gender	Pillai's Trace	.151	3.022 ^b	6.000	102.000	.009	.151
	Wilks' Lambda	.849	3.022 ^b	6.000	102.000	.009	.151
	Hotelling's Trace	.178	3.022 ^b	6.000	102.000	.009	.151
	Roy's Largest Root	.178	3.022 ^b	6.000	102.000	.009	.151
BT	Pillai's Trace	.534	2.697	24.000	420.000	.000	.134
	Wilks' Lambda	.542	2.857	24.000	357.046	.000	.142
	Hotelling's Trace	.712	2.982	24.000	402.000	.000	.151
	Roy's Largest Root	.475	8.309 ^c	6.000	105.000	.000	.322
Gender BT	Pillai's Trace	.223	1.034	24.000	420.000	.421	.056
	Wilks' Lambda	.792	1.029	24.000	357.046	.428	.057
	Hotelling's Trace	.244	1.022	24.000	402.000	.436	.058
	Roy's Largest Root	.117	2.041 ^c	6.000	105.000	.067	.104

Design: Intercept + Gender + BT + Gender * BT

The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level

Computed using alpha = .05_a

The Levene's test was conducted to find the homogeneity of variances of the groups in the IVs.

The results from the Levene's test were presented in the Table 41 below and inform the equality of homogeneity of error variances. From the Levene's test, based on mean showed that variances of the groups were not equal. The preliminary analysis indicates that the distributions fail to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of error variances on the dependent variables. However, MANOVA is robust to the violation of homogeneity of variances assumption. Thus, we continued the analysis.

Table 41: Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
SMU	Based on Mean	3.399	9	107	.001
	Based on Median	2.177	9	107	.029
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	2.177	9	72.195	.033
	Based on trimmed mean	3.237	9	107	.002
SMC	Based on Mean	2.431	9	107	.015
	Based on Median	1.886	9	107	.062
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.886	9	85.006	.065
	Based on trimmed mean	2.349	9	107	.019
SMI	Based on Mean	3.333	9	107	.001
	Based on Median	2.321	9	107	.020
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	2.321	9	73.767	.023
	Based on trimmed mean	3.229	9	107	.002
BA	Based on Mean	2.163	9	107	.030
	Based on Median	1.624	9	107	.117
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.624	9	89.783	.120
	Based on trimmed mean	2.148	9	107	.031
CFB	Based on Mean	2.340	9	107	.019
	Based on Median	1.109	9	107	.362

	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.109	9	66.646	.368
	Based on trimmed mean	2.178	9	107	.029
EE	Based on Mean	2.492	9	107	.013
	Based on Median	1.649	9	107	.111
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.649	9	78.601	.116
	Based on trimmed mean	2.411	9	107	.016

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Design: Intercept + Gender + BTYPES + Gender * BTYPES

In order to find the individual gender, BT and gender, ethnicity and their interaction differences on dependent variables, the researcher opted, and a separate two-way ANOVA was performed with each dependent variable, with each ANOVA evaluated at an alpha value of .05.

A two-way ANOVA between-subjects was performed to investigate the effect of gender and business types (BT) on social media uses (SMU). The preliminary analysis indicate that the distributions fail to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of error variances $F(9, 107) = 3.399$, $p = 0.001$ (see the Table 41, Levene's Test). However, ANOVA is robust to the violation of homogeneity of variances assumption. Thus, we continued the analysis. The main effect of gender did not significantly effect social media uses scores, $F(1, 107) = 1.212$, $p = 0.273$ with small effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.011$). Moreover, the main effect of BT did not significantly effect social media uses scores, $F(4, 107) = 1.058$, $p = 0.381$ with small effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.038$). Lastly, the interaction effect was investigated and also found to be not-significant $F(4, 107) = 1.760$, $p = 0.142$ but investigation of the effect size reveals that however non-significant this result has medium effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.062$). The between-subject effects are presented in Table 42.

Table 42: Social Media Uses Between-Subject Effects

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Gender	60.110	1	60.110	1.212	.273	.011
BT	209.827	4	52.457	1.058	.381	.038
Gender * BT	349.148	4	87.287	1.760	.142	.062
Error	5306.675	107	49.595			

A two-way between-subjects ANOVA performed to investigate the effect of gender and business types (BT) on social media communications (SMC). The preliminary analysis indicate that the distributions fail to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of error variances $F(9, 107)=2.431, p = 0.015$ (see the Table 41, Levene's Test). However, ANOVA is robust to the violation of homogeneity of variances assumption. Thus, we continued the analysis.

The main effect of gender did not significantly effect SMC scores, $F(1, 107)= 1.002, p = 0.319$ with negligible effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.009$). However, the main effect of business type was significant $F(4, 107)= 6.046, p < 0.001$ with very large effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.184$). Thus, we conducted a post-hoc analysis using Tukey correction. The results indicate that the Restaurant group scores significantly lower than Takeaway (MD=-3.92, $p = 0.04$) and Online Food Blogger Group (MD=-6.25, $p < 0.001$). The marginal means are presented in Table 43 and Figure 37.

Table 43: Marginal Means of Social Media Communications for Business Types

BT	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	UB
Fast food	27.750	1.233	25.305	30.195
Restaurant	25.369	.785	23.813	26.925
Takeaway	26.000	1.655	22.720	29.280
Desserts	27.940	1.189	25.584	30.297
Online Food Blogger	30.951	.861	29.245	32.658

Figure 37: Estimated Marginal Means of SMC for Business Types

Lastly, the interaction effect was investigated and found to be not-significant $F(4, 107)=2.073$, $p = 0.89$ but investigation of the effect size reveals that however non-significant this result has medium effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.072$). The between-subject effects are presented in Table 44.

Table 44: Social Media Communications Between-Subject Effects

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Gender	18.290	1	18.290	1.002	.319	.009
BT	441.461	4	110.365	6.046	.000	.184
Gender * BT	151.391	4	37.848	2.073	.089	.072
Error	1953.323	107	18.255			

A two-way between-subjects ANOVA performed to investigate the effect of gender and business types (BT) on social media interaction (Interaction). The preliminary analysis indicate that the distributions fail to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of error variances $F(9, 107)=3.333$, $p = 0.001$ (see the Table Levene's Test).

However, ANOVA is robust to the violation of homogeneity of variances assumption. Thus, we continued the analysis. The main effect of gender had a significant effect on Social Media Interaction scores, $F(1, 107) = 4.929, p = 0.029$ with small effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.044$). Further investigation reveals that males ($M=33.59$) scored significantly ($p= 0.029$) higher than females ($M=31.38$). This further indicates male entrepreneurs have a better social media interaction strategy as compared to female entrepreneurs (see Table 45).

Table 45: Pairwise Comparisons for Gender

Gender	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	UB
Male	33.59	.53	32.54	34.65
Female	31.38	.84	29.71	33.05

However, the main effect of BT did not significantly effect the social media interactions scores, $F(4, 107) = 2.237, p = 0.070$ with medium effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.077$). Lastly, the interaction effect was investigated and also found to be not-significant $F(4, 107) = 1.904, p = 0.115$ but investigation of the effect size reveals that however non-significant this result has medium effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.066$). Moreover, business types also had medium effect size. The between-subject effects are presented in Table 46.

Table 46: Social Media Interaction Between-Subject Effects

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Gender	79.590	1	79.590	4.929	.029	.044
BT	144.495	4	36.124	2.237	.070	.077
Gender * BT	122.971	4	30.743	1.904	.115	.066
Error	1727.723	107	16.147			

A two-way ANOVA between-subjects was conducted to explore the gender and business types (BT) effect on brand awareness. The preliminary analysis indicate that the distributions fail to satisfy the assumption of homogeneity of error variances $F(9, 107)= 2.163, p = 0.030$ (see the Table 41, Levene’s Test). However, ANOVA is robust to the violation of homogeneity of variances assumption. Thus, we continued the analysis. The main effect of BT had a significant effect on brand awareness scores, $F(4, 107)= 3.538, p = 0.009$ with medium effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.11$). However, the main effect of gender and interactions between gender and BT were not significantly effect the brand awareness scores, $F(1, 107)= 2.257, p = 0.613$ and $F(4, 107)= 1.419, p = 0.233$ with small effect size :partial $\eta^2 = 0.002$ ” and “partial $\eta^2 = 0.05$ ” respectively. The between-subject effects are presented in Table 47.

Table 47: Brand Awareness Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Gender	4.057	1	4.057	.257	.613	.002
BTYPES	223.421	4	55.855	3.538	.009	.117
Gender* BTYPES	89.633	4	22.408	1.419	.233	.050
Error	1727.723	107	16.147			

a. R Squared = .204 (Adjusted R Squared = .137)

Further investigation reveals that takeaway (M= 35.50) and online food business (M=35.09) runs by male entrepreneurs scored significantly ($p= 0.009$) higher than dessert (M=33.00), fastfood (M=33.00) and restaurant (M32.70). On the other hand, online food business (M=37.14) runs by female entrepreneurs scored significantly ($p= 0.009$) higher than dessert (M=33.16), fastfood (M=33.00), restaurant (M32.90) and takeaway (M= 29.50). The comparisons of business type for gender are presented in Table 48.

Table 48: Pairwise Comparisons of Business Type for Gender

Gender	Business Types	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Fast food	32.917	1.147	30.643	35.190
	Restaurant	31.690	.613	30.475	32.906
	Takeaway	35.500	1.256	33.009	37.991
	Desserts	33.000	1.502	30.023	35.977
	Online Food Blogger	35.091	1.198	32.716	37.466
Female	Fast food	33.000	1.987	29.062	36.938
	Restaurant	32.889	1.324	30.263	35.514
	Takeaway	29.500	2.810	23.930	35.070
	Desserts	33.167	1.622	29.951	36.382
	Online Food Blogger	37.143	1.062	35.038	39.248

The main effect of business type had a significant effect on customer feedback scores, $F(4, 107) = 4.752, p = 0.001$ with large effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.15$). However, the main effect of gender and interactions between gender and BT were not significantly effect the customer feedback scores, $F(1, 107) = .666, p = 0.416$ and $F(4, 107) = .600, p = 0.663$ with small effect size :partial $\eta^2 = 0.006$ ” and “partial $\eta^2 = 0.022$ ” respectively. The between-subject effects are presented in Table 49.

Table 49: Customer Feedback Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Gender	8.599	1	8.599	.666	.416	.006
BT	245.324	4	61.331	4.752	.001	.151
Gender * BT	30.997	4	7.749	.600	.663	.022
Error	1381.118	107	12.908			

a. R Squared = .138 (Adjusted R Squared = .066)

Further investigation indicated that takeaway (M= 31.60) and online food business (M=31.27) runs by male entrepreneurs scored significantly ($p= 0.001$) higher than dessert (M=27.00),

fastfood (M=28.66) and restaurant (M27.754). On the other hand, online food business (M=32.64) runs by female entrepreneurs scored significantly ($p= 0.001$) higher than Fast food (M=30.25), takeaway (M= 29.00) and restaurant (M28.33). The comparisons of business type for gender are presented in Table 50.

Table 50: Comparisons of Business Type for Gender

Gender	BTYPES	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Fast food	28.667	1.037	26.611	30.723
	Restaurant	27.548	.554	26.449	28.647
	Takeaway	31.600	1.136	29.348	33.852
	Desserts	27.000	1.358	24.308	29.692
	Online Food Blogger	31.273	1.083	29.125	33.420
Female	Fast food	30.250	1.796	26.689	33.811
	Restaurant	28.333	1.198	25.959	30.707
	Takeaway	29.000	2.540	23.964	34.036
	Desserts	29.500	1.467	26.592	32.408
	Online Food Blogger	32.643	.960	30.739	34.546

The effects of Gender and Ethnicity with SMU, SMC, SMI, BA, and CFB performed. In this regard, a series of two-way between-subjects ANOVA analyses conducted. The results indicate that only the Customer Feedback aspect is significantly affected. The other aspects of social media did not have a significant main effect or interaction effect.

Table 51: Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances

		Levene	df1	df2	Sig.
		Statistic			
CFB	Based on Mean	.760	9	107	.653
	Based on Median	.630	9	107	.769
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.630	9	88.824	.768
	Based on trimmed mean	.754	9	107	.659

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.^{a,b}

a. Dependent variable: CUSTFEEDB

b. Design: Intercept + Gender + Ethnicity + Gender * Ethnicity

Thus, a two-way between-subjects ANOVA conducted to investigate if Customer Feedback (CFB) differs in terms of Gender (Gender: Male, Female), the Ethnicity (Ethnicity: British Muslim, British Pakistani, British Indian, British Bangladeshi, and Other Muslim), or their interaction. The preliminary analysis of Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances indicates that the distributions satisfy $F(9, 107) = 0.76, p = 0.65$ the assumption of homogeneity of the variances presented in Table 51.

Table 52: F Test for Heteroskedasticity

F	df1	df2	Sig.
.092	1	115	.763

a. Dependent variable: CFB

b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.

c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + Gender + Ethnicity + Gender * Ethnicity

Moreover, the F Test for Heteroskedasticity (Table 52) indicates that the distributions also satisfy $F(1, 115) = 0.092, p = 0.76$ the assumption of heteroskedasticity. The results of the ANOVA analysis indicated that the main effect of Gender is not significant ($F(1, 107) = 1.814, p = 0.18, \eta^2_p = 0.017$ with a small effect size. Moreover the main effect of the Ethnicity is also not significant ($F(4, 107) = 1.005, p = 0.41, \eta^2_p = 0.036$ with a small effect size. However, the interaction effect is significant ($F(4, 107) = 2.631, p = 0.038, \eta^2_p = 0.090$ with a large effect size. Estimated marginal means of CFB is presented in Table 53.

Table 53: Estimated Marginal Mean of Gender*Ethnicity

Dependent Variable: CFB		95% Confidence Interval			
Gender	Ethnicity	Mean	Std. Error	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	British Muslim	32.100	1.148	29.824	34.376
	British Pakistani	29.043	.530	27.993	30.092
	British Indian	29.500	2.567	24.411	34.589
	British Bangladeshi	28.800	1.624	25.581	32.019
	Other Muslim	25.611	.856	23.915	27.308
Female	British Muslim	30.250	1.815	26.651	33.849
	British Pakistani	30.353	.881	28.607	32.099
	British Indian	31.000	1.624	27.781	34.219
	British Bangladeshi	28.333	2.096	24.178	32.489
	Other Muslim	31.833	1.482	28.895	34.772

5.9 Testing of Hypothesis

In this section, proposed hypotheses were tested. The path coefficient estimation is significantly important in order to test the hypotheses in empirical investigation using SPSS V.26 as each path refers to a hypothesis. The importance of these paths is entirely depending on the values of ‘*p*’ correlated with them. In order to estimate the p-value bootstrapping is one of the most reliable method. The analysis procedure sets off with testing the hypotheses, which tests the relationship between independents constructs (variables). Since all hypotheses in this study were directed in same manner, so all the hypotheses were tested using two-tailed t-tests. Moreover, the bivariate correlation analysis was given the R^2 value for the Pearson correlation. According to Downing and Clark (2003) “ R^2 measures the percent of the variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by regression. The value of R^2 will always be between 0 and 1”. The relationship is substantial if the value of R^2 is greater than 0.75; relationship is moderate if the value of R^2 is 0.50, and the relationship is weak if the value of R^2 is 0.25

(Wong, 2013). The measurement model presented in Figure 38 and proposed hypotheses results are presented in Table 54.

Figure 38: Measurement Model

Table 54: Hypotheses Results

Hypotheses	Relationships	Findings
H1	Social media uses (SMU) have a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Supported
H2	Social media communication (SMC) has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Supported
H3	Social media Interaction (SMI) has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Supported
H4	Brand Awareness has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Supported
H5	Customer Feedback has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Supported
H6	Gender has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.	Not Supported

H₀: Social Media Uses does not have a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₁: Social Media Uses have a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 55: H1 Results

<i>Correlations</i>		Social Media Uses	Entrepreneurial Experience
Social Media Uses	Pearson Correlation	1	.668**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	.668**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 55 shows the degree of relationship between social media uses and entrepreneurial experience. It can be deduced from the results that there is a positive correlation coefficient ($\rho=0.668$) that is statistically significant at 0.01 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and concludes that social media uses positively impact the entrepreneurial experience.

H₀: SM Communication has no positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₂: SM Communication has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 56: H2 Results

<i>Correlations</i>		Social Media Communication	Entrepreneurial Experience
Social Media Communication	Pearson Correlation	1	.664**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	.664**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 56 showed the degree of relationship between social media communication and entrepreneurial experience. The correlation results revealed that there is a positive correlation coefficient ($\rho=0.664$) that is statistically significant at 0.01 alpha level ($0.000 < 0.01$). Therefore, this study rejected the null hypothesis and concludes that social media communication has a positive significant impact on entrepreneurial experience.

H₀: Social media interaction has no positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₃: Social media interaction has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 57: H3 Results

<i>Correlations</i>		Social media Interaction	Entrepreneurial Experience
Social media Interaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.629**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	.629**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In Table 57 the degree of relationship between social media interaction and entrepreneurial experience presented. The outcomes revealed that there is a positive correlation coefficient ($\rho=0.629$) that is statistically significant at 0.01 alpha level ($0.000<0.01$). Thus, this study rejected the null hypothesis and concludes that social media interaction positively impacts on entrepreneurial experience.

H₀: Brand Awareness has no positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₄: Brand Awareness has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 58: H4 Results

<i>Correlations</i>			
		Brand Awareness	Entrepreneurial Experience
Brand Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.774**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	.774**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 58 presented the relationship between brand awareness and entrepreneurial experience. From the results, it is indicated that there is a positive correlation coefficient ($\rho=0.774$) that is statistically significant at 0.01 alpha level ($0.000<0.01$). Hence, this study again rejected the null hypothesis and concludes that brand awareness has a positive significant impact on entrepreneurial experience.

H₀: Customer Feedback has no positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₅: Customer Feedback has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 59: H5 Results

<i>Correlations</i>		Customer Feedback	Entrepreneurial Experience
Customer Feedback	Pearson Correlation	1	.595**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	.595**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 59 showed the degree of relationship between customer feedback and entrepreneurial experience where it was revealed that there is a positive correlation coefficient (rho=0.595) that is statistically significant at 0.01 alpha level (0.000<0.01). Thus, this study rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that customer feedback has a positive significant impact on entrepreneurial experience.

H₀: Gender has no positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

H₆: Gender has a positive significant impact on the entrepreneurial experience.

Table 60: H6 Results

<i>Correlations</i>		Gender	Entrepreneurial Experience
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	-.024**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.794
	N	117	117
Entrepreneurial Experience	Pearson Correlation	-.024**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.794	
	N	117	117

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 60 displayed the relationship between gender and entrepreneurial experience. The results indicated that there is a negative correlation coefficient ($\rho = -.024$) that is not statistically significant at 0.05 alpha level ($0.794 > 0.05$). Therefore, this study accepted the null hypothesis and concluded that gender does not have a positive significant impact on entrepreneurial experience.

5.10 Summary

Chapter five discussed quantitative findings on the topic of gender impacts on Muslim entrepreneurs using social media marketing in food SMEs. Firstly, the study presented the demographic characteristics of sampling. Secondly, it presented the descriptive statistics of the study. Thirdly, it was followed by details of data analysis to assess measurement variables constructs and GLM by using two-way ANOVA analysis. The measurement model and constructs variables' assessment comprise four different tests: reliability of constructs, including the internal consistency, validity, discriminant validity, and normality test to evaluate all the constructs in the study. Lastly, two-way ANOVA analyses were performed between the 'gender and business types' and 'gender and ethnicity and their interactions to determine the different gender impacts on Muslim entrepreneurs in this study.

Summary of key findings from quantitative study is presented on next page.

Summary of key Findings from Quantitative study

In this section, summary of the key findings presented emerged by the survey questionnaire that was undertaken with Muslim male and female entrepreneurs runs food businesses in the UK. The main aim of presenting this section is to provide the list of key findings emerged from the online questionnaire. The main aim of this study is to examine the gender impacts on Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards the use of social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. The key findings that were emerged from quantitative study can be summarised according to the research objectives as follows:

Research Objective 1: To explore the role of social media platforms usage by Muslim entrepreneurs in food businesses.

- Out of the finding seventy percent participants were the male entrepreneurs while 30% were the female entrepreneurs. Adding to this, majority of the 54% participants were British Muslim Pakistani, followed by 21% participants were the other Muslim and 12% were the British Muslim.
- The result from the table revealed that 62% of the total participants claimed they mainly use Facebook for their food business; 64.2% also claimed they mainly use Instagram for their food business while 43.3% of these total participants claimed they use the entire social media channel which includes Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Snapchat for their food business. Out of 72% and 64% participants indicated they do not mainly use Twitter and Snapchat.
- Interestingly, majority of 95% entrepreneurs informed social media is great opportunity in today's world because social media adoption increased the business performance in many ways, such as communication, brand awareness, interaction,

revenue, form marketing strategies, and engage with customers. Additionally, nearly 70% of the entrepreneurs have not any barriers to use social media as they regularly update these platforms.

Research Objective 2: To investigate social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK.

- The result indicates that the entrepreneurs observed social media communication enabled the relationship between customers and business. And they acknowledged that hashtags, giving likes and comments on the shared posts are productive communication activities.
- A big majority of both male and female entrepreneurs prefer uploading food pictures and direct messaging about food products, considered the most significant communication of interaction.

Research Objective 3: To find out the gender experience of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs using social media marketing for their food businesses.

- Findings indicated entrepreneurs employ extensively social media for brand awareness.
- Majority of both male and female entrepreneurs identified that social media has enabled the businesses to receive the positive and negative feedback on products.
- The results indicate that the majority of female entrepreneurs run online food blogger businesses as compared to takeaways and restaurant businesses.
- Further investigation reveals that male entrepreneurs have a better social media interaction strategy as compared to female entrepreneurs.

- A big majority of female entrepreneurs use SMM to increase the BA of online food blog businesses and dessert shop, whereas male entrepreneurs increase the brand awareness of takeaways and online food businesses
- Majority of female entrepreneurs run online food blogs and desserts shops, while male entrepreneurs run takeaways, Fast-food and restaurants.

Chapter six, which is the next chapter, will conclude the research.

Chapter 6 – Conclusions

6.1 Introduction

The chapter aims to cover both the research discussion and conclusion by responding to the research question and objective set for this study; thus, it will be categorized into several sections. Therefore, section 6.1 provides an overview of the chapter. In section 6.2, results presented against the research objectives. Section 6.3 discusses the deliberate results of the predictable variables findings. This was followed by section 6.4 that critically tests the hypothesis of this study, 6.5 compares similarities and differences between organization and customers. Also, section 6.6 outlines explicitly the key lessons learned from the research by considering the theoretical and practical contribution of this study, and section 6.7 states the limitation of the research, 6.8 suggests the future of research, and 6.9 provides important managerial implications for effective use of social media within the context of entrepreneurship and food business.

6.2 Results against the Objectives

This study explores whether gender impacts Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' experiences towards using social media marketing for their food businesses in the UK. This section concludes the research by drawing the main study results and acknowledging the set research objectives. This study has concluded that the research participants are British Muslim entrepreneurs following that they employ social media platform marketing to communicate and engage with customers influenced by their actions and gender.

- **Research question 1**

What are the roles of social media platforms used by Muslim entrepreneurs in the food industry?

- **Objective 1**

To explore the role of social media platforms usage by Muslim entrepreneurs in food businesses.

The participant's entrepreneurial decision and actions have a significant impact on forming a marketing opportunity. The research findings suggest that entrepreneurs form marketing opportunities based on their individual experiences, interests, decision, action, and gender. Moreover, results further inform that a social media platform could be referred to as a platform that enables an entrepreneur to communicate with customers to share vital ideas and information about their organisation's brands and service (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). To form and identify a marketing opportunity, these entrepreneurs employed several social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat. They consider that this study has identified these platforms as the main channels through which entrepreneurs marketing their small and medium-sized food businesses. These specific platforms helped the SMEs to grow, increased brand awareness and enhance the business performance.

- **Research question 2**

What are the social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK?

- **Objective 2**

To investigate social media marketing strategies used by Muslim Entrepreneurs in the UK.

The second objective of this research was to identify the British Muslim entrepreneurs' social media marketing strategies to engage with customers. The results indicate that Muslim entrepreneurs actively market food products and services via social media platforms to engage and communicate with customers. Moreover, findings suggest several other reasons behind this novel fact: low-cost marketing, free to use, social media is easily accessible, and can engage with niche markets.

The results further indicate Muslim entrepreneurs created business social media profiles and pages and connected with social media networks to show engagement and enhance communication with customers. They promote business online, they use paid-for marketing advertisements, such as Facebook ads, Instagram ads, Twitter, and YouTube ads, identified by these participants as the most sponsored ads to engage with various customers across the UK food industries. These social media business pages' promotional activities post food pictures, share food videos and allow customers to add positive or negative product reviews for further customer communication and engagement. The food pictures and videos they take are then posted on their social media business profiles, pages, and groups, generating relevant contents and enhancing their market reach. They also use their business social media pages to help different social causes that enable these entrepreneurs to create a business social image in society. The results indicate that British Muslim experiences highly influence the social media content, which enables customer engagement and gives them a competitive edge in the food market in the UK.

This study finding is consistent with that of Thoumrungroje (2014), who argued that social media marketing helps entrepreneurs take advantage of modern communication tools and adjust to the new effective business style. Moreover, the participants arguably believed that social media marketing tools are the most significant constructive pathway of communicating with customers online, give that social media marketing tools promote accessible communication with clients online.

- **Research question 3**

What are the different gender experiences of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employing social media marketing for their food businesses?

- **Objective 3**

To find out the gender experiences of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employing social media marketing for their food businesses.

To achieve the third objective of this study, the researcher explored the gender phenomena and their differences in social media marketing utilisation by Muslim entrepreneurs in the food industry. This study indicates that gender-based entrepreneurial orientations in social media marketing have impacts on business profitability and sustainability. Novel evidence obtained in this study shows that social media experience significantly increases the entrepreneur's business performance. Besides, this study informed that both male and female entrepreneurs have a different set of business goals; increase the business sale and increase the followers; conversely, some participants claimed their goals are to improve business sales and create business awareness for brands.

This research found that British Muslim entrepreneurs specifically preferred to use powerful social media platforms to engage and communicate with customers, given that they are commonly used across the globe. Adding to this, male entrepreneurs preferred to use Facebook due to the large number of followers, whereas female entrepreneurs are inclined to use Instagram because it helps create appealing food pictures and contents. Findings also informed the several issues related to social media marketing such as fakes brand review, technical problem, time-consuming and algorithm, which are the core barriers for Muslim entrepreneurs. This is also consistent with the literature, which claimed a lack of the identified factors was recognised as an important problem to social media marketing (Michaelidou, Siamagka, & Christodoulides, 2011). However, male entrepreneurs perceived fake reviews and algorithms, while female entrepreneurs considered it time-consuming and lack of technical knowledge. The findings show that women entrepreneurs are more towards service business such as online food blogging, male entrepreneurs towards product business: restaurant, takeaway and Fast food businesses.

6.3 Results against Effects of Predictable Variables.

6.3.1 Elements of Social Media Marketing

Social media for business purposes is one of the key marketing tools in the entrepreneurship business in today's food industries; hence social media will stand as the imperative marketing approaches for business, most especially for UK food industries. This study observed that both newly establish and older entrepreneurs can improve their marketing strategy through social media marketing (Lindsey-Mullikin and Borin, 2017; Pantano and Di Pietro, 2013). The elements of social media could be explored to have a clear understanding and impact of social media marketing in the context of entrepreneurship in the UK food industry.

Lindsey-Mullikin and Boring (2017) described how social uses (. i.e. an element of social media) can be utilised in communication to create content, customers contact and community activities. Meanwhile, to ensure that entrepreneurs make use of these elements; this study identified four core elements that are required for effective use of social media for business purpose; this includes social media perception, social media platform, social media as a marketing tool and social media marketing strategy.

Every entrepreneur is utilising social media in their daily business activities. Some entrepreneurs are using it much better than other entrepreneurs because their various perceptions and method of using social media for business may not be the same. Thus, social media in entrepreneurship context is a process of taking the merit of the customer audience, reach customers and potential advert of organisations brands and services for a better outcome and long-lasting profits. With the participant's experience, social media has enabled people to grow their business and make a better living through online businesses (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). Following this, Nielsen (2017) argued that most business customers of this era spend much time on social media for buying and selling.

For reasons, the perception of entrepreneurs on social media businesses would determine how effectively they use social media for business. For instance, participant 2-F asserted that everyone can use social media platforms through phone or other devices to make ends for business, while participant 2-M contented that the perception depends on the extent to which entrepreneurs advertise and update their businesses activities. This is in line with several scholars' empirical findings, which identified that effective uses of social media by entrepreneurs could improve B2B marketing and purchasing behaviours (Järvinen and Taiminen, 2016).

According to Ryan (2017) better understanding social media business helps prospective entrepreneurs be aware of brands and service interest of their customer. In the same way, Reijonen (2010) documented that entrepreneurs could strategies their social media business to capture the intention of customer to achieve increase business goals through this perception. Thus, participant 4-M argued that social media is a channel through which entrepreneurs communicate and provide businesses to people.

Therefore, social media business encompasses different online platforms where both entrepreneurs and customers communicate and engage people with buying and selling (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). In relation to this trend, participant 3-M and 1-M understood that social media means Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, Snapchat and other online community's entrepreneurs and customers share their knowledge regarding the company's brands and service offer. These findings aligned with prior studies, which identified Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, Snapchat as the core channel explored by many entrepreneurs to communicate and engage their customer for business transactions (Rayan, 2017; Genç, and Oksuz, 2015; Martin, 2015; Granger and Reiter, 2015).

In respect to participants' perceptions on significant social media platforms, it is observed that there were distinct social media at which entrepreneurs could be explored to communicate, advertise and engage with their prospective customers. Thus, a social media platform could be referred to as a platform that enables an entrepreneur to communicate with customers to share vital ideas and information about their organisation's brands and service (Doty and Dworkin, 2014). Considering this definition, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat have been identified by this study as the channel through which entrepreneurs market with their businesses.

Similarly, several studies have also acknowledged Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, Snapchat as the primary channel today's entrepreneurs use to engage with business and customers (Boupha et al., 2013). Interestingly among this platform, 18 participants disclosed that Instagram is the main channel explored by entrepreneurs to advertise and communicate with customers. This substantiated previously conducted research findings in the literature that identified Instagram as a platform that both entrepreneurs and customers negotiate (Aku, 2018; Granger and Reiter, 2015). For instance, Granger and Reiter (2015) identified Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Periscope and Snapchat but concluded that Instagram is one of the core platforms used by British Muslim entrepreneurs.

On the other hand, 15 participants specifically preferred the Facebook platform for their online business activities; for instance, participant 10-F stressed that Instagram, Twitter and Snapchat are difficult for her to use; thus, she preferred to explore the Facebook platform to interact and advertise the business. Participants 13-M, 14-M and 15-M shared similar views and claimed that they combined both Facebook and Instagram to communicate with customers. These findings are consistent with Oham, Kokkranikal, & Coca-Stefaniak (2019) and Gentina, Chen and Yang (2020) opinions that maintained that Facebook and Instagram are significant for entrepreneurs. It reduces the level of resource and increases performance.

Surprisingly empirically evidence showed that only 6 participants recognised Twitter, YouTube and Snapchat could be utilised by entrepreneurs to communicate and share information with customers. Following these findings, Hruska and Maresova (2020) argued that entrepreneurs with high income and high education explored the most in business, but their social media usage reduce when they are older. With this trend, it is observed from these participants, regardless of the platforms used by people, social media enable entrepreneurs to facilitate key resources and improve profitability (Ryan, 2017).

In relation to these findings, it is important to note that among these social media platform participants, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat, and YouTube platform mostly because it can be easy to use to shared food pictures with their customers. This concurs well with Martin (2015) results which specifically identified Snapchat and Instagram as the most innovative platform for food businesses. Conversely, it maintained that female entrepreneurs in the UK food industries are inspired to set up their platform for food business.

Thus, it was acknowledged that entrepreneurs preferred a specific platform for their business for three primary reasons: it is generally used worldwide. Secondly, many people could easily assess it, and thirdly it promotes extra features for business. In accordance with the present results, previous studies have demonstrated that social media platform, online advertisement and communities are successfully promoting both product loyalty and purchase intention through various platforms (Balakrishnan, Dahnil, & Yi, 2014).

The quantitative findings also revealed that the majority of the entrepreneurs used Instagram, followed by Facebook. Moreover, this result is supported and validated by survey (online questionnaire) analysis.

Social media marketing has become the central device for a higher level of entrepreneur arrangement, positively heavy principal creation through communication and content sharing that is particularly important social media platform (Evans, 2010). Following this definition, the participants agreed that social media marketing as a tool is the most creative means of managing a successful business in the UK food industries. Thus, these entrepreneurs claimed that social media marketing tools enable them to provide information about business needs, customer review and competitive movement (Constantinides, 2014), given that social media marketing could be used as tools of interaction, direct sales, gaining and retaining customers. The most obvious finding to emerge from the analysis is that 6 participants contended that social media marketing tools promote entrepreneurship business and increase their brand's awareness. This finding is consistent with that of Thoumrungroje (2014), who argued that social media marketing helps entrepreneurs take advantage of modern communication tools and adjust to the new effective business style. Considering this idea, participant 15-M claimed that organisations gain more customers through social media marketing. Moreover, the participants arguably believed that social media marketing tools are the greatest constructive pathway of communicating with customers online, give that social media marketing tools promote easy communication with clients online. These results corroborate Pantano and Di Pietro (2013) ideas, who advocated that social media marketing enables businessperson and customer to identify brands information and interact with customers view before purchasing them. The present results are significant in at least two major respects (i) it indicated that social media marketing tool promotes easy access to advance technology for business; (ii) it does not only promote easy contact with customers but also sharing brands information.

To use social media for marketing purposes, entrepreneurs must ensure that the marketing they explored is designed to both the organisation and customers through brands, products and competitors' engagement (Ryan, 2017). Following this assumption, this study proposes that analytics, sponsor aid and social media trend are the commonly used strategies by entrepreneurs to advertise their products brand and customer perception as a whole (Donoghue, 2011). More interestingly, 13 participants stressed that these strategies help to understand the product or services target of their customer, given that this understanding helps them to set up social media marketing strategies that promote business performance.

Analytics – This study claimed that analytics social media strategy is a more broadly used tool for creating online business strategy and assessing business operation. This is because 13 participants confirmed that analytics strategy provides an effective customer review. This aligns with Taiminen & Karjaluoto Karjaluoto (2015) findings which identified that uses and understanding of digital marketing tools help to adopt digitalise market platform in SMEs. With this, 6 participants said that Facebook insight helps to obtained customer review and information.

Similarly, 3 participants felt that Instagram analytics enable them to have access to the customer profile, which helps them know customers' choice. Typically, understanding customer taste or target would help organisations design accordingly (Amit and Zott, 2001). Though, it is also a few observed that only 2 participant uses using google analytics and google AdWords to examine customers attitude of their brands and services. The present results are significant in at least two major respects as it confirmed that entrepreneurs most use Facebook insight and Instagram analytics in UK food industries (Akbar & Özgül, 2018; Oham, Kokkranikal, & Coca-Stefaniak., 2019).

For instance, participant 17-F believed that the social media marketing strategy tool is important for the food industry in the UK, given that without marketing strategy tool,

entrepreneurs will lose their target audience and find it difficult to meet business goals. In respect to this idea, Carroll and Wagar (2010) maintained that insight on how distinct social media marketing strategies are used in online business required a broad understanding by entrepreneurs. In the same fashion, Parker and Castleman (2007) recommend that owner-managers of entrepreneurship businesses must ensure that digital marketing adopted in the organisation aligned with their business goals.

Furthermore, this study provides a piece of empirical evidence on how these analytics and techniques help entrepreneurs measure social media marketing and success. As most participants admitted that explored analytics tool to interact and access customers behaviours, the tools generate insights to design and measure the social media marketing strategy. These findings confirm the association with Kanan and Li (2017), who termed social media marketing strategy as a technology that promotes effective communication between entrepreneurs and customer to maintain business values.

Besides, among these participants, three female entrepreneurs claimed that social media analytics tools designed to analyse both business performance and customer behaviours are helpful, whereas male entrepreneurs claimed that using different analytics promotes business improvement. This study has shown a direct significance between analytics tool and entrepreneurs business performance (Chaffey and Smith, 2013); thus, it is important to entrepreneurs utilise these tools effectively in their daily business activities.

Sponsored Ads – it is crucial to note that sponsored ads have been identified as one of the social media marketing strategies within the entrepreneurship business. This matched with an assertion in the literature that states that sponsored ads epitomise alternative means of interacting with people, as does not intrusive and seem to respond to network searchers' own requests (Gauzente, 2010). Following this trend, 16 participants, which consist of male and female were on the views that to promote business digitally, they paid-for marketing

advertisement; as Facebook ads, Instagram ads, Twitter, and YouTube ads were identified by these participants the most sponsored ads to engage with various customers across the UK food industries.

For instance, participants 17-F stressed that these strategies enable entrepreneurs to attract many future customers and encourage that businessperson to pay for sponsored ads to improve business and customers satisfaction. In this way, literature documented that social media marketing helps both organisation and customers identify product information and an overview of customers about the products (Pantano and Di Pietro, 2013; Hsu et al., 2015). Similarly, participant 5 -F further that sponsored ads is cost-effective of which facilitate customer engagement.

Furthermore, Participant 8-M stated that Instagram ads are mostly efficient than Facebook ads because they are commonly seen by young people. These results reflect those of Aku (2018), who also assumed that Facebook and Instagram influence importantly in recognising creativity among entrepreneurs and customers retentions. Thus, it is observed that female participants perceived sponsored ads strategy to be cost-efficient, whereas male participants believed in a combination of various social media platform to improve business and customer needs. These results also supported by online survey that the majority of participants showed agreement, used sponsored ads to market the business.

Social Media Trend – This is an understanding of trends based on content-sharing of users' communication and chat discussion (Afiyanita, 2021). Following this notion, this study contends that the vast knowledge of social media marketing tools could help entrepreneurs solve business problems by taking customer product preferences based on social media marketing strategies. Evidence of this was revealed by 16 participants who claimed that they explored the modern social media marketing trends to advertise and communicate with

customers. This fit with empirical evidence of Kwok and Yu, (2013) who categories the social media marketing activities such as sales, marketing and conversational.

Interesting to derive the benefit of social media trend, 4 participants states that entrepreneurs must adopt distinct marketing trends such as Facebook Live video from the kitchen and Instagram hashtags to connect with many customers. This also shows the agreements with our earlier observations, which showed that Facebook and Instagram are mostly used platform for online business (Akbar, & Özgül, 2018; Greve & Salaff, 2003).

Contrary to this, 4 participants lack the understanding of social media trends; thus, they do not adopt any digital marketing strategies in their business operation; rather, they keep constant communication with customers concerning their needs. However, these results were not very encouraging, but it has been confirmed in the literature that effective communication with customers regularly improves business performance and customer retention (Ryan, 2017; Constantinides, 2014). The quantitative findings also revealed that the majority of the entrepreneurs use social media to update the customers with the latest food trends and do not go live to interact with customers. Therefore, this result is supported and validated by survey (online questionnaire) analysis (See Section 5.4.1.)

6.3.2 Social Media Gender Orientation/ Experience

This study acknowledged that gender entrepreneurial orientations in social media marketing have both direct and indirect impact on food SMEs, given that higher orientation of social media by both female and male entrepreneurs could improve competitive advantage and resilience to business problems (Okello, 2020). Novel evidence obtained in this study shows that social media experience is significantly information entrepreneurs business performance. Although the opinions of the participants are differ based on their gender differences. For instance, male participants argued that to improve business, entrepreneurs must keep a tap of a new trend of social media marketing tools.

This is consistent with extant literature, which stressed that social media experience promotes inter and intra organisation operations with diverse customers (Martín-Rojas, Garrido-Moreno, & García-Morales, 2020). One of the male entrepreneurs contended that the uses of social media for business purposes had been a learning experience, as it helps to understand an overview of customers' needs and taste. This is in line with Manca, Bocconi & Gleason (2021), who reasoned that social media marketing eases open interaction and advantageous views from customers and partners.

"Social Media use helps organisations to understand customer needs and respond to them proactively, enhancing innovation success" (Martín-Rojas, Garrido-Moreno, & García-Morales, 2020, p.397). Similarly, on the other hand, female participants claimed that social media orientation could enable entrepreneurs to form their marketing strategy with customers' needs. Following this, it is confirmed in the literature that female entrepreneurs are now competing with male entrepreneurs in social media marketing strategy (Okello, 2020). However, it observed that the gender of entrepreneurs could influence the profitability of entrepreneurial business and continuity. The quantitative study's results support this that 80% of the entrepreneurs agreed *"Social media helped me to know more about customer preferences"*. Moreover, these results are supported and validated by a survey (online questionnaire) that these entrepreneurs regularly maintain and update their social media platforms to follow the latest trends concerning food and business (See Section 5.5.1.).

Social media marketing strategies promote connectivity and customers with a wide range of customers, suppliers and partners that help develop investigative activities of both entrepreneurs and customers (Martín-Rojas, Garrido-Moreno, & García-Morales, 2020). Social media for business offers significant goals to entrepreneurs according to their business target. For this reason, 10 participants admitted that their social media's significant goals are to

increase followers; this links with wider literature that argued an increase in the number of customers improves business sales (Doty and Dworkin, 2014).

For instance, participant 8-M, 3-M and 16-F main goal is to have more followers on Facebook; participant 14-M, on the other hand, the significant goal is to create brand awareness using social media. This result collaborates with many scholars' views, which claimed that both increasing numbers of customer and brand awareness enhance business performance (Genç and Oksuz, 2015; Sarkar and Ghosal, 2018; Zhao et al., 2017). Participant 20-F suggested that making entrepreneurs should only aim gained more followers and ensure they are active at all time. However, the key important factors to improve social media business are having a future plan and choosing a specific platform.

Future Plan – based on this idea major of the participant major plans is to increase the number of customers online and establishing a personal website or blog; for instance, participant 1-M future plan is to build up a local social media platform in new few months. Surprisingly 6 participants plan to improve their social media marketing by posting videos and image content of their business. This links with Ukpere, Slabbert & Ukpere (2014), which states that social media platforms generate a lot, such as promoting and helping sales and brand awareness.

Significant Platform – This research found that entrepreneurs specifically preferred to used Facebook and Instagram platform, among other platforms, to engage with customers, given that they are commonly used across the globe. For instance, 12 participants expressed that Facebook and Instagram are much better than any social media network. Equally, ElAydi (2018) argued that Facebook and Instagram enable online communities' activities, interaction, sharing of content, accessibility and credibility because they are widely used.

These results supported by quantitative study's results that a significant number of entrepreneurs shown agreement on "*I have already set up my next social media goals*". Moreover, these results are supported and validated by these entrepreneurs in the quantitative study that "*Social media adoption has benefited my business a lot*".

Irrespective of the positive benefit of social media marketing impact in an entrepreneur's business development, this study argued that understanding factors affecting or may negatively influence the business operation of organisations is very important to the success of entrepreneurial online business activities. In this context, participant's opinions indicated that fakes brand review, technical problem, time-consuming and algorithm are the core barriers of entrepreneurs in social media marketing. Thus, a similar result has been obtained by several studies. As Bauer, Grether and Leach (2002) and Venkatesh & Davis (2000) identified, low capital, time, training and negative view about social media and low knowledge of technology. This is also consistent with the literature, which claimed a lack of the identified factors was recognised as an important problem to social media marketing (Michaelidou, Siamagka, & Christodoulides, 2011).

Fake Brand Review – following the findings of this study, it is confirmed by 4 participants that fake reviews of the company's brand on social media affect the development of entrepreneurs in business performance. Consistent with prior studies on the impact of customer comment on the brand (Yuan, & Peluso, 2020; Wisker, 2020; Kendall et al., 2019). For instance, Wisker (2020) identified that a brand's fake review violates Muslim entrepreneurs moral code, belief and value that affect organisational growth and performance.

Technical Problem – In many cases, the main reason for some entrepreneurs' reluctance to explored social media marketing tools is a lack of technical skills (Michaelidou, Siamagka & Christodoulides, 2011). For instance, a few participants identified technical skills as a barrier to social media marketing; yet the majority of the participants, both male and female

entrepreneurs, believed to have technical skills required to utilise social media marketing tools to engage and create their brand awareness online. This complement vest opinions in the literature which identified technical skill as the key solution to effective social media marketing activities (Matikiti, Mpinganjira, & Roberts-Lombard, 2018; Garg & Pahuja, 2020)

6.3.3 Performance Measurement

This study proposes that entrepreneurs require considerable measurement of their company's performance, engagement, and impressions from people by seeking customers' opinions, communicating, analysing feedback, and responding to feedback (Palalic et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Sundararaj & Rejeesh, 2021). For these reasons, this study identified social media brand awareness, customers feedback, social media interaction and social media use for communication as a significant measure to improve entrepreneurial online business operations.

6.3.3.1 Brand Awareness

This indicates the activity of entrepreneurs on social media to engage people with their products information, content and values to attract more customers. Thus, Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) encouraged entrepreneurs to ensure that brand awareness encompasses qualities that differentiate their brand from its competitors to gain a competitive advantage. The result now provides evidence that through brand awareness, organisations could measure their business performance; as many of the participants indicated, social media could be used to make products known to customers online. A similar pattern of results was obtained in Zhao et al. (2017), who found that brand awareness can impact positively on prediction and boosts product loyalty. Given that entrepreneurs could increase their product awareness through social media business.

However, the observed difference between male and female participants in this study was significant. A majority of the female participants believed that social media business stimulates brand awareness of which enlighten customers about the company's products value. For instance, participant 20 -F, who aimed to advocate for healthy food through social media marketing, concludes that social media is the utmost marketing element that could be used to connect with many shoppers (Alhaddad, 2015).

On the other hand, the male participants argued that brand awareness through social media motives numerous customers to get in contact often by posting current information on products, which in turn improve sales performance. From the results, it is certain that social media brand awareness directly influences an entrepreneur's food business (Timilsina, 2017). Conclusively participant -2- M and 3 -M claimed that brand awareness results in business growth, given that social media facilitates online communities, interaction, sharing of content, accessibility and credibility of entrepreneur's business (ElAydi, 2018; Fernández-Miguélez et al., 2020).

The quantitative findings also revealed that the majority of the entrepreneurs use social media for brand awareness. The study also found a positive relationship between brand awareness and entrepreneurial experiences (see Table 54). Therefore, this result is supported and validated by survey (online questionnaire) analysis (See Section 5.6.3)

6.3.3.2 Customer Feedback

According to Tajvidi et al. (2018), customers feedback is the data, perception and feedback of customers opinion about the company's products and services. Because of this notion, a further novel finding is that social media form a medium through which entrepreneurs could improve their product and service. Thus, it is recommended that organisations not only advertise their business on social media but also often seek customer reviews about their products and services (Fundin and Bergman, 2003).

More importantly, this study contended that positive, negative feedback, appreciation feedback and direct message feedback are important for business improvement purposes; hence analysing this feedback could provide solution and strategies required to improve both business performance and customer satisfaction (Keizers, 2015). For this reason, participants suggested that an organisation of all type should often obtain feedback from customers separately to be aware of their strengths and weaknesses.

Furthermore, it was understood that responding to customer feedback through direct message is the best method of reducing customers negative word of mouth and improved their satisfaction. Others have shown that responding to customer feedback often improves both sales and customers buying intention (Hanaysha, 2017; Ramanathan, Subramanian, and Parrott, 2017). On the other hand, some male participants reviewed that customer feedback could be best obtained through SurveyMonkey and Hootsuite to monitor the feedback. Similarly, a pattern of results was obtained in Grimes (2018); Erkan and Evans (2018); Kamboj et al. (2018) argued that effective customer feedback could be obtained through the survey, email and contact form, on-site activity and instant feedback from website to obtain customer feedback. For instance, Erkan and Evan (2018) identified that customers' anonymous feedback is more significant to customer purchase intention. Hence social media business review could lead to customers trust and loyalty (Kamboj et al., 2018).

The quantitative study findings also revealed that the majority of the entrepreneurs use social media for customer feedback. The study also found a positive relationship between customer feedback and entrepreneurial experiences (see Table 54). Therefore, this result is supported and validated by survey (online questionnaire) analysis (See Section 5.6.4)

6.3.3.3 Social Media Communication

This study proposed that social media communication and interaction influence how entrepreneurs interact with customer and generate effective opportunities that promote organisation development (Khajeheian, 2013). As the participants believed that social media communication provides easy and flexible interactions with prospective customers (Genç and Oksuz, 2015; Sarkar and Ghosal, 2018). Thus, it is worth discussing these interesting facts revealed by the results of this study of which identified content marketing, regular updating, hashtags, introducing promotion and direct messaging on various platforms as described below by participant 3 -M

"We always interact with customers via Facebook Instagram or Snapchat by introducing new promotions do you offer us new products and so on. We also interact with other customers on national holidays and summer holidays as well as keep our customers up to date with the latest trends like football matches update etc. We also interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback, and we also listen to complaints if anything creates inconvenience to the customers" (Participant- 3-M).

Marketing Content - The result now provides evidence that marketing content is one of the most important ways of communicating with customers. As participants indicated, they keep in touch with customers through products content sharing or posting (i.e. picture and details) using different social media platforms. A similar conclusion was reached by Olanrewaju et al. (2018) argued that posting or sharing product content on platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat improve brand awareness and sales.

Regular Updating - From these results, it is clear that the constant posting of product content or pictures with the newest update helps entrepreneurs to interact or communicate with customers. A similar result has been obtained by numerous which ascertained that product

updating is another way of keeping the customer informed and it improves customer loyalty and satisfaction (Oham, Kokkranikal, & Coca-Stefaniak, 2019; Olanrewaju et al., 2018).

Introducing Product Promotion - For entrepreneurs to flourish in any given environment he/she must engage in product promotion; to attract customers and generate a direct image of their organisation. Thus, participants suggested that all entrepreneurs introduce promotional activities for two key reasons: regular interaction with customers and the company's expansion. These ideas supported the assertion in the literature, which documented that product promotion enhances both business growth and financial performance (Deželjin, Bienenfeld, & Turkalj, 2017; Sinha & Verma, 2020).

Direct Messaging - The results confirm that this a good choice for social media communication for entrepreneurial business. As described by participant 9-M who indicated that to improve and create the awareness of products, entrepreneurial people must engage in direct message interaction and immediate response to customers comments. Overall, these findings are in accordance with the findings reported by Azar et al. (2016); Hammick and Ju (2016) argued that creating a page/profile on social media such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter could help both entrepreneurs and its managers interact and respond to customers reviews.

The quantitative study findings also showed that the majority of the entrepreneurs use social media for communication purposes. The study also found a positive relationship between social media for communication and entrepreneurial experiences (see Table 54). Therefore, this result is supported and validated by survey (online questionnaire) analysis (See Section 5.6.4).

6.4 Similarities and Differences among Muslim Entrepreneurs

This section compares and contrasts the views of both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs about the impact of gender on using social media marketing in UK SMEs in the food industry.

The results from both studies, i.e. in-depth interviews and online survey, report several views in common. Similarities include social media marketing as a marketing tool and online platforms for communication, engagement, interactions, brand awareness, receive and respond to customer's feedback about the food products and services.

The study has shown that entrepreneurs can differentiate significant social media platforms for marketing in food SMEs. However, both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs demonstrated a lack of technical skills as a barrier to social media marketing which may not be significant for successful and effective marketing. This presents the implications for small and medium-sized food businesses in the context of social media marketing uses, as there is a possibility that entrepreneurs will be unable to differentiate between significant and insignificant social media platforms marketing.

Both Muslim male entrepreneurs and female entrepreneurs have different experiences to run the food SMEs. Comparing and contrasting the two gender, male and female entrepreneurs, based on their actions, their management, and their decision-making show how different and similar the two are. Both entrepreneurs are experienced and believed that social media for business depended on the effective use of social media. They also found significant social media platforms, which are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat. Entrepreneurs have identified that these significant social media platforms are easily accessible and have enabled them to share food pictures, increasing brand awareness, communicating products and services, and interacting with customers.

Despite a similar interest, there are several differences in the experience of gender on Muslim entrepreneurs utilising social media marketing in the food SMEs. Female entrepreneurs, for example, revealed that UK food industries are inspired to set-up their own social media business pages or profiles for food SMEs and ranked Instagram, Facebook and Snapchat mainly employed platforms for their businesses because Instagram is easy to use and essential for food business.

On the other hand, male entrepreneurs ranked Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube mainly employed social media platforms and believed that Facebook has the highest number of followers and more features than any other platform. Both entrepreneurs have several different technical experiences as well as a similar marketing technique. Yet female entrepreneurs claimed that social media insights and analytics tools helped analyse both business performance and customer behaviours, while male entrepreneurs claimed that social media analytics helped create marketing strategies that promote business activities.

Both entrepreneurs also share and differ in their business goals; from gender point onward, female entrepreneurs surprisingly indicated that organisations must gain more customers to promote brand awareness on social media, create plans, and focus on a specific social media platform for successful business marketing. On the other hand, male entrepreneurs use social media to gain more customer, increase sales revenue, and promote brand awareness. This difference and advantage have more to do with female entrepreneurs compared to that of male entrepreneurs. Female entrepreneurs have identified that involving in social media business stimulates brand awareness that enlightens customers about its products' value and encourages their competitors and believed SMM in Halal food could proliferate by supporting each other. Both agreed that Social media as a marketing tool is the most significant constructive pathway of communicating with customers online, as social media marketing tools promote accessible communication with customers online.

Content marketing, regular updating, hashtags, introducing promotion and direct messaging on various platforms as the core elements of social media communication. Moreover, receiving customer feedback through direct messaging is the best way to reduce customers' negative word of mouth and improve their satisfaction. Even though both male entrepreneurs and female entrepreneurs are the main drivers of the food SMEs, they have experienced several differences and similarities.

6.5 The Main Lesson from the Research (Research Contribution)

By empirically exploring the conceptual research framework (see Figure 3), this thesis makes an important contribution to the literature on entrepreneurship, gender and social media marketing. In the literature, entrepreneurship suggested one of the main wheels of economic growth and new development. In recent time, an extensive level of investigations has recognised the relations between entrepreneurship and social media marketing development. However, this study explored the entrepreneurial social media marketing phenomenon in the context of gender. Meyer (2018) suggested females experiences dissimilar barriers and challenges as compared to their male's counterpart; consequently, mainly gender oriented research of entrepreneurship could assist in the development and improvement of female entrepreneurship.

Having said that current research gap in the study, this research exclusively focused on the impact of gender on both Muslim male and female entrepreneurs towards the use of social media marketing in the food-related SMEs in the UK. This study looked at gender-specific entrepreneurship perspective, but not the religious perspective. The findings from this study are novel and can help several different stakeholders such as academics, entrepreneurs, organisations, managers and marketing practitioners.

The current literature mainly examined each type of entrepreneurship separately (Hair et al., 2012). There are several significant implications of social media marketing in numerous aspects of business, such as social media communication, interaction, brand awareness, engagement and customer feedback. A limited understanding of the impacts of social media marketing on food businesses with the lens of gender. Therefore, this study contributes to the literature by examining the impact of gender used social media marketing on Muslim entrepreneurship.

Social media marketing employment and its importance must be considered significant more than a simple technology adoption (Richter et al., 2013). It is argued that utilisation of social media marketing has several impacts on entrepreneurial decisions. Thus, this research contributes to the current literature by undertaking an in-depth analysis and highlighting the entrepreneurial experiences of social media marketing. This study also established a theoretical research framework with the application of gender, entrepreneurship and social media marketing use in the food-related SMEs in the UK. The social media marketing platforms suggested various supporting roles in marketing activities that can create a synergy to enhance the performance of an organisation. Therefore, this study established the framework based on the elements of social media marketing to provide a comprehensive understanding of social media as a marketing tool to advance marketing activities.

Moreover, this research followed a mixed-method approach in the study. Therefore, in addition to the academic contribution, the study also contributed to research methodology pertaining to exploring the gender experiences of Muslim male and female entrepreneurs' social media marketing uses in food SMEs in the UK.

This study contributes several significant practical benefits that may enhance entrepreneurial marketing knowledge and marketing management within the food-related SMEs in the UK. Firstly, gender impacts entrepreneurial actions and their experiences might contribute to improving marketing strategies. Paulauskaite et al. (2017) argued that customers' demand for customised and authentic products increased; advanced marketing techniques might enhance business performance. Secondly, the Entrepreneurial view on social media marketing has vital recommendations for business owners and managers on what social media platforms significantly impact food SMEs. To employ powerful social media platforms to initiate the marketing activity for the food business, the manager should consider the social media platform's accessible features.

In addition, the current study points out that social media as a marketing tool has enabled entrepreneurs to enhance their marketing skills and increase the opportunities in communication, interaction, brand awareness, receive positive and negative feedback on the product and respond to the feedback. The British Muslim consumer's growth is a large part of the market, not limited to British Muslims. Moreover, marketing expertise under which gender influences entrepreneurial actions could inform why some businesses in the food industry fail. Therefore, this study provides an understanding to the social media marketing managers, practitioners and entrepreneurs to become fully experienced in utilising social media marketing strategies and techniques to cope with the challenges.

Finally, findings indicated that food businesses employ social media marketing to support several marketing activities (e.g., communication, interaction, brand awareness, receive positive and negative feedback), which aim to increase the companies' performance. Social media marketing is a new, inevitable managerial style to the marketing systems by using social media platforms.

6.6 Research Limitations

Every research has limitations to some extent; this study encompasses several research limitations and given as follows:

- One of the most significant limitations was time. Due to time constraint, the researcher was only able to gather qualitative data from south England (London), Midlands (Birmingham) and North West of England (Manchester, Bradford, Leeds and Sheffield) instead of the whole UK.
- The researcher purpose was to recruit the participants from different Muslim ethnic backgrounds in the interviews study. However, the researcher could only visit the majority of the cities that had south Asian majority businesses, which put the limitation on the researcher to search research participants from non-south Asian backgrounds such as Arabs, Muslim Africans, Caucasian Muslims etc. The researcher could manage to recruit 1 non-Asian British participant from the restaurant industry.
- The researcher found that time constraint was an important limitation in conducting the interviews with Muslim entrepreneurs in this research. The researcher also faced time management issues from the participant's side, so interviews were rescheduled on many occasions. Furthermore, the interview process was disrupted on many occasions, as one of the interviews was conducted inside the shop (Participant-2). Indeed, some interviews were carried out in two parts (Participant-12). Thus, in future researchers must allow sufficient time to conduct the interviews (at least 3 or 4 hours) with Muslim entrepreneurs and set up the appropriate venue before conducting the interview.
- Another main limitation was COVID-19. Because the research was on food businesses and due to virus issues, the second phase of the study was majorly affected.
- Sampling was initially considered another limitation of this research. In the case of sampling, the researcher has chosen the samples for both the interviews and online

questionnaire accordingly with methodological rigour. However, the researcher could not collect the questionnaire's desired sample size in the second stage of the study because of COVID-19, since Coronavirus has majorly affected the entrepreneurs running a food business in the UK.

- Conducting interviews with female entrepreneurs was considered another limitation in this study. Since this research recruited both gender male and female participants, female Muslims were hesitant to let the researcher conduct face-to-face interviews due to cultural background. However, interviews with female entrepreneurs went smoothly and in an excellent manner over the phone. Consequently, female Muslim entrepreneurs feel much more informative and expressive over the phone.

6.7 Future of Research

This study aimed to explore the experiences of the Muslim entrepreneur and their impacts on the employment of social media marketing activities in especially their food businesses. Findings suggested that Instagram and Facebook are mainly employed social media platforms by Muslim entrepreneurs in food SMEs. Therefore, future research in further social media platforms marketing on these two platforms is suggested. Unlike gender impact, religion is also an important perspective in any culture; thus, this study suggests future research can be looked at from religious perspectives to explore the gender specific entrepreneurship using SMM for their businesses.

Also, this research area can be extended by including the participation of other religious minorities such as Christianity and Hinduism etc., with British values. Similarly, demographic characteristics recommended in future researches (Islam and Kirillova, 2020) because these characteristics shape the entrepreneurial actions. It will be significant to examine how other demographics characterises such as age, education and socioeconomic background combined to shape entrepreneurial experiences of both genders.

This research inferred the phase two quantitative results with small sample size; in the future, the researcher must increase the number of participants in an online questionnaire, particularly in the area of the UK Mainland where the majority of the Muslim population live. Furthermore, this study has indicated the extensive use of social media marketing by Muslim entrepreneurs in the UK. Findings also indicated that the majority of female entrepreneurs used Instagram social media platform for marketing in SMEs. Hence, future research can further explore the female specific entrepreneurial experiences using Instagram in the context of B2B networks, and customer engagement recommended.

6.8 Managerial Implications

Due to widespread growth in social media users, it is not surprising that entrepreneurs have shown a high level of interest in social media marketing. Managers have taken attention into account to look at marketing opportunity, such as social media uses. Social media marketing useful for businesses to be more dynamic with their consumers. There are several useful implications and directions made for entrepreneurs such as marketing practitioners to initiate and formulate social media marketing strategies on food SMEs in the UK from the contributions of this study. One of the significant roles for managers is to recognise what is meant to be social media marketing and how it can be usefully employed when making decisions concerning marketing activities. The results from this research findings provide important and valuable insights from these opportunities.

Entrepreneurial perspective on social media marketing has vital suggestions for business managers what social media platforms significantly impact food SMEs. In order to employ significant social media platforms to initiate the marketing activity for the food business, the manager should consider the social media platform's accessible features.

Both the qualitative and quantitative findings of this research also indicate that Facebook and Instagram are the mainly employed social media platforms other than Twitter and Snapchat among food-related small and medium-sized businesses. Because these are easily accessible, have the largest number of followers (Facebook), suitable for food (Instagram), privacy, and more importantly, provides insights and analytical reports to design the marketing strategy.

The research also points out the employment of social media as a marketing tool that has enabled the entrepreneurs to rich their marketing expertise and develop opportunities in communication, interaction, brand awareness, receive positive and negative feedback on product and respond to back the feedback. The British Muslim consumers' growth is a potential segment of the market, which is not limited to only British Muslim entrepreneurs. Thus, this research informs the mainstream businesses as an opportunity to identify market gaps in this consumer segment and make the products and services available to them where Muslim consumer would be satisfied with their growing needs.

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1: Participant Introduction Letter (Information sheet)

Participant Introduction Letter

Dear Participant;

I Mudassar Sohail am a post graduate research student at University of the West of Scotland. For my doctoral thesis, I am conducting this interview to investigate the role of male and female Muslim entrepreneurs towards the use of Social Media Marketing on their businesses. The main aim(s)/Objective(s) of this study is to explore the gender experience of Muslim entrepreneurs employing Social Media Marketing strategies for their businesses in the UK.

The following interview questionnaire will be last for 40 minutes. Please answer all of the questions as accurately as you can. There are no right or wrong answers and if at any point you feel uncomfortable answering these questions, you may skip the questions.

Please note that collected data of this study will be used for research purposes and your all information will remain confidential. Interviewer, director of studies (DOS) and the university all have the access to collected data. Please also note that all the given responses will be kept anonymous throughout the research and you will not be identified anyway.

The results of this research will be used to help the Muslim entrepreneurs to understand Social Media Marketing usage for their business.

Thank you of your participation.

Best Regards

Researcher

Mudassar Sohail

Email: [REDACTED]

Director of Studies

Dr. Pravin Balaraman

Email: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Note: If you have any question concerning this interview questionnaire before interview please contact me on above email.

APPENDIX 2: Consent Form

Consent Form

Dear Invitees,

As a part of my doctorate study at University of the West of Scotland, I am undertaking research looking at gender experience of Muslim male and female entrepreneurs employing social media marketing for their businesses in the UK. The interview will contain questions on gender, social media, entrepreneurship and associated practices. If at any point you feel uncomfortable answering these questions, you may skip the questions. Please note that responses will be kept anonymous throughout the project and you will not be identified in any way. You can also withdraw your participation at a later stage. I would like to record the interview.

Interviewee

- I agree to participate in this interview.
- I understand that I have read the above form.
- I agree to have this interview recorded.

If you want to ask me anything prior to interview about these questions please contact me on this email Personal details withheld.

Thank you very much of your contribution.

Interviewee's signature Date

Interviewer's signature Date

APPENDIX 3: Research Interview Protocol Guide

Research Interview Protocol Guide

I Mudassar Sohail am a post graduate research student at University of the West of Scotland. For my doctoral thesis, I am conducting this interview to investigate the role of male and female Muslim entrepreneurs towards the use of Social Media Marketing for their businesses. The main aim(s)/Objective(s) of this study are to explore the gender experiences of Muslim entrepreneurs employing Social Media Marketing strategies for their businesses in the UK.

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The results of this research will be used to help the Muslim entrepreneurs to understand Social Media Marketing usage for their business.

The interview Questions for this research are as followed;

Demographics

Hi, can you please interduce me yourself, such as ethnic backgrounds, gender, age, marital status etc?

Can you please tell me your business foundation, type of business and your roles at your business in detail?

The following research interview questions will be asked (not particularly in the same format):

What is your initial perception about social media?

How and when did you start using the social media for personal use?

How long you have been using social media marketing for your business? Why?

- What types of social media platforms/channels you are using for your business? What are the names please?
- Why have you chosen these specific social media platforms/channels?
- Has it really contributed into the business life? How and why?
- How each of these platforms contributed individually?
- How do you use them?
- Do you have any social media Goal? Have you achieved?
- Do you face any problems while using social media?
- If yes, how have you resolved this problem?

Adding to this, would you like to share any occurred social media experience (whether negative or positive?)

What types of social media communication trends you are following in your business?

Are any of your business competitors using social media? If yes, do they have any impact on your business?

What is the main aim of using social media for your business?

Do you use any social media automation tools to measure the business performance such as Hootsuite or Klout?

Do you think these automation social media tools are helpful? How do they help you to measure the progress?

What types of technologies and techniques you use to measure the quality of social media campaign?

What do you think social media is an opportunity in today's world for Muslim Entrepreneurs? Can you explain this why?

Being a male/female entrepreneur to what extent you benefit from social media adoption, and why?

Being a Muslim male/female entrepreneur how would you suggest that which channel is more significant for your business?

Being a male/female do you face any barriers that prevent the use of social media?

Do you think social media marketing is cost effective for your business being a male/female, how?

Do you use social media paid ads for your business? What types of ads?

Do you have any plan of adopting social media in next 12 month? What type of social media you will use? What is your goal?

How do you interact with your customers on social media?

How do you monitor customer feedback on social media sites?

How regularly you maintain or manage your social media sites for communication?

Furthermore, would you like to tell us any other experience in regard to the usage of social media as a marketing tool for your business?

APPENDIX 4: Quantitative Questionnaire

QUANTITATIVE QUESTIONNAIRES

TOPIC

Social media marketing: the impact of gender in the experience of Muslim entrepreneurs in UK food industry.

AIM(S) OF THE RESEARCH

The overall aim of this research is to explore the gender experience of Muslim entrepreneurs using social media marketing strategies for their food businesses in the UK.

WHY HAVE YOU BEEN CHOSEN?

You have been chosen for the research as a business owner/manager/director.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE INFORMATION I GIVE?

The information that you give will be kept strictly confidential. Your identity will not be disclosed to anyone except only myself and my supervisor will be allowed to look at the answers that you give. All data collected from those taking part will be analysed together so it will be impossible to identify you individually or your company. The study will be written up in my thesis and hopefully later in published in academic journals.

INSTRUCTIONS

The enclosed questionnaire focuses on social media marketing and its employment by Muslim entrepreneurs running food businesses in the UK. Completion should not take more than 10 minutes of your time.

Please complete the questionnaire in your convenience and you may skip any questions at any stage during the survey.

Thank you in anticipation of your help. Yours truly,

CLASSIFICATION DATA

Participant's Job Role;

1. Director 2. Senior manger

Participant's Location;

London Birmingham Manchester Glasgow Bradford Overall UK

Type of food business:

Fast food Restaurant. Takeaway Desserts Food Bloggers. Wholesaler

Business Name:

How Long have you been running this business?

1 – 3 Years 4 – 6 Years 7 – 10 Years 11+ Years

Your Age Group;

18 - 24 25 - 34 35 - 44 45 - 54 Over 55

Ethnicity:

British British Pakistani British Indian British Bangladeshi Other Muslim

Gender:

Male Female prefer not to say

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

The following statements represent social media marketing strategies. Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.

Social Media (SM) uses:

I use SM to engage with customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I use SM to keep customers updated about my products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I use SM for networking.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I use SM to build relationship with customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I mainly use Facebook for my food business.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I mainly use Instagram for my food business.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I mainly use Twitter for my food business.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I mainly use Snapchat for my food business.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I use all SM channels i.e. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, & Snapchat.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I go live with my followers to interact with them.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media is very cost effective.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I use Social media paid ads that are very helpful.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I keep my customers up-to-date with the latest trends.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

The following statements represent social media marketing communication activities by Muslim entrepreneurs. Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.

SM Communication:

I communicate with my customers to see if they happy with my services

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I follow the hashtags to communicate with customers

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I follow the customers' like on my shared post to communicate with them.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I follow the customers' comments on my shared post to communicate with them.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

In order to communicate with customers, I promote the offers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

In order to communicate with customers, I promote new products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge with customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I communicate regularly to update my social media to build the bridge with the business.
Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

The following statements represent the interaction on social media by Muslim entrepreneurs. Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.

SM interaction:

My social media enable information-sharing with others.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I usually post on social media to interact with customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I generally share the posts on social media from other customers that are tagged to our profile.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I mainly interact with customers via social media by introducing new promotions.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

It is easy to provide my opinion through my social media to my customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I upload food pictures on social media that is the way to interact with customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media enable the business to interact with customers through 1-to-1 messaging about services.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

**The following statements represent social media brand awareness marketing strategies.
Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.**

Customer/Brand Awareness:

I use SM heavily for my business awareness.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Content of my social media seems interesting.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Content of my social media is the newest information.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I pass the information on products from my social media profiles to my customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I pass the information on my services from my social media profiles to my customers.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Using social media is very trendy.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helps to customise the products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helps to customise the services.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

**The following statements represent response to customer feedback on social media.
Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.**

Customer Feedback:

Social media helps the businesses to receive the positive feedback about the products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helps the businesses to receive the negative feedback about the products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine positive feedback about the products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helps the customers to leave the genuine negative feedback about the products.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I directly respond them back if someone message me on social media.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I interact with customers to appreciate them for their feedback.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I interact with customers to listen the complaints if anything creates inconvenience to them.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

The following statements represent the degree of gender experience using social media marketing strategies for their food businesses. Please indicate the extent to which you agree/disagree.

Gender experience:

Social media is an opportunity in today's world for Muslim entrepreneurs.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media adoption has benefited my business a lot.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

Social media helped me to know more about customer preferences,

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I have already set up my next social media plan for 12 months.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I regularly maintain the social media sites.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I regularly update the social media sites.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

I don't have any barriers using social media for my business.

Strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly disagree

APPENDIX 5: Demographics of Research Participants in Interviews

Interviewee(s)	Job Role	Gender	Location
Participant 1	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 2	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 3	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 4	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 5	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 6	Senior Manager	Female	Bradford
Participant 7	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 8	Director	Male	London
Participant 9	Director	Male	London
Participant 10	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 11	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 12	Director	Male	Birmingham
Participant 13	Senior Manager	Male	Manchester
Participant 14	Director	Male	Manchester
Participant 15	Director	Male	Leeds
Participant 16	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 17	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 18	Director	Female	Manchester
Participant 19	Director	Female	London
Participant 20	Director	Female	London